

Economic Growth in Global Value Chains

Lessons from the Golden Age with a New Input-Output Decomposition Framework and Database

Krisztián KOPPÁNY^{1*} – Péter VAKHAL²

¹ Kautz Gyula Faculty of Business and Economics, Department of International and Applied Economics, Széchenyi István University, Győr, Hungary, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4235-5817>, koppany.krisztian@sze.hu

² Department of Operations Research and Actuarial Sciences, Corvinus University, Kopint-Tárki Institute for Economic Research, Budapest, Hungary, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0167-5515>, peter.vakhal@kopint-tarki.hu

* corresponding author

This paper introduces a novel dynamic method for global value chain (GVC) analysis, moving beyond static frameworks that decompose nominal variables, such as gross exports or value added. Instead, it breaks down year-by-year real economic growth, considering contributions from value-added sources, final producers, users, and different types of value chains: pure domestic, traditional trade, and simple and complex GVCs. The approach, based on input-output theory, is demonstrated with a numerical example, applied to the WIOD and Long-run WIOD datasets to create the GVC Growth Contribution Database (GVC-GCD). Preliminary analyses with the GVC-GCD offer new insights into GVC growth, revealing that GVCs predate the term and influence global growth steadily over time despite short-term fluctuations, differences between large and small, developed and developing, more specialised or diversified economies. With few exceptions, growth contributions, including those of international ones, have decreased over time. In the long run, while trade and GVCs benefited many countries, they could not fully offset the decline in the contributions of domestic value chains. This historical perspective offers lessons for current policy. The GVC-GCD can serve as a tool for future empirical studies and growth modelling, with potential to expand across space, time, and levels of detail as data availability improves.

Keywords / JEL Classification: economic growth, global value chains, input-output analysis, decompositions, GVC Growth Contribution Database (GVC-GCD)

This working paper was prepared for and presented at the 22nd EUROFRAME CONFERENCE ON ECONOMIC POLICY ISSUES IN EUROPE: SHAPING EUROPEAN INDUSTRIES IN AN ERA OF TRANSITIONS hosted by CPB Netherlands Bureau for Economic Policy Analysis, held on Friday 12 June 2026. This version is circulated for discussion and comment purposes. To cite this paper use DOI link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20535821>

1 Introduction

Year-by-year volume indices of gross domestic product (GDP) or its basic-price equivalent, gross value added (GVA), which is the focus of this study, are still the primary indicators of economic development. They reflect the rate of real economic growth and have been measured and recorded by official statistics (or at least estimated) in most countries since the 1960s. Their global average shows a declining long-run trend since then; however, there are significant short-run differences across countries.

Since the golden age of growth in the 1960s (Crafts, 1995; Temin, 1997), the world has changed in many ways. Primarily, it has become much smaller. Of course, the distances have not physically decreased; rather, the difficulties in overcoming them have. The decline in

transportation and other costs, along with the gradual dismantling of barriers that hinder the development and maintenance of economic relations between countries—thanks to so-called trade liberalisation—has led countries to become increasingly open. Not only has the value and volume of traditional (final product) foreign trade grown rapidly, but so has that of semi-finished products. The fragmentation of production activities has led to the formation of so-called global value chains (GVCs) (Gereffi, 1994), in which countries participate at different stages of production based on comparative advantage. Within this framework, through direct foreign investments, the world's developed centres often relocated certain activities to less developed, so-called peripheral countries offering cheaper labour or more favourable regulations, mainly to ensure the supply of inputs, reduce costs, or get closer to and gain access to new markets. These processes, which characterised the golden age of globalisation (Michie, 2017), seemed to be reversing after the 2008-2009 Great Financial Crisis and in recent years due to the resurgence of trade and military conflicts (among other factors, e.g., automation, pandemics, etc.) and the elevated levels of risk and risk perception (Baldwin & Freeman, 2022). The era of soaring globalisation has been followed by some slowing, uncertainty, back- and near-shoring, restructuring and rewiring, with policies prioritising inclusivity, resilience, and sustainability to rebuild trust in global economic cooperation (WTO, 2023, 2025).

The phenomena described above significantly influence the structure of production, value-added generation, and economic growth. What does this mean? In the textbook model of a closed economy, there are purely domestic value chains. The final products are produced by domestic manufacturers that use only domestic suppliers, and are sold exclusively to domestic final users. There is no export for either production or final consumption purposes, and similarly, no import of the previous types. In a closed economy, therefore, the entire value added is produced by domestic value chains, and only these can ensure economic growth.

By contrast, in an open economy, alongside domestic value chains, traditional foreign trade and global value chains also contribute to growth. In traditional foreign trade, only final products produced either directly or indirectly by domestic producers, without the import of semi-finished products, are sold abroad. Global value chains, however, are characterised by intensive international trade in semi-finished products. If only a single such crossing of borders occurs, it is considered simple; if at least two crossings of semi-finished and/or finished products occur, they are called complex global value chains.¹

The emergence of global value chains has also created a need to examine them. The input-output theory, which forms the methodological basis for their quantitative analysis, was developed nearly a hundred years ago (Leontief, 1936), and has since been in use and continuously evolving. However, the data necessary for these analyses, the so-called world input-output tables and databases, only appeared and widely spread at the beginning of the 2010s. This enabled the development of quantitative analysis of GVCs.

Since the 2010s, global value chains have become a real hot topic. Studies on the subject proliferated rapidly, and schools based on the breakdown of gross exports and gross value added/final product were established, as were indicators to describe GVCs and measure their presence and roles within them (participation, position, length, exposures, etc.). (Backer & Miroudot, 2013; Baldwin et al., 2022, 2023; Baldwin & Freeman, 2022; Fally, 2012; Johnson & Noguera, 2012; Koopman et al., 2010, 2014). The typology of value chains presented above also emerged in the second half of this decade (Wang et al., 2017b).

¹ Of course, in reality, these cases do not appear in pure form: a given value chain may contain elements of all the aforementioned forms in certain proportions.

Some studies have examined the relationships between economic growth and various GVC indicators using econometric methods (Jangam & Rath, 2021a; Luzzati et al., 2026; P et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022). In this paper, we take a different approach. Firstly, we aim to answer the following questions using input-output methods. How can a country's real economic growth in a given year be decomposed into growth contributions caused by the different value chain types presented above? How can these be further broken down by end-product-producing sectors and value-added source industries, as well as by final user countries and sectors? If this is done, it also becomes possible to answer questions such as: in certain years within the analysed period, what level of growth was provided for a given country within a specific value chain type or within the value chain of a specific final product group, for example, in automotive value chains? What types of value chains and what magnitude of growth effects were observed within it? Which final user countries (direct or indirect) are responsible for these through their trade partners' purchases, and to what extent? Or, to what extent can the real growth of final consumption be attributed to different types of value chains, sectors, and partner countries? Real growth contributions bring a completely new approach to GVC analysis and provide a new perspective on the phenomenon.

The questions listed above can be answered using current- and previous-year price world input-output tables and applying specific input-output methods. Currently, only the World Input-Output Database (WIOD) and its historical extension, the Long-run WIOD, are suitable for this purpose. This study aims to produce an annual breakdown of real economic growth by value chain type for the time periods, countries, and sectors covered by these data.

In this paper, we not only present the applied methodology and the resulting GVC growth contribution database (GVC-GCD) generated from WIOD, but also demonstrate its wide-ranging potential uses. In some initial, illustrative analyses, we seek and find answers to the following questions, thereby confirming the database's validity and, hopefully, inspiring the research community to formulate further questions and address them using the GVC-GCD.

First, we examine the issue on a global scale and endeavour to uncover the extent to which the rise of foreign trade and GVC activities has transformed the structure of value-added production and growth. When did this process actually begin? And have international value chains truly achieved the level of dominance suggested by public discourse and, at times, by academic literature, which has somewhat sidelined the role of domestic actors?

Secondly, we explore the diversity behind global growth through comparative analyses at the national level. Which countries have achieved high and low growth, and to what extent have different types of value chains contributed to these outcomes? Among which countries are there similarities in the level and structure of growth? Based on this, how can the countries listed in the WIOD be grouped or clustered? We will see that these analyses will also offer many surprises.

To also provide examples of the potential uses in this direction, we naturally cannot omit econometric analyses. However, these differ significantly from previous ones in that the focus is now not on overall economic growth, but on the growth contributions triggered by different types of value chains, which serve as the dependent variable. Using the created database, we can examine separately how various explanatory variables (the level of development, the size of the domestic market, the degree of specialisation or diversification) influence domestic, traditional foreign trade, and global value chain-driven growth, in which direction, and to what extent.

The results of analyses concerning the end-product value chains and the participation of individual countries in them also yield interesting findings. Finally, we present an example of

breaking down the real growth of final use by value chain, and we explore the long-term relationships between the declining trend in economic growth and its value chain structure by analysing the entire nearly 50-year period covered by the WIOD and the Long-run WIOD.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 places the research into a broader context by providing an overview of the literature on international division of labour, trade, and economic growth. Section 3 describes the methodology. Section 4 illustrates its application with a small numerical example. Section 5 shows how the theoretical framework has been applied to the World Input-Output Database (WIOD) and the Long-run WIOD, and how the original GVC Growth Contribution Database (GVC-GCD) has been created. Section 6 presents the examples of the first analyses performed by using the database. Section 7 discusses the results. Section 8 deals with the limitations, and Section 9 concludes the paper.

2 International division of labour, trade, and economic growth: a literature review

2.1 Theoretical foundations: from autarky to open economy models

The division of labour among people is the cornerstone of every effectively functioning socio-economic structure. As such, it was already present in prehistoric communities. The division of labour, which initially took place within communities and later emerged in trade between them (in modern terminology, ‘international trade’), is a necessary condition for long-term, sustainable development (Barnes, 1966). Sustained economic growth, whether based on a market or a planned economy, cannot be achieved without an international division of labour. Manufacturing companies cannot be competitive without a stable network of suppliers; in the long term, they cannot meet demand, which also hampers the domestic economy's growth.

Classical growth models have primarily examined international trade in terms of imbalances, treating it as a consequence of growth rather than a root cause. These simplified models often assumed a closed, autarkic, two-sector economy with homogeneous productivity (see, for example, Uzawa (1961), Stiglitz (1967)). At the same time, small, capital-poor developing countries, even if initially organised as autarkies, must necessarily open up to the world market and to foreign investors to achieve sustained growth (Berrill, 1960). The incorporation of international trade into growth models—that is, making economies open—represented a significant simplification and a better fit with the empirical evidence. Vanek (1971) demonstrated that, for open economies, export specialisation allows for greater flexibility in the optimal allocation of production factors, and that the import of capital goods which cannot be produced domestically, or can only be produced less efficiently, provides an opportunity to achieve the desired level of investment even through simple trade alone.

2.2 Technological convergence, endogenous growth, institutions, and context

This is particularly true when there is a significant gap in development levels between trading partners, and imports by the less developed country from the developed country serve precisely to bridge this technological gap (Gabisch, 1975). Technological imports from developed countries by emerging or developing economies contribute to faster economic growth in the importing countries (Findlay, 1980), which they achieve partly through improved efficiency and partly through exports to developed countries based on a competitive advantage in factor prices (Balassa, 1978). The Central and Eastern European countries, undergoing systemic transition, for example, based their growth during the transition period on foreign trade, with

imports playing a key role, to such an extent that growth in some economies was demonstrably import-led (Awokuse, 2007).

Vanek (1971) notes, however, that specialisation and the import of technology do not necessarily lead to sustainable, faster growth and improved welfare (measured in terms of per capita consumption) in the long term, as unfavourable changes in terms of trade may undermine all of this. In such cases, without an improvement in the capital-to-labour ratio (increased productivity, or ‘moving up the value chain’ in modern terminology), the economy is unable to achieve a lasting increase in prosperity, even with a trade surplus.

Nevertheless, during the golden age of globalisation, successful emerging economies—that is, those characterised by rapid and robust growth—typically pursued export-oriented economic policies and were thus able to come closer to a state of optimal resource allocation (i.e. when differences in factor productivity across sectors are negligible) than more closed economies. Based on panel data, Feder (1983) found significant total factor productivity differences between exporting and non-exporting sectors; however, due to export-oriented economic policies, this gap narrows in emerging economies, driven by favourable factor flows. All this is the result of spillover effects from positive externalities, which were not reflected in market prices and also helped less productive sectors through more advanced technological adaptation, access to imported inputs, and better capacity utilisation. Feder (1983), however, notes that the rapid growth in export-led emerging and developing countries is not guaranteed to be sustainable due to diminishing returns and increasing exposure to export markets, particularly if there is no technological development in the economy.

By contrast, in trade between developed countries, faster growth can be achieved through the spillover of endogenous technological progress, fuelled by strong global competition. Thus, developed countries are also encouraged to pursue export-oriented economic policies and dismantle trade barriers among themselves, as this allows for faster growth and improved prosperity through expanding markets. In the case of emerging and developing countries, however, it may be desirable to protect young industries in order to facilitate catching up and capacity building, which may necessitate the temporary introduction of protectionist measures. All this may have temporary positive allocative effects on labour and capital, even if technological progress is negatively affected by restrictions on the flow of knowledge (Rivera-Batiz & Romer, 1991).

Empirical evidence shows that the impact of exports on growth varies widely across economies. The magnitude of this impact depends heavily on the level of economic development and the associated export structure. The comparative advantage of developing countries is generally found in low-value-added goods; as economic development progresses, this shifts towards labour-intensive goods; finally, in developed countries, high-tech, capital-intensive goods form the basis of comparative advantage. Economic development, therefore, strongly influences export capacity and the benefits derived from exports. According to Dodaro (1991), for developing countries, an export-oriented economic policy does not result in significant additional growth, as these countries have only limited export capacity; indeed, it may even have an adverse effect. The growth effect improves with export diversification, naturally to a greater extent the more high-value-added goods the economy can produce. The findings of Dodaro (1991) and other researchers, based on correlation analysis, OLS regression, and Granger causality analysis (Jung & Marshall, 1985; Yaghmaian, 1994), also indicate that the direct link between exports and growth assumed in neoclassical theories is highly conditional. Later, Frankel and Romer (1999) used a regression model incorporating instrumental variables to demonstrate that the average effect of trade (exports and imports) on

welfare and growth is positive (their sample was not disaggregated by level of development), the magnitude of which depends on the geographical distance from import and export markets as well as the size of the domestic market. The relationship between trade intensity and geographical distance has also been confirmed by others using gravity models (De Groot et al., 2004), as has the positive impact on incomes (Gervais, 2015); however, these models do not account for dependence on development levels.

In endogenous growth models (Lucas, 1988; Romer, 1986), exports are among the main drivers of endogenous growth factors (innovation, knowledge spillovers, and knowledge accumulation). With the removal of trade barriers, the expanding market and increased competition act as incentives for research and development processes, placing economies under constant pressure to innovate. Technology spillovers lead to faster economic growth, which is more pronounced in more open economies (Grossman & Helpman, 1991), thus exports have come to the forefront of dynamic growth models, in contrast to neoclassical models (Afonso, 2001). Trade can transmit knowledge not only through competitive pressure and scale effects, but also through ‘embodied’ technology in intermediate inputs. This mechanism provides a direct link between openness and productivity growth (Keller, 2002).

In endogenous models, institutions come to the fore in the better utilisation of the benefits derived from trade, which can be assessed from several perspectives; on the one hand, the need for market expansion necessitates the gradual dismantling of trade barriers; on the other hand, alongside firms, the institutional system also plays a key role in creating a supportive innovation environment and in developing human capital. This approach is reflected in Dollar and Kraay (2003) growth model, in which both exports and institutions have a positive impact on economic dynamics, although the impact of exports is significantly stronger than that of the institutional framework. Yanikkaya (2003) reached a similar conclusion, though his model nuances the picture of the role of the institutional system in that the pursuit of free trade does not always have a positive impact on growth, particularly in the case of developing countries, although moderate heterogeneity was observed across countries.

Using their static model, Rodrik et al. (2004) similarly examined the role of institutions and found that whilst the variance in countries’ levels of development is well explained in the long run by instrumental variables of the institutional background, the openness of economies does not have significant explanatory power, although a strong correlation exists between openness and the institutional system. Rodrik et al. thus posit that long-run equilibrium development is determined almost exclusively by the quality of the institutional framework, whilst in the medium term, growth (the rate of convergence towards the long-run equilibrium) is more strongly influenced by exports than by the current institutional framework, as reflected in the dynamic model of Dollar and Kraay (2003).

In his systematic literature review, Singh (2010) qualifies endogenous growth models by noting that a simultaneous relationship between growth and exports can introduce bias into OLS regressions, just as poorly chosen instruments can. The studies Singh examined often measured the openness of the economy solely through exports (i.e., in terms of the value chain, they considered only forward-looking relationships), thereby leaving a high level of unexplained variance. Singh included firms’ export capacity among the explanatory variables and noted that the positive relationship between exports and growth is highly context-dependent, with firms’ productivity, innovation capacity, and economies of scale as strong explanatory factors. Endogenous growth factors are primarily fuelled by these, and an effective institutional system can reinforce them. Consequently, the impact of exports on growth is also highly dependent on micro-level firm heterogeneity.

2.3 Global value chains and structural asymmetry

The improvement in firms' export competitiveness coincided with the relatively rapid fragmentation of production, driven by changes in investment and trade policy, particularly the rise of FDI-friendly policies, as well as the rapid development of communication and transport technologies. At the dawn of globalisation, the break-up of concentrated industrial complexes began, and subsidiaries were established in geographically distant locations, often in other countries, thereby setting in motion the process of internationalisation. In terms of ownership, the subsidiaries remained under the parent company's ownership but operated more efficiently than if the parent company had carried out the production itself. Subsidiaries exploited local competitive advantages, which were most often lower labour costs or better access to raw materials and markets. It became possible to separate the production phases and locate them in different, geographically distant locations. The rapid development of information and communication technology, particularly the trend towards digitalisation now known as Industry 4.0, has made it possible to manage production remotely, not only in terms of management issues but also in the area of physical implementation (Gereffy & Fernandez Jara, 2010; Strange & Zucchella, 2017). In the development of global value chains (GVCs), technological factors, and within these primarily digitalisation, play a central role, as they reduce production and transaction costs (Lund et al., 2019), and have created an entirely new type of trade, alongside those that developed a few decades ago, alongside traditional bilateral trade in finished goods.

With a few exceptions (typically countries under embargo), every country is now a participant in global trade. The global expansion of multinational or transnational companies, changes in production and stockpiling procedures, outsourcing, free trade agreements, integration into value chains, the freer movement of capital, the low interest rate environment and the abundance of liquidity in financial markets have all contributed significantly to the drastic rise in trade volumes and the emergence of vertical specialisations (Hummels et al., 2001). The growth policies of the United States and China, based on expanding consumption, ensured sufficient demand for all this, right up until the onset of the 2009 global economic crisis. The recession spread extremely rapidly across the world; on the one hand, through the globalised financial markets, and on the other, through the real economic channels created by the very value chains (Milberg & Winkler, 2010).

The rise of value chain analysis only began a few years before the turn of the millennium and is associated with the name of Gereffy (1994), although he wrote about global supply chains. Perhaps for this reason, the definition of a value chain most widely used today can be linked to Kaplinsky: *'The value chain includes all manufacturing activities, from conception through the semi-finished stage, to the delivery of the finished product to the consumer.'* (Kaplinsky, 2000).

Initially, geographical proximity was considered decisive in the development of chains and the formation of networks Leslie and Reimer (1999), but later Los et al. (2015) demonstrated that the share of value added generated abroad along global value chains is steadily rising.

The significance of companies, corporate groups and countries participating in GVCs within the value chain can therefore be assessed and ranked, thereby establishing a link between corporate and national competitiveness and GVCs. At that time, due to insufficient data, it was not yet possible to assess the value added at the various stages. Somewhat later, Mudambi's research, based on case studies, examined vertical integration and demonstrated that, across the entire production chain, manufacturing generates the lowest value added, whilst the design process preceding physical production and post-manufacturing activities (marketing,

distribution, etc.) generate significantly greater value, depicting the smile curve (Mudambi, 2008).

Corporate outsourcing has typically occurred from developed to emerging countries and can provide short-term growth impulses for both parties. In less developed countries, integration into the production chain can replace import-substitution industrial policy (Gereffi & Korzeniewicz, 1993), leading to improved terms of trade and technological development, which can positively impact growth. Productivity gains can also be achieved in more developed economies; however, as outsourcing deepens, terms of trade may deteriorate in the short term, a trend that is offset in the long term by the endogenisation of technology and the strengthening of innovation and research capacities (Bhagwati, 1958; Rodríguez-Clare, 2010). In emerging countries, however, the short-term positive effects of outsourcing may quickly erode if the spillover of knowledge and technology is not realised or is poorly utilised; in other words, economic policy based solely on FDI absorption is insufficient to achieve sustainable growth (Antràs, 2019).

2.4 The key to welfare growth: domestic integration and supplier base

The organisation of the international division of labour into global value chains has incorporated certain elements of international business economics into growth models, thereby introducing new exogenous factors. One such factor is the corporate group at the top of the value chain, which organises and manages the value chains, thereby imposing a structural constraint (for example, through market entry and exit opportunities or opportunities for upward mobility) on growth prospects, thereby making the economic growth potential arising from the value-chain-based division of labour even more contingent. In contrast to endogenous models, in which innovation and human capital development can be automatically converted into growth, in value chains, the benefits accrue primarily to the owners of intangible assets (i.e. in the economies of firms at the top of the chain), which can cause significant asymmetry in the distribution of benefits arising from the division of labour between developed and less developed countries (Gereffi, 2014; Gereffi et al., 2005; Kaplinsky, 2000). Such asymmetries in value capture can also have macro-growth consequences: Berg et al. (2018) show that higher net inequality is linked to slower and less durable growth, implying that who captures GVC rents may matter for long-run development trajectories, not just for static welfare distribution.

Participation in GVCs, therefore, does not, in the long term, entail systematic growth opportunities for participating economies; indeed, potential welfare gains are contingent on the specific part of the value chain where integration occurs. Joining the chain at the end (i.e., close to the final consumer) entails high import requirements, typically low value added, and no structural supplier relationships with domestic producers. Neither the conditions for endogenous growth (innovation capacity, technological and knowledge spillovers) nor the institutional conditions for this are created. Alternatively, if the leading company generates the necessary capacities within the economy (e.g., research and development centres), yet the welfare benefits accrue to the parent company's home country (Fagerberg et al., 2018; Tajoli & Felice, 2018).

Empirical econometric studies (Jangam & Rath, 2021b; Johnson & Noguera, 2017; Kim & Seo, 2025; Pahl & Timmer, 2020) confirm that participation in GVCs has indisputably positive effects on productivity; however, this does not necessarily hold true in a linear fashion depending on the level of development (P et al., 2023; Zhuqing, 2022). For an economy to capitalise on the long-term growth impulses arising from GVCs, it must certainly establish a strong domestic supplier base and adopt an 'upgrade' strategy. Economic growth driven by the

international division of labour does not necessarily translate into a clear improvement in welfare. The impact on employment is often negligible, so the welfare effects across a broad section of society may also remain limited. Somewhat paradoxically, productivity growth manifests primarily not through exports but through imports (Constantinescu et al., 2019), as this allows firms to access high-quality technological innovations and knowledge through imported semi-finished products. The strength of the effect is inversely proportional to the level of economic development, as developing and emerging countries start from a lower level of productivity and are located near the end of the value chain, closest to the end user (typically carrying out assembly activities), from where they have relatively more opportunities to move up the chain than developed countries, where labour productivity is already higher. In the same spirit, Ngai and Samaniego (2009) highlight that the growth impact of sectoral technical change is amplified when the affected goods are used as intermediates across sectors, providing an explicit general-equilibrium channel through which imported or upstream inputs can drive aggregate productivity.

Despite the fact that, in the long term, the extent of the benefits from participation in value chains remains unclear even for emerging countries, many governments have long regarded deeper integration as an industrial and economic policy objective. This is likely due to the illusion that deeper GVC integration leads to higher gross export growth; however, this does not necessarily result in economic growth. Kee et al. (2020) identified several necessary factors (a skilled workforce, supportive trade and FDI-promoting economic policies, institutional development, geographical proximity and connectivity, and sufficient industrial capacity in domestic sectors) required for countries to translate the benefits derived from GVCs into welfare growth. However, the combination of these factors is rarely found in emerging countries, which is why only a few have been able to truly capitalise on the globalisation trends of recent decades.

Several theoretical static models have sought to explain this phenomenon (Antràs & Gortari, 2020; Arkolakis et al., 2009)² by arguing that the magnitude of the welfare gains arising from participation in GVCs depends on the share of value added produced by purely domestic value chains in consumption, and on the price elasticity of foreign trade. Macro-based models do not contradict Singh's (2010) earlier finding that micro-level complexity influences export volume and determines the economy's export-based competitiveness. However, this complexity merely explains the distribution of gains at the firm level; the welfare effect achievable at the national level is independent of it. Arkolakis et al. (2009) identified two main reasons for this. On the one hand, the welfare gains from micro-level productivity growth, if they occur in an efficient market (Melitz, 2003), are often offset by a reduction in supply variety ('variety gains'). Similarly, the gains achieved through sectoral specialisation driven by trade liberalisation and based on comparative advantages (Eaton & Kortum, 2002) are often offset by rising imports; indeed, if export specialisation occurs in low-value-added products, deep integration into value chains can have a distinctly negative impact even on short-term growth (Jangam & Rath, 2021b). On the other hand, the share of purely domestic value chains in the production of value added is typically very high, with the result that the welfare-enhancing effect of export competitiveness based on increases in firm productivity affects only a small number of firms in the 'tradable' sector, whilst the spillover of knowledge is highly limited.

Recent growth-theoretic work also emphasises that trade in intermediate goods can alter the world income distribution through general-equilibrium interactions with capital accumulation

² This approach also appears in Krugman's (1980) model, but not yet in a value chain approach.

and cross-border capital flows. Basco and Mestieri (2019) developed a dynamic factor-proportions model with trade in final goods, intermediates, and capital in which countries differ in TFP, and show that unbundling generates a reallocation of capital toward high-productivity economies. High-TFP countries import/accumulate more capital and ultimately raise their real wages, because they produce more capital-intensive intermediate goods and the cost of capital is equalised internationally, thus they import/accumulate more capital and ultimately raise their real wages. This mechanism breaks conditional factor price equalisation and amplifies initial productivity differences into larger wage and income gaps, implying higher world income and welfare inequality.

2.5 Measuring the real contribution of value chains in a changing global landscape

The preceding subsections have established the theoretical underpinnings of the international division of labour, tracing its evolution from classical trade models to the complex landscape of global value chains (GVCs). However, the urgency of moving beyond these theoretical abstractions is underscored by the profound transformation the global economy landscape has been undergoing. As the latest international literature highlights (WTO, 2021, 2023, 2025), we are living in an era of ‘turbulent times’, where the intricate networks of production are facing exceptional challenges. Successive global shocks—most notably the COVID-19 pandemic, the Russian invasion of Ukraine, and intensifying trade tensions—have exposed inherent vulnerabilities and dangerous ‘choke points’ within traditional GVC structures. These shocks highlight how robust the growth strategy based on global value chains is, as GVCs have a much greater capacity to absorb shocks.

Another reason why this study is particularly timely is that, in such a volatile environment, conventional trade statistics measured at current (nominal) prices have become increasingly misleading. Surges in global inflation and exchange rate fluctuations can create a significant discrepancy between nominal and real participation rates. During the recent price spikes of 2021–2022, nominal data often overestimated actual GVC integration, masking the underlying structural shifts. This makes the transition to the analytical framework presented in the following sections essential. By utilising the World Input-Output Database (WIOD) and its historical extensions, this research leverages a unique feature: the previous year’s price (PYP) tables for the years 1966–2014. This allows for the rigorous measurement of real economic growth and volume changes, stripping away inflationary noise to reveal the true value-added contributions of national economies.

The necessity of this volume-based approach is further highlighted by the shifting priorities of global governance. The focus has moved from mere efficiency towards resilience, inclusiveness, and the ‘greening’ of value chains. As major economies embark on ‘reglobalization’ and supply chain ‘rewiring’, understanding the actual domestic value capture becomes paramount. While established nominal decomposition schemes have become benchmarks, there remains a distinct void in the international literature regarding the long-term dynamics of volume-based growth contributions. Consequently, the subsequent sections introduce the GVC Growth Contribution Database, a novel quantitative tool designed to isolate the real growth effects of domestic and international value chains, providing the granular perspective needed to navigate the geopolitically fragmented and climate-constrained reality of modern trade.

3 Methodology

3.1 Global input-output tables, GVC decomposition schemes and indicators

The quantitative analysis of global value chains has intensified since the early 2010s, driven by the emergence of international or global/world input-output (IO) tables. Since the beginning of

the decade, various world input-output databases have been appearing one after another, developed by university research communities, statistical offices, and regional and international organisations, often within the framework of consortium cooperation. Non-exhaustive examples of these include the *Global Trade, Assistance, and Production (GTAP) Data Base* (Aguiar et al., 2019), the *Eora Global MRIO* (Lenzen et al., 2012, 2013), the *Full International and Global Accounts for Research in Input-Output Analysis (FIGARO)* tables (Cazcarro et al., 2025; Redmond-Tiedrez & Rueda-Cantuche, 2019), as well as the *Inter-Country Input-Output Tables (ICIO)* (OECD, 2025a) and the *World Input-Output Database (WIOD)* (Dietzenbacher et al., 2013; M. P. Timmer et al., 2015, 2016). Some contain only the world input-output tables themselves, while others, e.g. the *Trade in Value Added (TiVA)* (OECD, 2025b) or the *UIBE GVC Database* (RIGVC UIBE, 2022), include derived indicators based on them. For an overview and comparison of the available global input-output data, see Jones et al. (2016), Steen-Olsen et al. (2016), Tukker & Dietzenbacher (2013), or Gáspár (2020) and Gáspár & Koppány (2020). For a list of the most important IO-data links, visit the website of the International Input-Output Association (<https://www.iioa.org/news/io-data.html>).

The general structure of a global input-output table is shown in Figure 1. The rows contain the sales (outputs) of country-industries for further production (matrix \mathbf{Z}) and final use (\mathbf{F}), while the columns represent the structure of their purchases (in \mathbf{Z} again) and value added (\mathbf{v}') (inputs), as well as the structure of final use by sector in monetary units (majorly million US dollars). Row and column sums of the table give the value of total production from the output (\mathbf{x}) and input (\mathbf{x}') sides. Mathematical operations on the different matrices and vectors in the table allow the calculation of global value chain indicators that also reflect the indirect relationships between productive industries and final user sectors. The calculation, magnitude, and interpretation of these indicators depend on the model framework, also known as the decomposition scheme, used to disaggregate economic variables across different types of value chains.

		Intermediate Use										Final Use						Total Output				
		Country#1			...			Country#m-1			Rest of the World (ROW)			Country#1		...			C#k-1		ROW	
		Ind#1	...	Ind#n	...	Ind#1	...	Ind#n	Ind#1	...	Ind#n	Households' Consumption	Other	...	HC	Other	HC		Other			
Country#1	Indsuby#1																					
	...																					
...	Indsuby#n																					
	...																					
Country#m-1	Indsuby#1																					
	...																					
ROW	Indsuby#1																					
	...																					
Value Added	Indsuby#1																					
	...																					
Total Input	Indsuby#1																					
	...																					

m = number of producer and intermediate user countries
 n = number of producer and intermediate user industries
 k = number of final user countries (in WIOD, $k = m$)
 s = number of final user sectors

Fig. 1 A Schematic World Input-Output Table.

Two theoretical schools have emerged for analysing and decomposing global value chains. The approach developed by Koopman and his co-authors was the first to gain widespread adoption, aiming to decompose gross exports (Koopman et al., 2010, 2014).³ This framework aligns with the initial motivations for compiling global input-output databases. Researchers studying world trade have observed that the gross export perspective used in traditional foreign trade statistics increasingly distorts results due to the proliferation of global value chains. The value of export products—especially at the end of the value chains due to increasingly high import content—progressively diverges from the actual economic performance and contribution of individual sectors and countries. This notion led to the development of the *Trade in Value Added* (TiVA) concept (Johnson & Noguera, 2012), which interprets the flow of value realised in global value chains as trade in value added, distinguishing between imported economic performance, domestic contribution, and exported value added. The practical application of the model framework and the quantification of its results would not have been possible without the compilation of global input-output tables.

Later, another competing decomposition scheme, associated with Wang and his co-authors, also emerged (Wang et al., 2017a, 2017b, 2022). Unlike the previous one, it does not break down gross exports but rather dissects gross value added or the value of final goods, in a manner slightly different from the earlier framework. The Wang model divides economic performance into local components, including pure domestic (pudo), both in terms of production and final use, and fully domestic production destined for export, being the so-called traditional foreign trade (*trtr*); as well as simple (*sGVC*) and complex (*cGVC*) global value chain activities. In simple GVCs, during production and the flow of semi-finished products, only a single border crossing occurs, whereas in complex ones, multiple border crossings occur. For an illustration of the differences between the four types of value chains defined above, see Figure 2.

The Wang decomposition framework supports both the backward/upstream and the forward/downstream perspectives. In the backward direction, it can be determined how much gross value added the industries of various countries contributed to the value of a specific country's final product during the period under study; from a forward perspective, it shows how much of the value added by individual country-industries went into the final products of different countries and industries. The ratios and distributions derived from these values provide the most important indicators for GVC analysis.

Participation indices measure the degree of involvement in global value chains and can be calculated using either of the two decomposition schemes. In the Koopman model, the share of imported value added in gross exports represents backward participation, while the ratio of domestic value added indirectly exported to total gross exports represents forward participation. In the Wang model, the share of value-added components originating from simple and complex global value chains in the final product constitutes backward participation, while the share of value-added components utilised through simple and complex global value chains indicates forward participation. The sum of the backward and forward ratios gives total participation.

³ This model family has gradually developed over the past years into an increasingly accurate and comprehensive unified general framework that reconciles different definitions, unambiguously and consistently defines domestic and foreign value-added terms across different accounting perspectives, and offers the most relevant decompositions for different types of trade analysis (Borin & Mancini, 2023; Los & Timmer, 2018; Miroudot & Ye, 2020, 2021).

Fig. 2 Wang-types of value chains.

Koopman's and Wang's schemes yield different results due to the differing categories, various indicator contents, and especially the distinct reference bases (gross exports in the first case, gross value added and total final product in the second). The different outcomes, in turn, portray contrasting pictures of the role of GVCs in the global economy. The Koopman scheme, based on the breakdown of gross exports, completely ignores economic activities (production and use) that take place solely within a country's borders. Yet—even though complex GVCs have indeed undergone significant expansion and comoved with global business cycles more than other types of production activities, thus they affected economic growth (Wang et al., 2017b, 2022)—it is still the local, specifically purely domestic, performance that accounted for the dominant part of global value added, not only in recent times of deglobalisation, but also in the golden age of GVCs (Koppány & Gáspár, 2022; Miroudot & Nordström, 2020).

Moreover, when examining economic growth, we cannot focus solely on export-related performance. In such cases, we must consider the total value added. Given that our study quantifies and analyses its real growth and the contribution of different types of value chains to this, only the Wang approach is applicable. The following subsections present the necessary input-output foundations and the technical background of our calculations in this vein.

3.2 Basic input-output modelling

Wang's scheme is based on the open static demand-driven input-output model (Leontief, 1936), in which direct inter-industry linkages are defined from the input side via input coefficients describing the required purchases from suppliers to produce 1 unit of output. All data in the IO table are expressed in monetary terms; however, the prices are assumed fixed, since this is a quantity model. Input coefficients are organised into a matrix (\mathbf{A}) and calculated as the ratio of \mathbf{Z} elements and the sum of their related column in the IO table (i.e., total inputs). Using matrix operations,

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{Z} \langle \mathbf{x} \rangle^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

where chevrons $\langle \rangle$ denote diagonalisation and power exponent -1 represent matrix inversion. $\langle \mathbf{x} \rangle^{-1}$ contains the reciprocal values of total outputs on the main diagonal and zeros elsewhere. \mathbf{A} has the same dimensions $mn \times mn$ as \mathbf{Z} .

When there is no need to distinguish between final user countries and sectors, we can sum the rows of matrix \mathbf{F} ,

$$\mathbf{F}\mathbf{i} = \mathbf{f}, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{i} is the identity (summing) vector and \mathbf{f} is an $mn \times 1$ -dimensional column vector of total final use of the products by country-industries in the rows.

Using Eq. (1) and (2), we can formulate a basic identity of the IO model where the supply (on the left side) and the intermediate ($\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}$) and final (\mathbf{f}) use of products (on the right) are in balance according to Eq. (3):

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{f}. \quad (3)$$

Rearranging (3) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} &= \mathbf{f}, \\ (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})\mathbf{x} &= \mathbf{f}, \end{aligned}$$

where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix with 1's on the main diagonal and zeros everywhere else. After multiplying by the inverse of $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})$ from the left,

$$\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{f},$$

and introducing the global Leontief inverse, $\mathbf{L} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-1}$, we have the most compact form of the model describing direct and indirect relations between countries and industries, final demand and production:

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{f}. \quad (4)$$

Since economic growth is measured by the volume index of gross value added, we must convert Eq. (4) into value-added terms. To do this, introduce the vector \mathbf{c}' of value added to output ratios:

$$\mathbf{c}' = \mathbf{v}' \langle \mathbf{x} \rangle^{-1}. \quad (5)$$

Using them, we can regain value-added vectors in the form of a row-, $\mathbf{v}' = \mathbf{c}' \langle \mathbf{x} \rangle$, or column-vector, $\mathbf{v} = \langle \mathbf{c} \rangle \mathbf{x}$. Substituting the right side of Eq. (4) into the latter, we have

$$\mathbf{v} = \langle \mathbf{c} \rangle \mathbf{L}\mathbf{f},$$

or with diagonalising the final use vector, $\langle \mathbf{f} \rangle$, we can derive a value-added matrix

$$\mathbf{V}_{mn \times mn} = \langle \mathbf{c} \rangle \mathbf{L} \langle \mathbf{f} \rangle, \quad (6)$$

a general element of which shows the value added generated by the country-industry in the related row and utilised by the country-industry in the related column to be incorporated into

the value of its final products. Eq. (6) serves as the primary formula for the gross value added (GVA) decomposition in the Wang model, linking value-added sources to final producers.

3.3 GVA decompositions by value chain type

As discussed earlier, Wang et al. (2017b, 2022) differentiate between four types of value chains: pure domestic, traditional foreign trade, simple and complex GVCs. To formalise their value-added generation, final use (\mathbf{F}) must be split up into domestic (\mathbf{F}^D) and foreign (\mathbf{F}^F) demand matrices with the same dimensions as of \mathbf{F} :

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}^D + \mathbf{F}^F$$

$mn \times ks$ $mn \times ks$ $mn \times ks$

\mathbf{F}^D contains zeros where the producer (row) and final user (column) countries are different, \mathbf{F}^F , in contrast, contains zeros where they are the same. Their other elements correspond to those of matrix \mathbf{F} . Then we apply a row-wise summation on the final use matrices:

$$\mathbf{F}\mathbf{i} = \mathbf{f} \quad , \quad \mathbf{F}^D\mathbf{i} = \mathbf{f}^D \quad , \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{F}^F\mathbf{i} = \mathbf{f}^F \quad .$$

$mn \times 1$ $mn \times 1$ $mn \times 1$

The additive relation between the three final use vectors still holds:

$$\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{f}^D + \mathbf{f}^F \quad . \quad (7)$$

The same separation between domestic and foreign (import) input coefficients can be implemented on matrix \mathbf{A} :

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}^D + \mathbf{A}^F \quad . \quad (8)$$

\mathbf{A}^D contains zeros where the supplier (row) and intermediate user (column) countries are different, \mathbf{A}^F , in contrast, contains zeros where they are the same. Their other elements correspond to those of matrix \mathbf{A} .

Substituting Eq. (7) and (8) into (3)

$$\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{A}^D + \mathbf{A}^F)\mathbf{x} + (\mathbf{f}^D + \mathbf{f}^F) = \mathbf{A}^D\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{A}^F\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{f}^D + \mathbf{f}^F \quad ,$$

then rearranging,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{A}^D\mathbf{x} &= \mathbf{f}^D + \mathbf{f}^F + \mathbf{A}^F\mathbf{x} \quad , \\ (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}^D)\mathbf{x} &= \mathbf{f}^D + \mathbf{f}^F + \mathbf{A}^F\mathbf{x} \quad , \end{aligned}$$

and introducing the local or domestic Leontief inverse, $\mathbf{L}^D = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A}^D)^{-1}$, we have

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{L}^D\mathbf{f}^D + \mathbf{L}^D\mathbf{f}^F + \mathbf{L}^D\mathbf{A}^F\mathbf{x} \quad .$$

Using Eq. (4) and replacing \mathbf{x} on the right side with $\mathbf{L}\mathbf{f}$ yields

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{L}^D\mathbf{f}^D + \mathbf{L}^D\mathbf{f}^F + \mathbf{L}^D\mathbf{A}^F\mathbf{L}\mathbf{f} \quad , \quad (9)$$

where the terms on the right describe world production by country-industry decomposed into pure domestic ($\mathbf{L}^D\mathbf{f}^D$), traditional foreign trade ($\mathbf{L}^D\mathbf{f}^F$), and global value chain ($\mathbf{L}^D\mathbf{A}^F\mathbf{L}\mathbf{f}$) components. In the first term, final demand is purely domestic and is satisfied exclusively from domestic production, both directly and indirectly. In the second, final products are exported, but the production is still purely domestic. In the third, final demand is global, the entire world can be involved in production, and at least one border crossing occurs during the sale of intermediate products.

The term $\mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{A}^F \mathbf{L} \mathbf{f}$ for global value chains can be further decomposed into simple and global GVCs. Wang defines simple GVCs as those in which only one border crossing occurs in the linkage of production steps, involving only the international trade of intermediate products. The final goods produced using these intermediate products are consumed exclusively in the domestic economy (see lower-left quadrant of Figure 2). Formally:

$$\mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{A}^F \mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{f}^D. \quad (10)$$

Output by complex GVCs, where the number of border crossings is more than one, and they can involve the trade of both intermediate and final products (lower-right quadrant of Figure 2), can be determined as a residue, output by total GVCs less the output by simple ones:

$$\mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{A}^F \mathbf{L} \mathbf{f} - \mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{A}^F \mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{f}^D = \mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{A}^F (\mathbf{L} \mathbf{f} - \mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{f}^D). \quad (11)$$

Now we can summarise the decomposition of output by value chains with the following equation:

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{L} \mathbf{f} = \underbrace{\mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{f}^D}_{\text{pure domestic (pudo)}} + \underbrace{\mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{f}^F}_{\text{traditional trade (trtr)}} + \underbrace{\mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{A}^F \mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{f}^D}_{\text{simple GVCs (sGVC)}} + \underbrace{\mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{A}^F (\mathbf{L} \mathbf{f} - \mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{f}^D)}_{\text{complex GVCs (cGVC)}}. \quad (12)$$

Since we still want to provide a breakdown of economic growth, we need to convert the output data into value-added terms. Based on Eq. (6) it is quite simple:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{V} = \langle \mathbf{c} \rangle \mathbf{L} \langle \mathbf{f} \rangle &= \underbrace{\langle \mathbf{c} \rangle \mathbf{L}^D \langle \mathbf{f}^D \rangle}_{\text{pure domestic (pudo)}} + \underbrace{\langle \mathbf{c} \rangle \mathbf{L}^D \langle \mathbf{f}^F \rangle}_{\text{traditional trade (trtr)}} + \underbrace{\langle \mathbf{c} \rangle \mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{A}^F \mathbf{L}^D \langle \mathbf{f}^D \rangle}_{\text{simple GVCs (sGVC)}} + \\ &+ \underbrace{\langle \mathbf{c} \rangle \mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{A}^F (\mathbf{L} \langle \mathbf{f} \rangle - \mathbf{L}^D \langle \mathbf{f}^D \rangle)}_{\text{complex GVCs (cGVC)}}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

For the sake of shorter mathematical notations, introduce the following matrices for different value chain types (\mathbf{D} for pure domestic, \mathbf{T} for traditional international trade, \mathbf{S} for simple, and \mathbf{C} for complex global value chains):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D} &= \langle \mathbf{c} \rangle \mathbf{L}^D \langle \mathbf{f}^D \rangle, \\ \mathbf{T} &= \langle \mathbf{c} \rangle \mathbf{L}^D \langle \mathbf{f}^F \rangle, \\ \mathbf{S} &= \langle \mathbf{c} \rangle \mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{A}^F \mathbf{L}^D \langle \mathbf{f}^D \rangle, \text{ and} \\ \mathbf{C} &= \langle \mathbf{c} \rangle \mathbf{L}^D \mathbf{A}^F (\mathbf{L} \langle \mathbf{f} \rangle - \mathbf{L}^D \langle \mathbf{f}^D \rangle). \end{aligned}$$

Using them we have

$$\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{T} + \mathbf{S} + \mathbf{C}, \quad (14)$$

a complete breakdown of global value added by source and final producer country-industries as a sum of four $mn \times mn$ -dimensional matrices, each corresponding to a specific value chain type (Figure 2). \mathbf{D} (*pudo*) and \mathbf{T} (*trtr*), by definition, contain zero elements in the off-diagonal blocks (where row and column countries, i.e. value-added source and final producer countries, are different). Inversely, \mathbf{S} (*sGVC*) has zeros in the diagonal blocks (where row- and column-countries are the same). \mathbf{C} (*cGVC*) can contain non-zero elements everywhere. The blocks with zero and non-zero elements were distinguished with light and dark colours in Figure 3.

Fig. 3 Global GVA decomposed by value chain type, value-added source, and final producer.

3.4 GVA shares

Summing the elements of each matrix in Eq. (14), $i'V_i$, $i'D_i$, $i'T_i$, $i'S_i$, $i'C_i$, and dividing both sides by $i'V_i$ yields the percentage breakdown (share) of value added by value chain type expressing their weight or role in the global economy.

$$100\% = \frac{i'D_i}{i'V_i} \cdot 100\% + \frac{i'T_i}{i'V_i} \cdot 100\% + \frac{i'S_i}{i'V_i} \cdot 100\% + \frac{i'C_i}{i'V_i} \cdot 100\% \quad (15)$$

The same calculation can be performed at the country or industry level (using the relevant blocks) to describe the main sources of value-added generation and participation in different types of value chains.

3.5 Real GVA growth

Growth in real terms is expressed as volume indices, which require GVA data at current and previous-year prices. For a decomposition by value chain, we need full world IO tables at both prices. Having a table for year t at previous-year's prices and another for year $t-1$ at the current-year prices prevailing in that year, we can perform the decomposition presented hereinbefore.

$${}_{pyp}V_t = {}_{pyp}D_t + {}_{pyp}T_t + {}_{pyp}S_t + {}_{pyp}C_t, \text{ and} \quad (16)$$

$${}_{cp}V_{t-1} = {}_{cp}D_{t-1} + {}_{cp}T_{t-1} + {}_{cp}S_{t-1} + {}_{cp}C_{t-1}, \quad (17)$$

where pyp and cp denote the previous and current years' prices, respectively.

The real growth rate of the four value chain components of the global GVA in percentage terms are

$$\frac{\mathbf{i}'_{py} \mathbf{D}_t \mathbf{i} - \mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{D}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}}{\mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{D}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}} \cdot 100\%, \quad \frac{\mathbf{i}'_{py} \mathbf{T}_t \mathbf{i} - \mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{T}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}}{\mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{T}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}} \cdot 100\%, \quad \frac{\mathbf{i}'_{py} \mathbf{S}_t \mathbf{i} - \mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{S}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}}{\mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{S}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}} \cdot 100\%, \quad \text{and}$$

$$\frac{\mathbf{i}'_{py} \mathbf{C}_t \mathbf{i} - \mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{C}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}}{\mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{C}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}} \cdot 100\%. \quad (18)$$

At the country or industry level, Eq. (16), (17) and (18) need to be set up for the given country or industry (i.e., calculations must be made using the rows of the four sub-tables in Figure 3 belonging to the value-added source country or industry under investigation).

Unfortunately, growth rates are not additive. The sum of *pudo*, *trtr*, *sGVC*, and *cGVC* growth does not equal the actual growth in global value added. The same applies at the sectoral or corporate level. To have additive components of growth, we need to express the growth contributions. It offers a completely novel approach to GVC input-output analysis.

3.6 Real GVA growth contributions

At the global level, growth contributions can be calculated using the right-hand terms in Eq. (19):

$$\underbrace{\frac{\mathbf{i}'_{py} \mathbf{V}_t \mathbf{i} - \mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{V}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}}{\mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{V}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}} \cdot 100\%}_{\text{total annual global real GVA growth \%}} = \underbrace{\frac{\mathbf{i}'_{py} \mathbf{D}_t \mathbf{i} - \mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{D}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}}{\mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{V}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}} \cdot 100\%}_{\text{pudo VCs' growth contribution \% (pudo\%)}} + \underbrace{\frac{\mathbf{i}'_{py} \mathbf{T}_t \mathbf{i} - \mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{T}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}}{\mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{V}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}} \cdot 100\%}_{\text{trtr VCs' growth contribution \% (pudo\%)}} +$$

$$+ \underbrace{\frac{\mathbf{i}'_{py} \mathbf{S}_t \mathbf{i} - \mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{S}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}}{\mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{V}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}} \cdot 100\%}_{\text{sGVCs' growth contribution \% (pudo\%)}} + \underbrace{\frac{\mathbf{i}'_{py} \mathbf{C}_t \mathbf{i} - \mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{C}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}}{\mathbf{i}'_{cp} \mathbf{V}_{t-1} \mathbf{i}} \cdot 100\%}_{\text{cGVCs' growth contribution \% (pudo\%)}}. \quad (19)$$

Since they are additive, their sum accounts for the total worldwide real GVA-growth.

At the country level, calculations are a bit more complex:

$$\underbrace{\left\langle \mathbf{v}_{cp}^c \mathbf{v}_{t-1} \right\rangle^{-1} \left(\mathbf{v}_{py} \mathbf{V}_t - \mathbf{v}_{cp} \mathbf{V}_{t-1} \right) \cdot 100\%}_{\text{total annual real GVA growth \%}} = \underbrace{\left\langle \mathbf{v}_{cp}^c \mathbf{v}_{t-1} \right\rangle^{-1} \left(\mathbf{v}_{py} \mathbf{D}_t - \mathbf{v}_{cp} \mathbf{D}_{t-1} \right) \cdot 100\%}_{\text{pudo VCs' growth contribution \% (pudo\%)}} +$$

$$+ \underbrace{\left\langle \mathbf{v}_{cp}^c \mathbf{v}_{t-1} \right\rangle^{-1} \left(\mathbf{v}_{py} \mathbf{T}_t - \mathbf{v}_{cp} \mathbf{T}_{t-1} \right) \cdot 100\%}_{\text{trtr VCs' growth contribution \% (trtr\%)}} +$$

$$+ \underbrace{\left\langle \mathbf{v}_{cp}^c \mathbf{v}_{t-1} \right\rangle^{-1} \left(\mathbf{v}_{py} \mathbf{S}_t - \mathbf{v}_{cp} \mathbf{S}_{t-1} \right) \cdot 100\%}_{\text{sGVCs' growth contribution \% (sGVC\%)}} +$$

$$+ \underbrace{\left\langle \mathbf{v}_{cp}^c \mathbf{v}_{t-1} \right\rangle^{-1} \left(\mathbf{v}_{py} \mathbf{C}_t - \mathbf{v}_{cp} \mathbf{C}_{t-1} \right) \cdot 100\%}_{\text{cGVCs' growth contribution \% (cGVC\%)}}. \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{v}_{l \times mn}^c = \left[\begin{array}{ccc|ccc|ccc} v_1 & v_1 & \dots & v_1 & v_2 & v_2 & \dots & v_2 & \dots & v_m & v_m & \dots & v_m \end{array} \right]$ contains the national

(country-level) GVA for each of the n intermediate user productive industries from the world IO table (Figure 1) (i.e. v_1, v_2, \dots, v_m denote national gross value added in country 1, 2, ..., m , respectively). The right-hand side of Eq. (20) defines four $mn \times mn$ -dimensional sub-matrices by value chain type (for an illustration, see Figure 4), which possess a very favourable

characteristic: they are additive according to the rows. Row sums of a specific country-industry give its growth contributions to total national growth by value chain type. The row sums across all industries in the value-added source country reflect the total value chain contributions to national growth. Moreover, within the blocks for the same value-added source country, elements are additive across the columns, as well. With it, one can, for instance, explore the extent to which a given final-product manufacturing country or industry contributed to a country's economic growth through a specific type of value chain.

Fig. 4 Real GVA growth contributions by value chain type, value-added source, and final producer.

To depict the global economy by industries, calculations by Eq. (20) should be implemented on an artificial ‘world’ country, where industries are the sum of the corresponding industries of all countries. It is shown in Figure 4 as the TOT (total) row block at the bottom of the tables. Note that the elements in TOT are not the sums of the columns; however, summarising by rows and columns functions here as well. They provide value chain contributions to global real growth from various perspectives.

Beyond the conceptual novelty of this approach, the database of decomposition matrices provides researchers with a versatile and flexible analytical tool. For illustration, let’s consider a country where the annual real GVA growth rate, say 3%, is known from basic input-output data. Using the crosstabs shown in Figure 4, one can explore the contribution of the four types of value chains to this. For instance, let’s have $pudo$ 1.4%, $trtr$ 0.6%, $sGVC$ 0.3%, and $cGVC$

0.7%. We have four fully additive components, which can be further decomposed into value-added (source) industries and final-product country-industries. It may be revealed, for example, that 0.7% of cGVC is primarily due to two domestic manufacturing sectors, electronics and automotive, with contributions of 0.35% and 0.25%, respectively (the remaining 0.1% is attributed to other industries). Further investigation may explore the 0.25% to identify the main final-product partner: a country-industry, which is the most important direct and indirect buyer of the intermediate goods manufactured in the country under investigation. Those who don't need the value chain breakdown and are only interested in the source industry and final product country-industry details can use the left side of Eq., which is the sum of the four tables in Figure 4. For an analysis of global growth, TOT rows can be utilised. This new device works like a kaleidoscope: by twisting it, i.e., aggregating or breaking down decomposition matrices from different perspectives, economic growth reveals another facet.

3.7 Relations between GVA shares, growth and growth contributions

When using the database, some trivial but important features must be kept in mind. Additivity of the matrix elements within the same decomposition scheme is very attractive, as it enables their handling and processing as data cubes. The decompositions relating to national and global growth rates, however, impose certain summation limitations already discussed in the previous subsection. Another attribute and the associated considerations are highlighted now.

The growth contributions reflect both the share (weight) and growth of individual value-added source industries, final-product country-industries, and value chain types. The greater the share of a value chain type or an industry in GVA production, *ceteris paribus*, the greater its contribution to growth. Similarly, the larger the GVA real growth generated by a value chain type, *ceteris paribus*, the greater its contribution to growth. These relationships are functional.

Moreover, the current shares of the value-added components are functionally related to the previous shares and the growth of the components since then. If the growth of one component exceeds that of the others, it naturally takes an increasing share. Important notes to keep in mind when designing econometric studies.

It is also important to consider the part-whole relationships between growth contributions and national growth. The latter is a function of the former: the sum of all contributions gives the total growth. Regressing total growth on its components makes no sense: it trivially yields a perfect fit. Similarly, the correlation between the parts and the whole is easily predictable. An increase in the growth contribution of any component enhances the entire country's economic growth and is positively correlated with it. The larger the component's share, the stronger the correlation becomes. Unless the variances and covariances of the components' growth rates exhibit extreme deviations, national economic growth is expected to show the highest correlation with the growth contribution of the component with the largest share.⁴

⁴ It can be easily proven that in a two-component case, where k_1 and k_2 are the shares, and g_1 and g_2 are the growth rates of the two components, the latter two are independent of each other, and the first component has a greater share, $k_1 > k_2$, its correlation with the total growth will be bigger (than the other) until $\left(\frac{k_1}{k_2}\right)^2 \sigma_{g_1} > \sigma_{g_2}$ holds, where σ_{g_1} and σ_{g_2} are the standard deviations of g_1 and g_2 , respectively.

3.8 Real GVA growth contributions by final user

In addition to the different value chain types, value-added sources, and the country and industry of the final product, further breakdowns by other categories may also be of interest to researchers.

The country-industry producing the final product does not represent the real end of the value chains. At the very end of them stands the final user. Thus, a decomposition by country and sector that uses the final product may prove particularly useful. If we are looking to answer the question of what portion of a country's annual economic growth is due to domestic (D) or foreign (F) consumption or investment, then our tables need to be transformed as follows.

First, construct matrices representing the distribution of final use by country and sector, both for total final use and separately for domestic and foreign ones. The individual elements of the final use matrices are divided by the sum of the corresponding rows. Using matrix algebra, these are:

$$\mathbf{F}^{\%} = \langle \mathbf{f} \rangle^{-1} \mathbf{F} \cdot 100\%, \quad \mathbf{F}^{D\%} = \langle \mathbf{f}^D \rangle^{-1} \mathbf{F}^D \cdot 100\%, \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{F}^{F\%} = \langle \mathbf{f}^F \rangle^{-1} \mathbf{F}^F \cdot 100\%. \quad (21)$$

All three distribution matrices (with the percentage signs in the upper right index) are equally of $mn \times ks$ dimensions. (For the sake of conciseness, this was only indicated in the first equation. The dimension notations will be applied accordingly in the following.)

Equations (21) represent the bridge between the previous matrices of final-product manufacturers and the matrices of final users to be produced now. By multiplying the previously defined \mathbf{D} , \mathbf{T} , \mathbf{S} , and \mathbf{C} from the right with the appropriate domestic and foreign sales ratios, the $mn \times ks$ -dimensional final use variants, marked with the index FU , are obtained, which show the value added generated by different final demands for each type of value chain in each country:

$$\mathbf{D}^{FU} = \mathbf{D} \mathbf{F}^{D\%}, \quad \mathbf{T}^{FU} = \mathbf{T} \mathbf{F}^{F\%}, \quad \mathbf{S}^{FU} = \mathbf{S} \mathbf{F}^{D\%}, \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{C}^{FU} = (\mathbf{S} + \mathbf{C}) \mathbf{F}^{\%} - \mathbf{S}^{FU}.$$

The fourth matrix, \mathbf{C}^{FU} , for complex value chains, is determined as a residue: the matrix for simple value chains is subtracted from the matrix containing all global value chains.

Of course, the additive relationship between the four matrices still applies, both to current and constant-price tables.

$${}_{cp} \mathbf{V}_{t-1}^{FU} = {}_{cp} \mathbf{D}_{t-1}^{FU} + {}_{cp} \mathbf{T}_{t-1}^{FU} + {}_{cp} \mathbf{S}_{t-1}^{FU} + {}_{cp} \mathbf{C}_{t-1}^{FU} \quad (22)$$

$${}_{pyp} \mathbf{V}_t^{FU} = {}_{pyp} \mathbf{D}_t^{FU} + {}_{pyp} \mathbf{T}_t^{FU} + {}_{pyp} \mathbf{S}_t^{FU} + {}_{pyp} \mathbf{C}_t^{FU} \quad (23)$$

Using (22) and (23), in a manner analogous to Eq. (20), we obtain the growth contributions by final user countries and sectors:

$$\begin{aligned}
\underbrace{\left\langle \begin{matrix} c \\ cp \end{matrix} \mathbf{v}_{t-1} \right\rangle^{-1} \left(\begin{matrix} pyp \\ cp \end{matrix} \mathbf{V}_t^{FU} - \begin{matrix} pyp \\ cp \end{matrix} \mathbf{V}_{t-1}^{FU} \right) \cdot 100\%}_{mn \times mn} &= \underbrace{\left\langle \begin{matrix} c \\ cp \end{matrix} \mathbf{v}_{t-1} \right\rangle^{-1} \left(\begin{matrix} pyp \\ cp \end{matrix} \mathbf{D}_t^{FU} - \begin{matrix} pyp \\ cp \end{matrix} \mathbf{D}_{t-1}^{FU} \right) \cdot 100\%}_{\text{pudo VCs' growth contribution \% (pudo\%)}} + \\
&+ \underbrace{\left\langle \begin{matrix} c \\ cp \end{matrix} \mathbf{v}_{t-1} \right\rangle^{-1} \left(\begin{matrix} pyp \\ cp \end{matrix} \mathbf{T}_t^{FU} - \begin{matrix} pyp \\ cp \end{matrix} \mathbf{T}_{t-1}^{FU} \right) \cdot 100\%}_{\text{trtr VCs' growth contribution \% (trtr\%)}} + \\
&+ \underbrace{\left\langle \begin{matrix} c \\ cp \end{matrix} \mathbf{v}_{t-1} \right\rangle^{-1} \left(\begin{matrix} pyp \\ cp \end{matrix} \mathbf{S}_t^{FU} - \begin{matrix} pyp \\ cp \end{matrix} \mathbf{S}_{t-1}^{FU} \right) \cdot 100\%}_{\text{sGVCs' growth contribution \% (sGVC\%)}} + \\
&+ \underbrace{\left\langle \begin{matrix} c \\ cp \end{matrix} \mathbf{v}_{t-1} \right\rangle^{-1} \left(\begin{matrix} pyp \\ cp \end{matrix} \mathbf{C}_t^{FU} - \begin{matrix} pyp \\ cp \end{matrix} \mathbf{C}_{t-1}^{FU} \right) \cdot 100\%}_{\text{cGVCs' growth contribution \% (cGVC\%)}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

The structure of the resulting matrices is illustrated in Figure 5. Again, we marked the blocks containing zero elements in a light colour. (These differ from the previous ones in the case of *trtr*.) The relationships and constraints concerning the row and column sums are valid in the same way as in the tables of Figure 4, and the rows of the world economy labelled TOT are derived similarly.

Figure 5 displays four matrices illustrating the structure of Real GVA growth contributions by value chain type, value-added source, and final user. The matrices are labeled **pudo%**, **trtr%**, **sGVC%**, and **cGVC%**. Each matrix has a grid structure with shaded and unshaded blocks representing non-zero and zero elements respectively. The columns represent final users (Country#1, ..., Country#k-1, Rest of the World (ROW)) and the rows represent value-added sources (Country#1, ..., Country#m-1, ROW, TOT). A 'Total Real GVA Growth Contributions' column is on the right of each matrix.

Fig. 5 Real GVA growth contributions by value chain type, value-added source, and final user.

3.9 Real final use (FU) growth contributions

Another aspect of the GVC and growth phenomenon is the growth in real final use (as a proxy for welfare gains) that can be reached by participating in global or other types of value chains. For the database to support such analyses, additional variants of the matrices must be prepared.

Using (22) and (23) again, and dividing the differences between their elements by the total value of the final use in the given country yields

$$\begin{aligned}
 \underbrace{\left(\begin{matrix} \text{py} & \mathbf{V}_t^{FU} & - & \text{cp} & \mathbf{V}_{t-1}^{FU} \end{matrix} \right) \left\langle \begin{matrix} \text{c} & \mathbf{f}_{t-1} \end{matrix} \right\rangle^{-1} \cdot 100\%}_{\text{total annual real FU growth \%}} &= \underbrace{\left(\begin{matrix} \text{py} & \mathbf{D}_t^{FU} & - & \text{cp} & \mathbf{D}_{t-1}^{FU} \end{matrix} \right) \left\langle \begin{matrix} \text{c} & \mathbf{f}_{t-1} \end{matrix} \right\rangle^{-1} \cdot 100\%}_{\text{pudo VCs' FU growth contribution \% (pudo\%)}} + \\
 &+ \underbrace{\left(\begin{matrix} \text{py} & \mathbf{T}_t^{FU} & - & \text{cp} & \mathbf{T}_{t-1}^{FU} \end{matrix} \right) \left\langle \begin{matrix} \text{c} & \mathbf{f}_{t-1} \end{matrix} \right\rangle^{-1} \cdot 100\%}_{\text{trtr VCs' FU growth contribution \% (trtr\%)}} + \\
 &+ \underbrace{\left(\begin{matrix} \text{py} & \mathbf{S}_t^{FU} & - & \text{cp} & \mathbf{S}_{t-1}^{FU} \end{matrix} \right) \left\langle \begin{matrix} \text{c} & \mathbf{f}_{t-1} \end{matrix} \right\rangle^{-1} \cdot 100\%}_{\text{sGVCs' FU growth contribution \% (sGVC\%)}} + \\
 &+ \underbrace{\left(\begin{matrix} \text{py} & \mathbf{C}_t^{FU} & - & \text{cp} & \mathbf{C}_{t-1}^{FU} \end{matrix} \right) \left\langle \begin{matrix} \text{c} & \mathbf{f}_{t-1} \end{matrix} \right\rangle^{-1} \cdot 100\%}_{\text{cGVCs' FU growth contribution \% (cGVC\%)}} ,
 \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

where $\begin{matrix} \text{c} & \mathbf{f}' \\ \text{1} \times & \text{ks} \end{matrix} = \left[\underbrace{f_1 \quad f_1 \quad \dots \quad f_1}_{s \text{ sectors}} \quad \underbrace{f_2 \quad f_2 \quad \dots \quad f_2}_{s \text{ sectors}} \quad \dots \quad \underbrace{f_k \quad f_k \quad \dots \quad f_k}_{s \text{ sectors}} \right]$ and f_1, f_2, \dots, f_k denote

total final use in country 1, 2, ..., k , respectively.

Figure 6 shows the structure of the FU growth contribution tables, where the column totals are meaningful across the entire table. Row sums are meaningful only within blocks for the same final user countries.

4 Illustrative numerical examples

Section 4 illustrates the application of the methodology described above. The calculation and use of the matrices defined in Section 3 are presented with a fictitious numerical example in which the world economy comprises two countries and three industries.

4.1 Year $t-1$ data and results at current prices

Table 1 shows the base ($t-1$) year data. Country#1 is a small (see its total output and value added, $600 + 4,800 + 3,900 = 9,300$ and $240 + 1,090 + 2,280 = 3,610$, respectively) and open economy (see its export and import to output ratios in the table or the export and import to GVA ratios, $3,740/3,610$ and $3,710/3,610$, respectively, both above 100%). Country#2, in contrast, is a large (46,700 total output and 23,620 total GVA) and closed economy (with 16% export and import-to-GVA rates). There are also significant differences between the two countries in value-added ratios by productive industries.

Figure 7 presents the results of the GVA decomposition by value chain type, value-added source, and final producer according to Eq. (14). (Vectors and matrices based on Table 1 data and used for the calculations can be found in Appendix A.)

Fig. 6 Real final use (FU) growth contributions by value chain type, value-added source, and final user.

Table 1 World input-output table (with some additional data) for year $t-1$ at current prices

	Intermediate use						Final use				Total use = Total output	Export/ Output%
	Country#1			Country#2			Country#1		Country#2			
	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Households	Other	Households	Other		
Country#1 Industry#1	90	150	30	60	60	60	90	30	20	10	600	35,0%
Country#1 Industry#2	70	800	270	40	1 020	240	270	390	1 400	300	4 800	62,5%
Country#1 Industry#3	60	420	870	50	150	180	1 050	970	90	60	3 900	13,6%
Country#2 Industry#1	60	40	30	120	440	60	120	30	250	50	1 200	23,3%
Country#2 Industry#2	50	2 120	180	200	6 350	2 350	260	220	3 150	2 920	17 800	15,9%
Country#2 Industry#3	30	180	240	150	3 300	8 250	100	50	8 700	6 700	27 700	2,2%
Value added	240	1 090	2 280	580	6 480	16 560					27 230	
Total input, total use	600	4 800	3 900	1 200	17 800	27 700	1 890	1 690	13 610	10 040	56 000	
Value-added ratios (c)	40,00%	22,71%	58,46%	48,33%	36,40%	59,78%						
Import ratios	23,33%	48,75%	11,54%	12,50%	6,91%	1,73%	25,4%	17,8%	11,1%	3,7%		

Row sums in the \mathbf{V} (*total*) table give GVA by industry: 240, 1,090, and 2,280 for Country#1, and 580, 6,480, and 16,560 for Country#2; same as in the value-added row in the world input-output table (WIOT) (Table 1). Rows in \mathbf{V} (Figure 7) show the infiltration of row country-industries' value added (they are the source of GVA) into the final products of column country-industries. Columns in \mathbf{V} reveal the contributions of country-industries in the rows to the final products of country-industries in the columns. Column totals are equal to the value of final products (final use) in the WIOT (for Country#1-Industry#1 it is $90 + 30 + 20 + 10 = 150$).

Sub-matrices \mathbf{D} , \mathbf{T} , \mathbf{S} , and \mathbf{C} (Figure 7) decompose \mathbf{V} by value chain types. Pure domestic (*pudo*) value chains emerge only between industries and final users within the same country. Thus, off-diagonal country blocks contain zeros. Based on matrix \mathbf{D} , 82 of Country#1-

Industry#1's 240 GVA were generated in pure domestic value chains. Similarly, $82 + 238 + 1,604 = 1,924$ of the 3,610 total GVA of Country#1 was produced and used domestically.

D (pudo)		Final Product						Total GVA
		Country#1			Country#2			
Value Added		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	
Country#1	Ind#1	57	12	13	0	0	0	82
	Ind#2	5	183	51	0	0	0	238
	Ind#3	12	55	1,537	0	0	0	1,604
Country#2	Ind#1	0	0	0	163	134	67	363
	Ind#2	0	0	0	36	3,589	1,106	4,730
	Ind#3	0	0	0	51	1,586	13,606	15,243
Total Final Product		74	250	1,600	250	5,308	14,778	22,261

T (trtr)		Final Product						Total GVA
		Country#1			Country#2			
Value Added		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	
Country#1	Ind#1	14	31	1	0	0	0	47
	Ind#2	1	470	4	0	0	0	475
	Ind#3	3	142	114	0	0	0	259
Country#2	Ind#1	0	0	0	81	11	1	93
	Ind#2	0	0	0	18	284	11	312
	Ind#3	0	0	0	26	125	133	284
Total Final Product		18	644	119	125	420	144	1,470

S (sGVC)		Final Product						Total GVA
		Country#1			Country#2			
Value Added		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	
Country#1	Ind#1	0	0	0	9	37	40	85
	Ind#2	0	0	0	6	170	111	287
	Ind#3	0	0	0	15	140	175	330
Country#2	Ind#1	8	14	19	0	0	0	42
	Ind#2	16	218	147	0	0	0	380
	Ind#3	16	129	214	0	0	0	360
Total Final Product		40	361	380	30	347	325	1,484

C (cGVC)		Final Product						Total GVA
		Country#1			Country#2			
Value Added		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	
Country#1	Ind#1	1	10	3	5	6	3	27
	Ind#2	1	41	9	4	26	9	89
	Ind#3	2	36	10	8	22	9	86
Country#2	Ind#1	2	40	3	3	20	15	83
	Ind#2	6	612	23	15	244	157	1,057
	Ind#3	5	366	24	12	157	109	674
Total Final Product		17	1,105	70	46	475	302	2,015

V (total)		Final Product						Total GVA
		Country#1			Country#2			
Value Added		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	
Country#1	Ind#1	72	53	17	13	43	42	240
	Ind#2	7	693	64	10	196	120	1,090
	Ind#3	17	233	1,661	23	162	184	2,280
Country#2	Ind#1	11	54	22	246	165	83	580
	Ind#2	21	830	169	69	4,117	1,274	6,480
	Ind#3	22	496	238	89	1,868	13,848	16,560
Total Final Product		150	2,360	2,170	450	6,550	15,550	27,230

Fig. 7 Global GVA decomposition by value chain type, value-added source, and final producer for year $t-1$ at current prices: an illustrative numerical example

D ^{FU} (pudo)		Final Use				Total GVA
		Country#1		Country#2		
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other	
Country#1	Ind#1	54	28	0	0	82
	Ind#2	105	133	0	0	238
	Ind#3	831	774	0	0	1,604
Country#2	Ind#1	0	0	243	121	363
	Ind#2	0	0	2,517	2,213	4,730
	Ind#3	0	0	8,552	6,691	15,243
Total Final Use		990	935	11,312	9,025	22,261

T ^{FU} (trtr)		Final Use				Total GVA
		Country#1		Country#2		
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other	
Country#1	Ind#1	0	0	36	11	47
	Ind#2	0	0	390	85	475
	Ind#3	0	0	188	72	259
Country#2	Ind#1	71	21	0	0	93
	Ind#2	175	137	0	0	312
	Ind#3	177	107	0	0	284
Total Final Use		423	265	614	167	1,470

S ^{FU} (sGVC)		Final Use				Total GVA
		Country#1		Country#2		
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other	
Country#1	Ind#1	0	0	49	36	85
	Ind#2	0	0	156	131	287
	Ind#3	0	0	184	146	330
Country#2	Ind#1	22	20	0	0	42
	Ind#2	177	203	0	0	380
	Ind#3	177	183	0	0	360
Total Final Use		376	406	389	314	1,484

C ^{FU} (cGVC)		Final Use				Total GVA
		Country#1		Country#2		
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other	
Country#1	Ind#1	8	6	9	4	27
	Ind#2	21	19	35	14	89
	Ind#3	24	18	32	13	86
Country#2	Ind#1	3	2	54	24	83
	Ind#2	27	24	716	290	1,057
	Ind#3	18	16	450	189	674
Total Final Use		101	84	1,296	534	2,015

V ^{FU} (total)		Final Use				Total GVA
		Country#1		Country#2		
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other	
Country#1	Ind#1	63	33	93	51	240
	Ind#2	126	152	582	230	1,090
	Ind#3	854	792	403	231	2,280
Country#2	Ind#1	96	43	297	145	580
	Ind#2	380	364	3,233	2,503	6,480
	Ind#3	372	306	9,002	6,880	16,560
Total Final Use		1,890	1,690	13,610	10,040	27,230

Fig. 8 Global GVA decomposition by value chain type, value-added source, and final user for year $t-1$ at current prices: an illustrative numerical example

Matrix **T** (traditional trade) follows a similar structure to **D** in terms of zero and non-zero elements: although the final products are sold abroad, they are still produced domestically. In **S** (simple GVCs), however, zero and non-zero positions are swapped, as this matrix shows the direct foreign value-added content of domestic final production and use. Finally, any cell in the **C** matrix (for complex GVCs) can and, in the example, does contain a non-zero value.

Based on the row sums of the four matrices, one can easily explore the structure of industry- and country-level GVA by value chains. For Country#1-Industry#1 this is

$$\frac{\text{pudo}}{\text{total}} + \frac{\text{trtr}}{\text{total}} + \frac{\text{sGVC}}{\text{total}} + \frac{\text{cGVC}}{\text{total}} = \frac{82}{240} + \frac{47}{240} + \frac{85}{240} + \frac{27}{240} = 34.1\% + 19.4\% + 35.4\% + 11.1\% = 100\%.$$

For Country#1 and Country#2 they are

$$\frac{1,924}{3,610} + \frac{781}{3,610} + \frac{702}{3,610} + \frac{202}{3,610} = 53.3\% + 21.6\% + 19.5\% + 5.6\% = 100\%, \text{ and}$$

$$\frac{20,336}{23,620} + \frac{689}{23,620} + \frac{782}{23,620} + \frac{1,813}{23,620} = 86.1\% + 2.9\% + 3.3\% + 7.7\% = 100\%,$$

respectively. These examples illustrate the industry- and country-level applications of Eq. (15) in Subsection 3.4. Using it in its original form for global calculations, based on the grand totals of the five matrices, the GVA shares by value chain type for the entire ‘world’ are

$$\frac{22,261}{27,230} + \frac{1,470}{27,230} + \frac{1,484}{27,230} + \frac{2,015}{27,230} = 81.8\% + 5.4\% + 5.5\% + 7.4\% = 100\%.$$

In Figure 8, the matrices show the decomposition of GVA by final users (rather than final producers, as in Figure 7). Columns indicate the country and sector where the final use occurs. Our simplified example, according to the details available in the WIOT (Table 1), distinguishes between two sectors only: household consumption and other final use. Row sums of the matrices, of course, have not changed. They still show the value added generated by the source country-industries. The structure of the rows, however, now reveals their breakdown by final demand. Column sums in the V^{FU} matrix correspond to the sums of the related total final use columns in the WIOT.

4.2 Year t data and results at previous year’s prices

Let us now assume that in the subsequent (t) year, the changes in the world economy unfold as presented in Table 2. Dark background cells indicate an increase, although decreases can also be observed (with light shade). Both economies have become more open, while value-added shares tend to decline in Country#1 and increase in Country#2.

Table 2 presents nominal data at constant (previous year’s) prices, allowing for the calculation of the key indicators of real economic growth in year t . The GVA of Country#1 increased from the previous year’s level of 3,610 units to $281 + 1,155 + 2,350 = 3,786$. This corresponds to a growth rate of 4.88%. The GVA of Country#2 rose from 23,620 to 24,254, representing an economic growth rate of 2.68%. In real terms, the gross value added of the entire world economy increased from 27,230 to 28,040, that is, by 2.97%.

Table 2 World input-output table (with some additional data) for year t at previous year's prices

		Intermediate use						Final use				Total use = Total output	Export/ Output%
		Country#1			Country#2			Country#1		Country#2			
		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Households	Other	Households	Other		
Country#1	Industry#1	101	160	31	64	63	61	110	30	40	10	670	35,5%
	Industry#2	79	861	282	44	1 085	244	280	410	1 500	340	5 125	62,7%
	Industry#3	60	446	898	54	156	183	1 080	980	100	70	4 027	14,0%
Country#2	Industry#1	60	43	31	141	454	61	130	30	280	50	1 280	23,0%
	Industry#2	56	2 270	187	214	6 437	2 388	290	250	3 300	3 000	18 392	16,6%
	Industry#3	33	190	248	157	3 403	8 361	120	70	8 820	6 750	28 152	2,3%
Value added		281	1 155	2 350	606	6 794	16 854					28 040	
Total input, total use		670	5 125	4 027	1 280	18 392	28 152	2 010	1 770	14 040	10 220	57 646	
Value-added ratios (c)		41,94%	22,54%	58,36%	47,34%	36,94%	59,87%						
Import ratios		22,24%	48,84%	11,57%	12,66%	7,09%	1,73%	26,9%	19,8%	11,7%	4,1%		

Note: dark/light background indicate the increase/decrease of the cell value from previous year.

Figures 9 and 10 present the decomposition of value added in year t using the same structure as Figures 7 and 8. The calculations were performed using the same methods as before. (Vectors and matrices based on Table 2 data and used for the calculations can be found in Appendix B.) On this basis, we could again calculate the various value-added shares—as presented in the previous subsection—and analyse their changes over time. However, we will refrain from doing so here. Current- and constant-price matrices offer far more analytical possibilities. With their help, we can decompose not only the level of GVA but also its real growth rates calculated in the previous paragraph by value chain types, source industries, final producer countries and industries, and final user countries and sectors, thereby expressing the contribution of each factor to overall growth. Moreover, we can analyse the real growth of final use (FU) in a similar breakdown and along the same dimensions. We will therefore use the matrices presented in Figures 9 and 10 for this purpose in the following subsections.

D (pudo)		Final Product						Total GVA
Value Added		Country#1			Country#2			
		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	
Country#1	Ind#1	70	13	14	0	0	0	97
	Ind#2	6	190	52	0	0	0	247
	Ind#3	13	57	1,564	0	0	0	1,634
Country#2	Ind#1	0	0	0	177	136	66	379
	Ind#2	0	0	0	40	3,738	1,121	4,899
	Ind#3	0	0	0	56	1,625	13,752	15,433
Total Final Product		88	260	1,630	273	5,499	14,939	22,690

T (trtr)		Final Product						Total GVA
Value Added		Country#1			Country#2			
		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	
Country#1	Ind#1	25	36	1	0	0	0	62
	Ind#2	2	506	4	0	0	0	512
	Ind#3	5	152	129	0	0	0	286
Country#2	Ind#1	0	0	0	86	12	1	98
	Ind#2	0	0	0	19	320	14	354
	Ind#3	0	0	0	27	139	168	334
Total Final Product		31	694	135	133	471	182	1,646

S (sGVC)		Final Product						Total GVA
Value Added		Country#1			Country#2			
		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	
Country#1	Ind#1	0	0	0	10	40	42	92
	Ind#2	0	0	0	7	179	113	298
	Ind#3	0	0	0	17	145	175	337
Country#2	Ind#1	9	14	19	0	0	0	42
	Ind#2	18	230	152	0	0	0	400
	Ind#3	19	134	218	0	0	0	371
Total Final Product		45	378	389	33	364	330	1,540

C (cGVC)		Final Product						Total GVA
Value Added		Country#1			Country#2			
		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	
Country#1	Ind#1	1	11	3	5	7	3	30
	Ind#2	2	44	10	4	28	10	97
	Ind#3	2	38	10	9	24	10	93
Country#2	Ind#1	3	42	3	3	20	15	86
	Ind#2	9	669	25	17	261	162	1,142
	Ind#3	8	393	26	13	165	110	716
Total Final Product		25	1,198	76	51	506	309	2,164

V (total)		Final Product						Total GVA
Value Added		Country#1			Country#2			
		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	
Country#1	Ind#1	95	60	18	15	47	45	281
	Ind#2	9	740	66	11	207	122	1,155
	Ind#3	20	248	1,703	25	169	185	2,350
Country#2	Ind#1	12	56	22	266	168	82	606
	Ind#2	27	898	177	76	4,320	1,296	6,794
	Ind#3	27	528	244	96	1,929	14,030	16,854
Total Final Product		190	2,530	2,230	490	6,840	15,760	28,040

Fig. 9 Global GVA decomposition by value chain type, value-added source, and final producer for year t at previous year's prices: an illustrative numerical example

D^{FU} (pudo)		Final Use				Total GVA
		Country#1		Country#2		
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other	
Country#1	Ind#1	67	29	0	0	97
	Ind#2	109	139	0	0	247
	Ind#3	853	781	0	0	1,634
Country#2	Ind#1	0	0	259	120	379
	Ind#2	0	0	2,627	2,272	4,899
	Ind#3	0	0	8,689	6,744	15,433
Total Final Use		1,029	949	11,575	9,136	22,690

T^{FU} (trtr)		Final Use				Total GVA
		Country#1		Country#2		
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other	
Country#1	Ind#1	0	0	50	12	62
	Ind#2	0	0	417	96	512
	Ind#3	0	0	204	82	286
Country#2	Ind#1	77	22	0	0	98
	Ind#2	197	157	0	0	354
	Ind#3	203	131	0	0	334
Total Final Use		476	310	670	190	1,646

S^{FU} (sGVC)		Final Use				Total GVA
		Country#1		Country#2		
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other	
Country#1	Ind#1	0	0	53	39	92
	Ind#2	0	0	163	135	298
	Ind#3	0	0	189	148	337
Country#2	Ind#1	23	19	0	0	42
	Ind#2	187	213	0	0	400
	Ind#3	183	188	0	0	371
Total Final Use		393	420	406	321	1,540

C^{FU} (cGVC)		Final Use				Total GVA
		Country#1		Country#2		
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other	
Country#1	Ind#1	10	6	10	4	30
	Ind#2	23	20	38	16	97
	Ind#3	26	19	34	14	93
Country#2	Ind#1	3	2	56	24	86
	Ind#2	30	26	772	313	1,142
	Ind#3	20	17	478	201	716
Total Final Use		111	91	1,389	572	2,164

V^{FU} (total)		Final Use				Total GVA
		Country#1		Country#2		
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other	
Country#1	Ind#1	77	36	113	55	281
	Ind#2	132	159	618	246	1,155
	Ind#3	879	800	427	244	2,350
Country#2	Ind#1	102	43	316	145	606
	Ind#2	414	396	3,399	2,585	6,794
	Ind#3	406	336	9,167	6,945	16,854
Total Final Use		2,010	1,770	14,040	10,220	28,040

Fig. 10 Global GVA decomposition by value chain type, value-added source, and final user for year t at previous year's prices: an illustrative numerical example

4.3 Real GVA growth contributions by final producer

Based on Eq. (19) and (20), the absolute indicators of growth are obtained as the differences between the corresponding values in Figures 9 and 7 (that is, by subtracting the matrices in Figure 7 from those in Figure 9). Economic growth, however, is typically expressed as a percentage change. Moreover, we aim to obtain result tables whose percentage values can be aggregated, at least at the national level. These will be the so-called growth contributions, which are derived by dividing the differences between the previous-year price tables for period t and the current-price tables for period $t-1$ by the country's total value added in period $t-1$, in accordance with Eq. (20). The resulting values are shown in Figure 11.

The *total%* matrix shows the same national and global growth rates as calculated in the previous subsection: 4.88% for Country#1, 2.68% for Country#2, and 2.97% for the 'world'. The row sums indicate the contributions of individual source industries. In Country#1, Industry#3 had the highest growth contribution (1.80%), while in Country#2, Industry#2 contributed most significantly (1.33%). Globally, Industry#2 was also the most dominant (1.39%). The detailed row-level data reveal which industries in which countries, through final-product production, contributed most to sectoral growth along global value chains.

Using the *pudo%*, *trtr%*, *sGVC%*, and *cGVC%* submatrices, we can further decompose the 4.88% growth of Country#1: 1.50% is attributable to purely domestic activities, 2.19% to traditional foreign trade, 0.69% to participation in simple global value chains, and 0.50% to participation in complex global value chains. For Country#2, these growth contributions are 1.59%, 0.41%, 0.13%, and 0.55%, respectively. At the global level, the contributions are 1.58%, 0.65%, 0.20%, and 0.55%. In Country#1, the highest growth contribution stemmed from Industry#2's participation in traditional foreign trade (1.03%), whereas in Country#2 it was driven by Industry#3's purely domestic value chains (0.80%).

pudo%		Final Product						Total Real GVA Growth Contributions	
		Country#1			Country#2				
Value Added		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3		
Country#1	Ind#1	0.35%	0.03%	0.03%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.41%	1.50%
	Ind#2	0.02%	0.20%	0.04%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.26%	
	Ind#3	0.02%	0.05%	0.76%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.83%	
Country#2	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.06%	0.01%	0.00%	0.07%	1.59%
	Ind#2	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.63%	0.06%	0.71%	
	Ind#3	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.17%	0.62%	0.80%	
TOT	Ind#1	0.05%	0.00%	0.00%	0.05%	0.01%	0.00%	0.11%	1.58%
	Ind#2	0.00%	0.03%	0.00%	0.02%	0.55%	0.05%	0.65%	
	Ind#3	0.00%	0.01%	0.10%	0.02%	0.14%	0.54%	0.81%	

trtr%		Final Product						Total Real GVA Growth Contributions	
		Country#1			Country#2				
Value Added		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3		
Country#1	Ind#1	0.29%	0.12%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.42%	2.19%
	Ind#2	0.02%	0.99%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	1.03%	
	Ind#3	0.04%	0.28%	0.41%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.74%	
Country#2	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.41%
	Ind#2	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.16%	0.01%	0.17%	
	Ind#3	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.06%	0.15%	0.21%	
TOT	Ind#1	0.04%	0.02%	0.00%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.08%	0.65%
	Ind#2	0.00%	0.13%	0.00%	0.01%	0.13%	0.01%	0.29%	
	Ind#3	0.01%	0.04%	0.05%	0.01%	0.05%	0.13%	0.28%	

sGVC%		Final Product						Total Real GVA Growth Contributions	
		Country#1			Country#2				
Value Added		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3		
Country#1	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.04%	0.10%	0.07%	0.21%	0.69%
	Ind#2	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.23%	0.04%	0.29%	
	Ind#3	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.05%	0.13%	0.02%	0.19%	
Country#2	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.13%
	Ind#2	0.01%	0.05%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.08%	
	Ind#3	0.01%	0.02%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.05%	
TOT	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.01%	0.01%	0.03%	0.20%
	Ind#2	0.01%	0.04%	0.02%	0.00%	0.03%	0.01%	0.11%	
	Ind#3	0.01%	0.02%	0.01%	0.01%	0.02%	0.00%	0.07%	

cGVC%		Final Product						Total Real GVA Growth Contributions	
		Country#1			Country#2				
Value Added		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3		
Country#1	Ind#1	0.01%	0.04%	0.01%	0.02%	0.03%	0.01%	0.10%	0.50%
	Ind#2	0.01%	0.10%	0.01%	0.01%	0.08%	0.02%	0.22%	
	Ind#3	0.01%	0.07%	0.01%	0.02%	0.05%	0.01%	0.17%	
Country#2	Ind#1	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.55%
	Ind#2	0.01%	0.24%	0.01%	0.01%	0.07%	0.02%	0.36%	
	Ind#3	0.01%	0.11%	0.01%	0.01%	0.03%	0.00%	0.18%	
TOT	Ind#1	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.03%	0.55%
	Ind#2	0.01%	0.22%	0.01%	0.01%	0.07%	0.02%	0.34%	
	Ind#3	0.01%	0.11%	0.01%	0.01%	0.04%	0.01%	0.18%	

total%		Final Product						Total Real GVA Growth Contributions	
		Country#1			Country#2				
Value Added		Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3	Ind#1	Ind#2	Ind#3		
Country#1	Ind#1	0.65%	0.19%	0.04%	0.06%	0.12%	0.08%	1.14%	4.88%
	Ind#2	0.05%	1.29%	0.06%	0.03%	0.31%	0.05%	1.80%	
	Ind#3	0.07%	0.41%	1.18%	0.06%	0.18%	0.04%	1.94%	
Country#2	Ind#1	0.01%	0.01%	0.00%	0.08%	0.01%	0.00%	0.11%	2.68%
	Ind#2	0.02%	0.29%	0.03%	0.03%	0.86%	0.09%	1.33%	
	Ind#3	0.02%	0.13%	0.03%	0.03%	0.26%	0.77%	1.24%	
TOT	Ind#1	0.09%	0.03%	0.01%	0.08%	0.03%	0.01%	0.25%	2.97%
	Ind#2	0.03%	0.42%	0.03%	0.03%	0.79%	0.09%	1.39%	
	Ind#3	0.03%	0.17%	0.18%	0.04%	0.25%	0.67%	1.34%	

Fig. 11 Real GVA growth contributions by value chain type, value-added source, and final producer for year t at previous year's prices: an illustrative numerical example

pudo%		Final User				Total Real GVA Growth Contributions	
		Country#1		Country#2			
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other		
Country#1	Ind#1	0.36%	0.05%	0.00%	0.00%	0.41%	1.50%
	Ind#2	0.11%	0.15%	0.00%	0.00%	0.26%	
	Ind#3	0.63%	0.20%	0.00%	0.00%	0.83%	
Country#2	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.07%	0.00%	0.07%	1.59%
	Ind#2	0.00%	0.00%	0.47%	0.25%	0.71%	
	Ind#3	0.00%	0.00%	0.58%	0.23%	0.80%	
TOT	Ind#1	0.05%	0.01%	0.06%	0.00%	0.11%	1.58%
	Ind#2	0.01%	0.02%	0.40%	0.22%	0.65%	
	Ind#3	0.08%	0.03%	0.50%	0.20%	0.81%	

trtr%		Final User				Total Real GVA Growth Contributions	
		Country#1		Country#2			
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other		
Country#1	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.38%	0.04%	0.42%	2.19%
	Ind#2	0.00%	0.00%	0.73%	0.30%	1.03%	
	Ind#3	0.00%	0.00%	0.45%	0.29%	0.74%	
Country#2	Ind#1	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.41%
	Ind#2	0.09%	0.08%	0.00%	0.00%	0.17%	
	Ind#3	0.11%	0.10%	0.00%	0.00%	0.21%	
TOT	Ind#1	0.02%	0.00%	0.05%	0.01%	0.08%	0.65%
	Ind#2	0.08%	0.07%	0.10%	0.04%	0.29%	
	Ind#3	0.10%	0.09%	0.06%	0.04%	0.28%	

sGVC%		Final User				Total Real GVA Growth Contributions	
		Country#1		Country#2			
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other		
Country#1	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.13%	0.07%	0.21%	0.69%
	Ind#2	0.00%	0.00%	0.19%	0.10%	0.29%	
	Ind#3	0.00%	0.00%	0.15%	0.04%	0.19%	
Country#2	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.13%
	Ind#2	0.04%	0.04%	0.00%	0.00%	0.08%	
	Ind#3	0.03%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.05%	
TOT	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.01%	0.03%	0.20%
	Ind#2	0.04%	0.03%	0.03%	0.01%	0.11%	
	Ind#3	0.03%	0.01%	0.02%	0.01%	0.07%	

cGVC%		Final User				Total Real GVA Growth Contributions	
		Country#1		Country#2			
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other		
Country#1	Ind#1	0.03%	0.02%	0.03%	0.01%	0.10%	0.50%
	Ind#2	0.06%	0.05%	0.08%	0.03%	0.22%	
	Ind#3	0.05%	0.04%	0.06%	0.02%	0.17%	
Country#2	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.01%	0.55%
	Ind#2	0.01%	0.01%	0.24%	0.10%	0.36%	
	Ind#3	0.01%	0.01%	0.12%	0.05%	0.18%	
TOT	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.03%	0.55%
	Ind#2	0.02%	0.02%	0.22%	0.09%	0.34%	
	Ind#3	0.01%	0.01%	0.11%	0.05%	0.18%	

total%		Final User				Total Real GVA Growth Contributions	
		Country#1		Country#2			
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other		
Country#1	Ind#1	0.40%	0.07%	0.55%	0.12%	1.14%	4.88%
	Ind#2	0.17%	0.19%	1.00%	0.43%	1.80%	
	Ind#3	0.69%	0.23%	0.66%	0.36%	1.94%	
Country#2	Ind#1	0.03%	0.00%	0.08%	0.00%	0.11%	2.68%
	Ind#2	0.14%	0.13%	0.70%	0.35%	1.33%	
	Ind#3	0.15%	0.13%	0.70%	0.27%	1.24%	
TOT	Ind#1	0.08%	0.01%	0.14%	0.02%	0.25%	2.97%
	Ind#2	0.15%	0.14%	0.74%	0.36%	1.39%	
	Ind#3	0.22%	0.14%	0.69%	0.29%	1.34%	

Fig. 12 Real GVA growth contributions by value chain type, value-added source, and final user year t at previous year's prices: an illustrative numerical example

4.4 Real GVA growth contributions by final user

The growth contributions by final user are obtained, in accordance with Eq. (24), as the ratios of the differences between the matrices shown in Figures 10 and 8 to the countries' base-period ($t-1$) value added. These results are presented in Figure 12.

Naturally, the row totals correspond to the respective values shown in Figure 11; the differences arise solely in the columns and internal elements of the matrices. On this basis, it can be clearly observed, for example, that the 1.03% traditional-trade-related growth of Industry#2 in Country#1 is primarily explained by the contribution of Country#2's consumption demand to growth (0.73%).

4.5 Real FU growth contributions

Finally, we can also express the contributions of the various types of value chains to the real growth of final use. For this purpose, in accordance with Eq.(25), the differences between the matrices in Figures 10 and 8 must be divided not by base-period national value added, but by the total national final-use values. The results are presented in Figure 13.

pudo%		Final User					
		Country#1		Country#2		TOT	
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other	Households	Other
Country#1	Ind#1	0.36%	0.05%	0.00%	0.00%	0.05%	0.01%
	Ind#2	0.11%	0.15%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.02%
	Ind#3	0.64%	0.20%	0.00%	0.00%	0.08%	0.03%
Country#2	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.07%	0.00%	0.06%	0.00%
	Ind#2	0.00%	0.00%	0.47%	0.25%	0.40%	0.22%
	Ind#3	0.00%	0.00%	0.58%	0.23%	0.50%	0.20%
Total Real FU Growth Contributions		1.11%	0.40%	1.11%	0.47%	1.11%	0.46%
		1.51%		1.59%		1.58%	

trtr%		Final User					
		Country#1		Country#2		TOT	
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other	Households	Other
Country#1	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.06%	0.01%	0.05%	0.01%
	Ind#2	0.00%	0.00%	0.11%	0.05%	0.10%	0.04%
	Ind#3	0.00%	0.00%	0.07%	0.04%	0.06%	0.04%
Country#2	Ind#1	0.15%	0.01%	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.00%
	Ind#2	0.59%	0.55%	0.00%	0.00%	0.08%	0.07%
	Ind#3	0.73%	0.69%	0.00%	0.00%	0.10%	0.09%
Total Real FU Growth Contributions		1.47%	1.25%	0.24%	0.10%	0.40%	0.25%
		2.73%		0.33%		0.65%	

sGVC%		Final User					
		Country#1		Country#2		TOT	
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other	Households	Other
Country#1	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.01%	0.02%	0.01%
	Ind#2	0.00%	0.00%	0.03%	0.02%	0.03%	0.01%
	Ind#3	0.00%	0.00%	0.02%	0.01%	0.02%	0.01%
Country#2	Ind#1	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
	Ind#2	0.27%	0.26%	0.00%	0.00%	0.04%	0.03%
	Ind#3	0.19%	0.11%	0.00%	0.00%	0.03%	0.01%
Total Real FU Growth Contributions		0.48%	0.37%	0.07%	0.03%	0.13%	0.08%
		0.85%		0.11%		0.20%	

cGVC%		Final User					
		Country#1		Country#2		TOT	
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other	Households	Other
Country#1	Ind#1	0.03%	0.02%	0.01%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%
	Ind#2	0.06%	0.05%	0.01%	0.01%	0.02%	0.01%
	Ind#3	0.06%	0.04%	0.01%	0.00%	0.02%	0.01%
Country#2	Ind#1	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%	0.01%	0.00%
	Ind#2	0.08%	0.07%	0.24%	0.10%	0.22%	0.09%
	Ind#3	0.05%	0.04%	0.12%	0.05%	0.11%	0.05%
Total Real FU Growth Contributions		0.28%	0.21%	0.39%	0.16%	0.38%	0.17%
		0.49%		0.55%		0.55%	

total%		Final User					
		Country#1		Country#2		TOT	
Value Added		Households	Other	Households	Other	Households	Other
Country#1	Ind#1	0.40%	0.07%	0.08%	0.02%	0.13%	0.03%
	Ind#2	0.17%	0.20%	0.15%	0.07%	0.16%	0.08%
	Ind#3	0.69%	0.24%	0.10%	0.05%	0.18%	0.08%
Country#2	Ind#1	0.17%	0.01%	0.08%	0.00%	0.09%	0.00%
	Ind#2	0.95%	0.88%	0.70%	0.35%	0.74%	0.42%
	Ind#3	0.97%	0.84%	0.70%	0.27%	0.73%	0.35%
Total Real FU Growth Contributions		3.35%	2.23%	1.82%	0.76%	2.02%	0.95%
		5.59%		2.58%		2.97%	

Fig. 13 Real FU growth contributions by value chain type, value-added source, and final user for year t at previous year's prices: an illustrative numerical example

It can be observed that in the smaller Country#1, the volume of final use (5.59%) increased at a higher rate than income—that is, gross value added (4.88%). In contrast, in the larger Country#2, economic growth (as measured by GVA growth, 2.94%) exceeded final-use growth (2.58%) by a small margin.

Just as in the case of economic growth, the expansion of final use in Country#1 was driven primarily by traditional foreign trade (2.73%). By contrast, in Country#2 the main engine of final-use growth was the domestic economy.

5 Empirical applications

After the illustrative calculations based on a hypothetical example, let us examine the results obtained using real countries, real sectors, and real data. These can be found in global or world input-output databases. The first paragraph of Subsection 3.1 listed several such databases. Of these, to date, only the *World Input-Output Database* (WIOD) contains both current- and previous-year price tables. Thus, for our dynamic analyses and the calculation of real growth contributions, this is currently the only database available.

Subsection 5.1 reviews the range of raw data available in WIOD relevant to our analysis. Subsection 5.2 presents how we processed these raw data using the methods outlined in Sections 3–4. We also address the transformations and balancing that were necessary, as well as the limitations that arise even at the raw-data level. Finally, we present all the result tables, their structure, and the variables they contain, that is, the complete GVC real growth contribution database that we compiled from these.

5.1 Raw data: the World Input-Output Database (WIOD)

The *World Input-Output Database* (WIOD) (Dietzenbacher et al., 2013; M. P. Timmer et al., 2015), first released in 2012, remains a key resource for analysing the evolution of global economic structures over time. The WIOD Release 2016 (M. P. Timmer et al., 2016) and the subsequent *Long-run WIOD* version (Woltjer et al., 2021) extended the scope of the original project and database by increasing sectoral resolution and expanding geographical and temporal coverage.

The standard WIOTs in Release 2016 cover 43 countries, and a model for the rest of the world (ROW) for the period 2000-2014. Data for 5 final user sectors and 56 industries are classified according to the International Standard Industrial Classification of All Economic Activities, Revision 4 (ISIC Rev. 4). The tables adhere to the 2008 version of the SNA.

The long-run time series of WIOTs has been estimated for the period 1965-2000, encompassing the period of the Golden Age of Growth, characterised by increasing production and consumption, including the integration of Japan, South Korea and other East-Asian countries in the world economy, and the continuous integration of countries within the European Union. The tables include data for 25 developed countries and 23 industries, classified according to the International Standard Industrial Classification of All Economic Activities (ISIC Rev. 3). The tables adhere to the 1993 version of the SNA.

In addition to the time series of current price tables, both the WIOD and the Long-run WIOD also include time series of constant price (previous year's prices) tables (Los et al., 2014), making them exceptionally well-suited for our analytical purposes. Based on them, we can examine economic growth for the periods 1966-2000 and 2001-2014, both globally and by country and sector. This is also why the following phrase appears in the title: Golden Age of Growth, meaning that our analyses are rather historical in nature; not only the ones prepared with the Long-run WIOD, but even those made with the standard WIOD.

Moreover, the number of countries and sectors included in the Long-run WIOD is more limited. Its coverage does not extend to less developed countries that integrated into GVCs later, so their contributions to growth cannot be examined with this database. For this reason, this paper uses the Long-run WIOD database mainly for global analyses. Analyses that distinguish individual countries will be conducted primarily using the standard WIOD dataset covering the 2000-2014 period, which spans a significant part of the golden era of GVCs.

5.2 Resulting model data: the GVC Growth Contribution Database (GVC-GCD)

The decomposition schemes presented in Sections 3-4 were applied to the current year's (*cy*) and previous year's price (*pyp*) WIOTs available in the WIOD and the Long-run WIOD.

Some adjustments were necessary for the Long-run WIOD *pyp* tables. Here, the rows of the final demand (**F**) matrix were balanced to ensure that the row and column totals of the input-output tables (i.e., total output and input) matched perfectly in every country-industry.⁵ However, perfect alignment of global gross value added and global final products (final use) is still not guaranteed, neither for the balanced Long-run nor for the original standard WIOD tables. These insignificant discrepancies were accepted (and ignored in subsequent analyses) without any further balancing.

As a result, we produced a variety of decomposition table series, which we organised into a unified database named the *GVC Growth Contribution Database* (GVC-GCD). The data is available in text files containing semicolon-separated values. Figure 14 shows the structure and contents of the database, which can be downloaded as a zip file (approx. 3 GB, after unzipping ~11 GB) from the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20533035>.⁶

Fig. 14 The structure and contents of the GVC Growth Contribution Database.

Two separate folders contain the real growth contributions to gross value added (*GVA Real Growth*) and final use (*FU Real Growth*). The latter was prepared exclusively for the standard WIOD due to the Long-run WIOD balancing mentioned earlier. We compiled all data for the period 2001-2014 into a single large file (*GVC Real FU Growth Contributions Full Final Use 2001-2014.txt*). In each data file, the first row contains descriptive field names: *Year*; *Value_Chain_Type*; *VA_Country*; *VA_Industry*; *FU_Country*; *FU_Sector*; and *Value* (*VA* and *FU* stand for Value Added and Final Use, respectively). *Value_Chain_Type* can be *pudo%*, *trtr%*, *sGVC%*, or *cGVC%* according to the definitions in Sections 3-4. Fields *VA_Country*, *VA_Industry*, *FU_Country*, and *FU_Sector* contain country, productive industry, and final user sector codes. For the full list of codes and corresponding names, see Appendix C. *Values*

⁵ For the balancing, we used an additive correction procedure: all deviations between input and output were distributed among the elements of **F** according to the proportions of the absolute values of the original elements of **F**. For an iterative application of this method for two-directional matrix balancing, see Revesz (2025) and Révész and Koppány (2018).

⁶ When using this database, please refer this working paper: Koppány, K., & Vakhal, P. (2026). Economic Growth in Global Value Chains. Lessons from the Golden Age with a New Input-Output Decomposition Framework and Database. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20535821>

express growth contributions to the countries' national-level real economic growth. For contributions to global growth, use TOT as the *VA_Country*. Values in the txt files are given in a scientific format. To display them when processing the data, use percentage format (or multiply them by 100 and add a percent symbol).

The contributions to the real growth of gross value added are contained in several subfolders. Decompositions by *Final Users* also rely on the standard WIOD and include the results for the entire 2001-2014 period in a single file. There are two versions available: a smaller database that only distinguishes between final use countries (*FU_Country*) (*GVC Real GVA Growth Contributions Final Use 2001-2014.txt*). We recommend this for those who want a less detailed, quickly processable analysis. The more detailed version, roughly five times larger (*GVC Real GVA Growth Contributions Full Final Use 2001-2014.txt*), also contains a breakdown by final user sectors (*FU_Sector*).

The largest datasets are related to decompositions by final-product-producing countries (*FP_Country*) and sectors (*FP_Industry*). For the years 1966 to 2000, the files prepared based on the Long-run WIOD contain the data for five-year subperiods. The names corresponding to the country and sector codes in the database are provided in Appendix D.

For the years between 2001 and 2014, the files prepared based on the standard WIOD are even larger than the previous ones, even though there is a separate file for each year. The most detailed (and time-consuming) analyses can be prepared with these. Figure 15 shows an excerpt from the *GVC Real GVA Growth Contributions Final Product 2014.txt*.

```
Year;Value_Chain_Type;VA_Country;VA_Industry;FP_Country;FP_Industry;Value
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;A01;2.92183707610885E-04
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;A02;2.09384621337119E-07
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;A03;2.50930288653698E-06
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;B;-1.79786753575995E-06
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C10-C12;1.91144190633607E-04
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C13-C15;1.05773676522741E-05
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C16;5.05717743611599E-08
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C17;4.38597998215398E-07
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C18;9.69320674079937E-08
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C19;1.12788090602967E-06
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C20;3.16875591291179E-06
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C21;5.38590753377322E-06
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C22;3.94441715903642E-07
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C23;1.06275953072655E-07
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C24;3.69048750245052E-07
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C25;3.36902911522806E-07
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C26;1.00220619010964E-07
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C27;2.11377926844068E-07
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C28;2.87702748040392E-07
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C29;2.06729797150315E-06
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C30;6.2290858009466E-07
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;C31-C32;4.43258067256757E-07
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;D35;9.65818070450589E-07
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;E36;5.70159795292962E-07
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;E37-E39;1.86513708695361E-08
2014;pudo%;AUS;A01;AUS;F;4.86311736924351E-05
```

Fig. 15 An extract from the GVC Growth Contribution Database (GVC Real GVA Growth Contributions Final Product 2014.txt).

6 Analyses and results

The purpose of Section 6 is twofold. First, it aims to demonstrate the various applications of the database; second, it seeks to contribute new findings to the literature on GVC analysis.

6.1 The weight and role of value chains in global GVA and GVA growth

Figure 16 presents the long-run evolution of the weight and role of value chains in global GVA and growth. Panels A and B show the share of value chain types in value-added generation. They make it clear that during the period under review, foreign trade and global value chains gradually played an increasingly important role, while pure domestic value chains declined; however, on a global scale, they still provide the majority of value added. This remains completely hidden when using decomposition schemes restricted to gross exports.

Fig. 16 Share (panels A and B), real growth contributions (panel C), and real growth of value chain types (panel D).
 Notes: global value added is gross value added (GVA) of all countries in WIOD and the rest of the World (ROW); shares have been calculated using nominal GVA at current prices.

With the share of domestic value chains falling from 91% to 80%, the share of foreign trade increased from 3% to 7%, and that of global value chains rose from 6% to 13%. Panels A and B clearly show that, apart from short-term turbulence, these changes were gradual, and that global value chains, as defined in Section 3, existed even before the onset of the outsourcing wave and the integration of less developed countries from the 1990s onward.

Panel C was created using the GVC-GCD. It highlights that the growth contribution of pure domestic value chains has declined alongside their weight, but remains the highest, whereas for other types of value chains, no clear increasing or decreasing trend can be identified.

Based on the definitions and relations described in Section 3, growth contributions divided by shares (weights) yield growth rates of the components. They are shown in Panel D, which reveals that, over the nearly half-century investigated, the growth rate of pure domestic value-added was consistently the lowest. Its high growth contribution was solely due to its large weight. The figure also shows, however, that the growth rate of complex global value chains was highest in almost every year, not only since the 1990s but even earlier. This made it possible to gradually increase their weight (share) in GVA from 1% to 5% over the years. Let us also note that the growth rate of each type of value chain shows a declining trend.

6.2 Growth clusters: a country-level descriptive comparative analysis

Having examined the diverse interrelationships between long-term global growth and value chains from multiple perspectives, let us now examine the details that emerge when we zoom in to the level of national economies. Global results are generally determined by data from the largest economies. At the national level, significant deviations and varied patterns may emerge.

Figure 17 shows the average growth for the 2001–2014 period covered by WIOD, along with their breakdown by value chain type for each country in the database. This period can even be regarded as the golden age of GVCs, and by then, a number of less developed countries had also joined them.

We have ranked and grouped countries by growth rate and composition. Figure 17 shows them in this order, with those most similar in terms of both the level and composition of total growth placed side by side. The white and grey bars indicate countries that are clustered according to the applied criteria.

The list is led by China, India and Indonesia. All three countries are characterised by growth rates significantly exceeding those of the others, with domestic value chains contributing most. In the case of China, growth stemming from integration into world trade and global value chains is also notable, yet even so, it ranks only third behind two other, much smaller countries—Slovakia and Lithuania, which will be discussed later. However, in terms of their proportions and scale, the dominance of domestic value chains can still be observed in China, India and Indonesia alike. This somewhat contradicts the hypothesis that the growth of East Asian countries has been primarily export-driven since China's accession to the WTO (e.g. Ahmad et al. (2018); Tang et al. (2015)). Although net exports undoubtedly played a role in these outstanding results, the contribution of investment and private consumption to growth was much greater in all three countries (Prasad, 2011). This demand was met primarily from domestic sources rather than through imports. According to Baldwin et al. (2022, 2023), China's exposure to imported intermediates has fallen since the mid-2000s. The rapid economic growth of South-East Asian countries was therefore based primarily on improvements in living standards driven by productivity growth and, above all, on an endogenous growth model (Foster-McGregor & Verspagen, 2016; Siddiqui & Rehman, 2017).

Fig. 17 Average real GVA growth and GVA growth contributions by value chain type in WIOD countries between 2001 and 2014.

Russia and the unspecified countries of the WIOD (ROW) also achieved average growth of nearly 4%, above the global average, between 2001 and 2014. The contribution of traditional foreign trade value chains here is smaller, particularly in the case of Russia, where domestic value chains also tended to dominate, despite the fact that one of the cornerstones of the Russian economy is the export of mined raw materials, which, given its high degree of upstreamness, would primarily support growth stemming from simple and complex global value chains. At the same time, since the turn of the millennium, GDP production in Russia, as in other former planned economies, has shifted towards services. Financial and business services account for approximately 10% of total value added, and other service sectors (telecommunications, construction, tourism, retail, etc.) have also grown extremely rapidly, whilst manufacturing and agriculture have contributed only modestly to growth. Services rely on domestic resources, so the high weight of domestic value chains is not surprising in an emerging country where prosperity is growing faster than in developed countries. Meanwhile, the oil and gas industry's contribution to GDP has steadily declined, or at least stagnated, largely due to sanctions following the occupation of the Crimean Peninsula (Tuzova & Qayum, 2016). In addition, construction investment also rose significantly following the global economic crisis, again relying on domestic value chains (Voskoboynikov, 2017). Nearly three-quarters of this growth was driven by domestic demand and value added generated within domestic value chains.

This proportion is even higher in Australia and Brazil, although it is associated with somewhat lower average economic growth of around 3%. Changes in GVA volume in Australia are clearly dominated by domestic value chains: the share of domestic value added is significantly higher than the global average in both final and intermediate consumption. GDP is primarily driven by services and mining. Mining products are supplied to downstream value chains, which support growth through both simple and complex GVCs. The greater role of

simple GVCs stems partly from the nature of the exported goods and partly from relative geographical isolation. Trading partners are primarily Asian countries where finished goods are typically produced, which aligns with the definition of simple value chains (Kelly & La Cava, 2014). The situation is similar in Brazil, where GDP is driven primarily by domestic consumption rather than net exports. As an emerging country, services account for an increasing share of expenditure year on year, so the production of value added is steadily shifting towards pure domestic value chains (Alves-Passoni & Neria, 2023).

Next come two more countries characterised by higher growth rates: Turkey and Romania. Even in their cases, the average contribution of pure domestic value chains remains significant (around 60% of total growth), yet external links now play a much greater role, both in foreign trade (particularly in Turkey) and in global value chains. Turkey's integration into the latter is the result of a process that began in the 1990s, during which the vertical specialisation of the Turkish economy grew increasingly strong, primarily in textiles, metals, and automotive products (Kılavuz et al., 2013). The FDI absorption economic policy has successfully integrated the Turkish manufacturing sector into global value chains. This has led to strong backward integration, in which production is primarily based on the processing of imported inputs (Gündoğdu & Saracoğlu, 2016). In some respects, Romania has followed a similar path since the transition, though its participation is much more forward-looking. Romanian exports consist of a mix of finished goods (primarily motor vehicles) and semi-finished goods, with domestic value added well above the regional average (Şerbănel, 2015; Vakhal, 2023).

The next group comprises countries (Korea, Taiwan, Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia, Poland) that have continued to achieve significant growth of roughly 4% per annum (Lithuania even exceeding this), with their pure domestic value chains contributing at least 1 percentage point to this. In Korea, this contribution is almost 2 percentage points, so here, unlike the other countries listed, internal value chains still account for more than half of the growth. From other perspectives, however, it does in fact resemble the countries following it in the ranking more closely than those ahead of it. In this group, therefore, average GVA growth is still well above the global average, but the role of domestic value chains in economic growth is now smaller in proportion, though still significant (20–50 per cent). These are typically small, open economies where exports account for a relatively high share of GDP, as does integration into GVCs. The cases of these countries demonstrate that intensive participation in the international division of labour does not necessarily entail the decline of domestic value chains. It is characteristic of both South Korea and Taiwan, as well as of countries that operated under a planned economy prior to 1990, that they built up their domestic value chains before 1990, thus possessing a relatively developed industrial structure on which they could rely during their integration into GVCs (Hauge, 2020). Furthermore, the service sector in the Baltic states is well developed, and a significant proportion of their exports consists of services to Northern European countries, indicating a relatively high contribution to traditional foreign trade and simple value chains. These services are typically knowledge-based, meaning they generate higher value added, which also boosts the productivity of the non-tradable sector, thereby increasing the contribution of purely domestic value chains to growth (Benkovskis et al., 2020; Kapela, 2024).

The cases of Bulgaria and Slovakia are quite unique, as they have average growth rates well above the global average (over 4% in Slovakia), whilst, in contrast to the countries examined so far, this is overwhelmingly based on value added arising from the international division of labour. The contribution of domestic value chains does not reach 1 percentage point; in terms of share, it is barely 20% in Bulgaria and barely 10% in Slovakia. In Slovakia, the contribution of foreign trade and global value chains to growth is particularly high, the highest among all

countries. Both countries are deeply and backwards-linked into global value chains, meaning that foreign value added accounts for a high proportion of their output, whether in exports or domestic consumption. Bulgaria has made significant progress since joining the EU, mainly thanks to the Cohesion Funds, but has been unable to improve its relative development over the past two decades. The service sector, which contributed significantly to growth in the countries examined previously, has remained notably underdeveloped (Ivanova & Ivanov, 2017). Partly as a result of this, the complexity of the Bulgarian economy has not improved substantially since EU accession; production is heavily import-dependent and international competitiveness is based on low cost levels, which do not make domestic value chains productive, and they struggle to compete with imports (Magistretti & Vassileva, 2024).

The case of Slovakia is somewhat similar to that of Bulgaria, as services are also overshadowed by the manufacturing sector. The Slovak automotive industry is one of the sectors most deeply integrated into international value chains worldwide and is, moreover, heavily dependent on German demand. This integration is characterised by extremely strong backward linkages, based on the processing of imported semi-finished products, which are then exported as semi-finished or finished goods. The majority of Slovakia's GDP is generated by large international corporations through participation in GVCs (Ciešlik et al., 2021), meaning that the bulk of capacity is tied up in simple or complex value chains, effectively crowding out pure domestic value chains. It is important to note, however, that Slovakia's GDP per capita has grown significantly, and its relative position among the Member States that joined in 2004 has improved considerably, reflecting a significant increase in productivity.

The following cluster comprises several smaller countries at varying stages of development, with growth rates of around 2–3 per cent: Malta, Luxembourg, Ireland, Cyprus, the Czech Republic, Hungary and Slovenia. In each of these countries, the contribution of foreign trade and global value chains to overall growth is significant, at 70% or higher. It is important to note that, in addition to being among the world's most open economies (with exports exceeding 100% of GDP), these countries are also relatively small. Their growth potential clearly lies in exports, and they can capitalise on their local comparative advantages in export sectors, which underpin their growth. However, despite a high export share, this ensures only moderate growth, as it is based much more on volume than on productivity gains or optimal capacity allocation. Weber (2011) notes that export demand in these countries is met primarily by foreign companies rather than by domestic firms, thereby positioning the countries within a long supply chain. The FDI-promoting economic policies of the countries concerned typically place little emphasis on established firms using local suppliers. Consequently, production's import requirements are very high, continuously stifling and leaving growth only average despite the exceptional openness. Foreign firms that have set up operations are typically far more competitive in relatively small domestic markets, thereby crowding out purely domestic value chains; consequently, domestic final consumption is increasingly met by complex value chains, leading to higher import requirements for private consumption, which also acts against growth. At the same time, this has a positive impact on welfare, as the more competitive complex GVCs can offer price advantages to the domestic market (Marčeta & Bojnec, 2023).

Interestingly, Slovakia and Poland do not fit into this pattern. The latter, because its domestic market is significantly larger, which creates demand for the output of domestic value chains; on the other hand, Polish economic policy has placed greater emphasis on involving domestic suppliers in FDI absorption strategies. Another important difference between the group under review and Slovakia is that in the former (particularly Ireland, Malta and Cyprus), the share of services in exports is very high. In contrast, in Slovak production, the share of the

manufacturing sector (and, within that, the automotive industry) is high, and productivity improvements have been significant, though from relatively low levels. Nevertheless, during the period under review, which was characterised by a strong boom in the automotive industry, Slovakia secured a significant share of this, with positive welfare effects (although significantly lower than GVA-growth), and an improved contribution of domestic value chains to growth (particularly through retail trade and the construction industry). As growth was largely volume-based, these companies gradually became dominant producers in the country. After 2014, however, the global automotive industry began to slow, a trend felt in countries with a high concentration of automotive production.

It is worth treating the new EU Member States separately when considering their contribution to growth. As in Slovakia, the manufacturing sector in the other Member States primarily exports value added rather than meeting domestic demand. As mentioned above, domestic value chains consist primarily of services; at the same time, the contribution to growth from exports is so high that the contribution of domestic value chains pales in comparison. Hagemeyer's (2018) calculations show that productivity growth in both the Czech Republic and Hungary was significantly faster in those sectors that used more imported semi-finished products, that is, the contribution to growth of sectors integrated into value chains with strong backward linkages has become increasingly significant over time, despite the fact that they produce relatively low value added, but in terms of volume, considerably more than pure domestic value chains (Koppány, 2017a).

These are followed by countries characterised by even lower growth, at around 1.5%, generally with a pure domestic contribution that is greater than or equal to that of the former: Croatia, Switzerland, Belgium and Austria. In their case, average growth already lags behind the global average; however, as they are developed countries (with the exception of Croatia), this is not particularly surprising, since these economies have already moved beyond the phase of rapid catch-up. Services play a much greater role in GDP (particularly in Austria and Switzerland) than in emerging countries, indeed, manufacturing output also contains a much higher proportion of services, which typically represent higher local value added, thereby strengthening the role of domestic value chains in domestic final consumption (Stehrer & Stöllinger, 2013), not to mention that, as a result, exports also contain higher domestic value added. All this results in a nominally higher welfare effect even with lower growth, and generates demand for the output of domestic value chains, primarily through services. When discussing developed countries, it is essential to mention the high price levels of non-tradable goods (mainly services), characterised by higher wages and a shift in consumption towards these goods (De Gregorio et al., 1994). Meanwhile, the prices of manufactured goods are rising more slowly due to strong international competition and technological progress (Lipseý et al., 1990), leading to a greater weight of domestic value chains in final consumption in developed countries.

In the case of Belgium, an interesting observation can be made based on Bernon et al. (2025): the country can be divided into two radically different parts in terms of value chains. The Flemish regions are much more strongly integrated into the international division of labour, whereas Brussels and the Walloon regions are presumably more dominated by local value chains. Alongside regional polarisation, this also suggests that the multipliers of different types of value chains differ.

Croatia is something of an odd one out in this context, as it is an emerging country that nevertheless differs somewhat from the other new EU Member States. The higher-than-average share of pure domestic value chains stems in part from the country's significant tourism growth

driver. Of course, this would not count as pure domestic final consumption, but rather as simple trade, as consumption by foreign tourists is not part of domestic private consumption. However, the statistical representation of tourism consumption is based on sampling, which may cause some distortion. What is certain, however, is that in Croatia the role of the manufacturing sector in GDP is significantly smaller than in the other new EU Member States, and services and private consumption clearly dominate. For this reason, the country has effectively missed out on the GVC boom. Croatia's GVC participation has not changed significantly for a long time; it participates less in the international division of labour than other Eastern European countries. Consequently, domestic value chains play a greater role in production, particularly due to the tourism sector in the broadest sense (Peruško et al., 2018).

Figure 17 then shows two developed Western European countries, the Netherlands and Germany, with an average growth rate of 1.2%, where the contribution of domestic value chains is effectively zero or negative. Germany occupies a special place in the world of global value chains, as, unlike the countries examined so far, it serves as a kind of hub in the international division of labour. German-owned companies have a significant share of value added in almost every international value chain. Moreover, Germany is one of the largest markets in Europe and the world. Against this backdrop, the near-zero contribution to growth made by pure domestic German value chains between 2000 and 2014 may seem a strange result at first glance, yet it is most likely caused precisely by Germany's strong international presence. The demand of German companies is met by German-owned firms in numerous countries. This is particularly true of German private consumption, which, even when it extends to German products, contains a sophisticated international dimension that manifests itself partly as imports (Eppinger et al., 2021). In other words, demand for apparently pure German value chains also manifests itself partly in other countries, resulting in a very low domestic contribution to growth. This global exposure cannot, in principle, be viewed as unequivocally negative, but it must be added that this type of import dependency can be a serious disadvantage in the case of economic stimulus packages designed to boost private consumption, as relatively little growth in pure domestic value added can be achieved through them, thereby leaving the economy at the mercy of external supply.

The Netherlands' economic structure is similar to Germany's, and the use of re-imported domestic value-added plays a major role. This is also reflected in the steady decline in the share of domestic value added in both domestic consumption and exports, which, in turn, implies a lower growth rate (M. Timmer & Vries, 2015). Nor should we forget the ports in the Netherlands and Germany, which serve as Europe's gateways to world trade, as this can cause accounting difficulties.

In Denmark and Japan, the average rate of total growth is even lower, but the contribution of domestic value chains is more significant. Japan's growth problems are also evident in this structure. Before the turn of the millennium, Japan's GVC integration was relatively high among developed countries, but today it has fallen significantly to roughly half that level, just as in other East Asian countries such as South Korea or Taiwan. Meanwhile, the integration of India, China and other emerging countries has risen significantly. Similar processes took place as in Germany, with the difference that in Japan, it was primarily global exporting companies that relocated their production abroad, whereas producers for the local market did not do so; in other words, Japan typically does not import semi-finished or finished products from Japanese companies based abroad for domestic use. To meet export demand, given that Japan's export structure consists of high-tech products, foreign value added is also utilised; however, original Japanese value added accounts for a larger share of domestic final consumption. For this reason,

although growth is low due to known structural problems, the share of pure domestic value chains is proportionally higher than in other countries producing high-tech manufactured goods (Kiyota et al., 2017).

Although structurally similar, the Danish case can be attributed to different causes. As a developed country, growth below the global average is not surprising. It is a small and open country where services account for a much larger share of GDP in final consumption than in emerging countries. There is also strong regional integration within Scandinavia, characterised by a high degree of mutual utilisation of domestic value added. Vertical specialisation is also observed in these countries (Andersen et al., 2015).

Next come three Mediterranean countries, Portugal, Italy and Greece, in which the contribution of domestic value chains is negative across the board. The positive impact of external value chains attempts to offset this, but in the latter two countries, this is not entirely successful, so overall average growth is also negative in those countries. The situation of the peripheral European countries is quite unique. They integrated relatively quickly into European and global value chains, but were unable to capitalise effectively on the resulting benefits. Their export competitiveness is relatively weak compared to the core European countries and even to the new EU Member States, reflected in their relatively low level of domestic value-added supply. Consequently, their contribution to growth through value chains is also low. Import consumption is very strong in domestic final consumption, so pure domestic value chains cannot significantly support growth in this dimension either. Domingues et al. (2021) highlight that the position of domestic producers has weakened in several countries and that deindustrialisation remains evident, particularly in Portugal. The global economic crisis has eroded domestic purchasing power in the affected countries, and domestic private consumption is very weak. The domestic corporate structure is struggling with serious competitiveness issues and low productivity, which has often led to import substitution, to the detriment of domestic value chains. The economy's export competitiveness has also deteriorated, with a strong shift in supply towards low-value-added products.

Next come the Scandinavian and other Western European countries (Finland, France, Spain and Sweden), showing growth of between 1% and 2%, where internal value chains account for more than half, and in some cases three-quarters, of that growth.

Norway stands completely apart from the rest. Although its average growth is positive (around 1.5%), this is entirely due to domestic value chains, which offset the negative external growth effects.

The US, a textbook example of a large and closed economy, is the world's largest economy, but, in this sense, only the second most closed. Nearly 90% of its average annual growth of around 1.6% is driven by its domestic value chains, which also leave their mark on global data.

Bringing up the rear, with an average growth rate of roughly 2%, are the UK, Canada and Mexico, where foreign trade and global value chains account for between 15% and 25%, with varying compositions.

The situation on the North American continent is quite unique, as within global value chains, the region is surrounded by a relatively closed (regional) value chain, with the United States at its centre. This 'regional organisation' fits well with the observation that a significant proportion of value chains operate not along global but regional lines, and that final demand (particularly in the US) exerts a strong pull on supplier networks.

The US situation is also interesting because the contribution to growth from pure domestic value chains is one of the highest here; in other words, the country allows relatively little foreign value added into its own value creation structure, whilst the contribution to growth from

complex and simple global value chains (GVCs) is relatively low. One important (and often misunderstood) reason for this is methodological: in Wang's classification, the 'pure domestic' category strictly measures the extent to which domestic final demand is satisfied by value added whose factor content does not cross borders for production purposes. In the case of a large and deep domestic market, many activities, among them those of foreign-owned resident companies, therefore remain recorded as 'domestic chains' (Degain et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2017b). WIOD-based results support this. The foreign value-added content of US exports is low compared to, for example, European hubs, which mechanically increases the weight of domestic chains in value-added-based decompositions (Meng et al., 2012).

This, however, does not mean that the US does not participate in value chains; on the contrary, a significant proportion of global corporations are American. At the same time, a significant portion of the value added is generated by American firms outside the US, in the countries where the subsidiaries are located. Thus, under a residence-based accounting system, it cannot be counted as US value added (Herzer, 2010; Lipsey, 2010). The consequence is that the US has the largest trade deficit in value added in the world: US final consumption induces value-added production 'worldwide', which manifests itself in large volumes as imports, whilst the share of foreign value added in exports remains relatively low.

It is important to emphasise, however, that a low contribution of GVCs to US growth does not mean that the US has a 'small' global impact. Growth decomposition breaks down the types of value added generated domestically, whilst the 'global multiplier effect' describes the direct and indirect ripple effects that US final demand (consumption and investment) triggers in the global economy. In the input-output approach, final demand not only generates direct imports but also induces production at multiple levels of supply chains, including in third countries, a phenomenon that is particularly pronounced in the case of a major global centre of demand such as the US.

Following the 2007 global economic crisis, a structural shift in US growth can be observed, with the emphasis shifting towards pure domestic value chains and traditional foreign trade. This can be partly interpreted in the context of emerging protectionist economic policies (particularly the intensification of regulatory and normative frictions); however, according to the literature, this is not a single 'deliberate deglobalisation' decision, but rather the combined effect of multiple factors. This period also saw the slowdown of globalisation ('slowbalisation'), which was accompanied to a small extent by a wave of reshoring and a deepening of the domestic division of labour: whilst the number of cross-border movements decreased, production processes within national borders became longer and more fragmented (Antràs & Gortari, 2020). Barriers to trade naturally consist not only of tariffs, but also, and significantly, of transport costs and the administrative burdens of crossing borders. If production relies to a significant extent on imported semi-finished inputs, even a seemingly moderate transport/border cost can impose a disproportionately high cost advantage requirement on lower-cost assembly locations; that is, due to the repeated movement of intermediate inputs and the final product, supply chains may react in a 'threshold-like' manner to changes in friction. Consequently, the 'hyperglobalisation' of the post-1990 era led to a sharp increase in trade in intermediate goods and complex supply chains, partly because transport and trade liberalisation reduced this effective protection; however, when frictions and policy risk rose after the crisis, the dynamics of complex, multi-border supply chains understandably stalled (Krugman, 2017).

Nor should it be forgotten that the global economic crisis significantly increased the risks associated with integration into long value chains involving multiple cross-border movements

(primarily through inventories and stock of orders), and that complex GVC activities are cyclically more vulnerable: they expand more rapidly during an upturn but fall more sharply during a recession, and they provide less support for growth during the post-crisis stagnation period. In such an environment, it was often more advantageous for companies to turn to the domestic market (retaining certain production steps domestically), as during recessions, government incentives (demand stimulation, supplier programmes, public procurement preferences) typically support domestic players, and the US was no exception.

Finally, for benchmarking purposes, we have included the average global (TOT) growth rate (2.61%) and the contribution of the various value chain types to this figure. Of the 44 countries featured in the WIOD (including ROW), average national economic growth between 2001 and 2014 exceeded the global growth rate in 20 countries.

The countries outlined in the thick black rectangle, ranging from Taiwan to Greece (25 in total), were those in which foreign trade and global value chains played a greater role in average growth between 2001 and 2014 than purely domestic factors.

A total of 10 countries fall within the intersection of the previous two sets. In these countries, more than half of the growth is attributable to value chains that also include external elements, enabling them to grow faster than the global economy.

6.3 Growth dependencies

Of course, there are many other options to design country-level analyses. For example, one can decompose growth by final producers or final users to create heat maps that highlight growth driven by different direct and indirect domestic and global partners. Figure 18 illustrates this.

Fig. 18 Heat maps for growth-final product country dependencies (upper panel) and growth-final use country dependencies (lower panel)

In the rows, the source countries of added value are listed, where economic growth occurs. In the columns, the top panel shows the countries that produce the final product, and the bottom panel shows the countries that use it. The numbers in each row of the matrices indicate the percentage points by which the exporting countries, as end-product producers, and the importing countries, as end-product users, contributed on average to the growth of the row countries between 2001 and 2014. Green cells indicate positive contributions to growth, while red cells indicate negative contributions. The darker the shade within a given row, the greater (more positive) or smaller (more negative) the cell value.

Tables—for easier overview—do not include all WIOD countries, only the most significant countries of Factory North America, Factory Europe, and Factory Asia (Baldwin & Freeman, 2022), as well as some peripheral countries in Europe. The highest growth contributions are located along the main diagonal, especially in the top table. Italy is the only country where the overall negative growth is mainly due to a decline in domestic final goods production and use. The foreign final producer countries—particularly Germany and China—show a slight positive (0.02%) contribution to Italian growth.

In the 'three major factories', the leading role of the central countries is clearly visible: their final goods production generally has a greater influence on the growth of peripheral countries than vice versa. This asymmetry is quite evident in the case of the USA, Canada, and Mexico ($0.09\% > 0.02\%$, and $0.11\% > 0.01\%$). It is even more pronounced for Germany and the three peripheral countries listed (Czech Republic, Hungary, and Slovakia) ($0.22\% - 0.40\% > 0.01\% - 0.02\%$). However, in the relationship among the other three major economies (the United Kingdom, France, and Italy), the situation is reversed: their final production contributed more to German growth than German production contributed to theirs. The relationship between China and Japan during the examined period is relatively symmetrical, but Chinese final goods production contributed much more to Korea's and India's growth than vice versa.

In the lower panel of Figure 18, we see patterns that differ from those in the upper part in several respects. The main diagonal now contains the highest row elements in far fewer cases. Examples include the Czech Republic, Hungary, and Slovakia: German final utilisation contributed to higher growth in these countries than domestic consumption. A similar situation exists in Japan, where the role of Chinese final utilisation in growth was at least as significant as the domestic. The growth of the USA and Canada was restrained by the final utilisation of several foreign countries. For Canada, the most notable of these is the United States.

Considering the overall growth of the global economy (TOT series), China's significant role is clearly visible: as a final producer, it contributed an average of 0.74 percentage points, and as a final user, 0.66 percentage points to global growth, compared to the USA's contribution of 0.46-0.49 percentage points.

More detailed heat maps can serve as a basis for further clustering or network analyses to explore deeper patterns and dependencies in the growth structure of the world economy.

6.4 Determinants of economic growth in value chains: an econometric analysis

Based on the previous subsections, we can see that the extent and value chain structure of growth vary considerably across countries. The decompositions offered by the GVC-GCD allow us to examine these using econometric methods. On the one hand, we can create separate regression models for the growth contributions generated by each component of the value chain; on the other hand, we can define and derive additional explanatory variables based on the database. Examples of these include diversification of growth sources or, conversely, concentration indicators that reflect the opposite.

To illustrate the possibilities of statistical analysis, we followed the procedure below. During our investigation, we analysed the average growth rates of individual countries between 2001 and 2014, categorised by value chain type. The outcome variables were the growth contributions of pure domestic, traditional foreign trade, simple, and complex global value chains. Each was examined separately using regression models. Among the explanatory variables, we included the level and size of development and the domestic market at the beginning of the period (in 2000), as well as various concentration indicators.⁷ Development was measured by the per capita GDP at current prices in 2000, and the size of the domestic market by the level of final utilisation (excluding inventory changes). The former was sourced from the IMF World Economic Outlook (WEO) database, and the latter from the WIOD itself, specifically its 2000 current-price global input-output table. During the regressions, we used the natural logarithm of the two explanatory variables.

We examined the concentration of growth contributions according to different types of value chains from multiple perspectives and variables: value-added source industries (*VA_Industry*), final product-producing industries (*FP_Industry*), countries producing final products (*FP_Country*), and countries of final consumers (*FU_Country*). The concentration of the growth structure was measured using Herfindahl–Hirschman indices (*HHI*) (Herfindahl, 1950; Hirschman, 1945). This indicator can be calculated as the sum of the squares of the shares of individual components, thus being sensitive to the presence of dominant factors. Since the HHI is defined for non-negative shares, only industries and countries with positive growth contributions were included in the concentration calculation. The resulting indices therefore measure the concentration of the driving forces behind economic growth. Negative contributions, which act as dampening factors in growth dynamics, were excluded from the HHI calculations. However, their effects are reflected in the outcome variables.

The results of the econometric analysis are summarised in Table 3 and Figure 19. The former presents the regression model variants that provide the best fit, the greatest explanatory power, and the most significant explanatory variables for each type of value chain. Several of these models include interaction terms, so particular care must be taken when exploring the relationships between the explanatory and outcome variables.

Such a regression, shown in the first column, relates to the growth contribution of pure domestic value chains, where both the initial level of development (*ln_intl_dev*), the size of the domestic market (*ln_dom_mrkt*), and their product are significant explanatory variables. ($p \leq 0.001$). The regression coefficients for the three variables yield the following relationships for the examined period. (a) The higher a country's initial level of development, the generally smaller the growth it could achieve, except for the smallest countries (those with the smallest domestic markets), where a high initial level of development was associated with higher growth compared to countries of similar size but lower development levels (such as Luxembourg and Switzerland).⁸ (b) In most cases, there was a positive correlation between the size of the internal market and growth derived from pure domestic value chains, except in the most developed

⁷ The growth contributions are naturally also associated with many other variables used in growth theory, such as physical capital stock, foreign capital inflow, technological development, capacity utilisation, population, human capital stock, activity and employment, education, expenditures on research and development and education, fiscal and monetary conditions, etc. (Cervellati et al., 2023).

⁸ Based on well-known convergence theories (Barro, 1992; Galor, 1996; Sala-i-Martin, 1996a, 1996b), a negative relationship between the initial level of development and growth is expected. Our investigations reflect this across most countries; however, results that also depend on country size somewhat nuance the clear direction of this relationship—at least for the growth contributions of domestic value chains.

countries, where larger markets generally had a smaller proportion of growth (see, for example, the USA or Germany), or even experienced a decline (e.g., Italy).

The initial level of development is a significant explanatory variable for the growth contribution of all three other types of value chains, except for the complex global value chains. Furthermore, in the case of foreign trade and simple global value chains, the direction of the relationship is clearer than in the previous cases: less developed countries grew faster through foreign trade and simple global value chains than more developed countries.

The extent of growth through complex value chains, however, cannot be explained by development level. Both developed and less developed countries have achieved similar results in this regard. This is consistent with the literature, which suggests that participation in global value chains, even if limited to lower-end activities on the smile curve, offers growth opportunities for less developed countries (Raei & Ignatenko, 2019).

The size of the domestic market proved to be a significant explanatory variable for both foreign trade and global value chains. These results are consistent with the literature (Frederick, 2019; Kowalski et al., 2015; Raei & Ignatenko, 2019) and with prior expectations: the smaller a country's domestic consumer market, the more likely it is that export activity will be the main source of growth (provided that the necessary production capacities are available).

Table 3 Overview of Regression Models

Explanatory Variable / Model	pudo growth contributions (<i>avg_growth_contr_pudo%</i>)	trtr growth contributions (<i>avg_growth_contr_trtr%</i>)	sGVC growth contributions (<i>avg_growth_contr_sGVC%</i>)	cGVC growth contributions (<i>avg_growth_contr_cGVC%</i>)
<i>(Intercept)</i>	-41.23 ***	3.730 ***	3.209 ***	3.236 ***
<i>ln_intl_dev</i>	4.144 ***	-0.217 **	-0.166 **	–
<i>ln_dom_mrkt</i>	4.605 ***	-0.082 **	-0.084 **	-0.229 ***
<i>ln_intl_dev * ln_dom_mrkt</i>	-0.443 ***	–	–	–
<i>HHI_VA_ind_pudo%</i>	-0.113 ***	–	–	–
<i>HHI_FP_ind_trtr%</i>	–	0.019 *	–	–
<i>ln_intl_dev * HHI_FU_cou_trtr%</i>	–	-0.002 ***	–	–
<i>HHI_FP_cou_sGVC%</i>	–	–	-0.006	–
<i>HHI_FP_ind_cGVC%</i>	–	–	–	-0.046 ***
<i>HHI_FU_cou_cGVC%</i>	–	–	–	-0.191 ***
<i>ln_dom_mrkt * HHI_FU_cou_cGVC%</i>	–	–	–	0.013 **
R²	0.810	0.551	0.444	0.718
Adjusted R²	0.790	0.504	0.401	0.668
RMSE	0.718	0.32	0.269	0.166
F-statistic	40.49	11.68	10.38	24.19
F p-value	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001	< 0.001

Legend for significance stars: *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$.

In certain respects, concentration influenced growth rates across almost all types of value chains. In pure domestic value chains, the source industries of value added (i.e., the GVA sectoral structure) played a role; in simple global value chains, the countries producing the final product were influential; and in foreign trade and complex value chains, the concentration of

the final product-producing sectors and the final consumer countries (i.e., the ultimate sales markets) was significant.

The most evident was the negative relationship between the contribution of domestic value chains to growth and the concentration of GVA in the source industry structure: the higher the concentration, the greater the reduction in growth.

In the case of foreign trade value chains, conflicting effects, often cited in the analysis of the structural resilience (Braun & Sebestyén, 2025; Kiss et al., 2025), become apparent. Higher concentration enables more efficient utilisation of the benefits derived from specialisation. This endeavour frequently appears at an institutional level, as a strategic objective or programme within national or regional development policies, for example, in the EU Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) (Morrison & Pattinson, 2020). The growth advantages associated with specialisation manifest in the positive relationship between the concentration of final product-producing export sectors and growth derived from foreign trade (see the coefficient of $HHI_FP_ind_trtr\%$). Accordingly, a more concentrated foreign trade relying on fewer types of export goods can contribute to greater growth. However, the asymmetries resulting from excessive efficiency and concentration may lead to a more vulnerable economic structure. Shock impacts affecting key nodes and connections can be significantly amplified, thereby increasing exposure and risks, reducing economic resilience, and potentially negatively impacting long-term average growth. This correlation is reflected in the significantly negative coefficient for the concentration of growth contributions generated by countries that use the exported final products ($HHI_FU_cou_trtr\%$). This coefficient actually pertains to the interaction between the initial level of development and the concentration of export partners, meaning that the more developed a country is, the more it generally reduces the growth contribution of foreign trade through an increasingly concentrated export structure among partners. Overall, during the examined period, a more focused export structure by product type (industry) was associated with a greater contribution to foreign trade growth, whereas a more diversified export structure by partner countries was associated with a higher contribution to foreign trade growth.

The growth contribution of simple global value chains did not actually show any significant positive or negative relationship with any of the concentration measures. However, we still included the HH index, which has the greatest explanatory power, in the regression and reported it in Table 3. The increased concentration of partner countries producing the final product ($HHI_FP_cou_sGVC\%$) (in the case of simple global value chains, all export partners; we will return to the implications of this shortly in Subsection 6.5) slightly, albeit somewhat uncertainly, reduced growth.

Finally, in the case of complex global value chains, the two-way relationships already mentioned in foreign trade can also be observed. An increase in the concentration of final product industries ($HHI_FP_ind_cGVC\%$)—that is, product line specialisation—tends to promote growth, whereas an increase in concentration by final user country ($HHI_FU_cou_cGVC\%$) generally has a dampening effect on growth. However, the latter situation is somewhat more complicated, as this HH index interacts with the size of the domestic market, producing a positive (or counteracting) effect. Consequently, the combined influence of the variables $\ln dom_mrkt$, $HHI_FU_cou_cGVC\%$, and $\ln dom_mrkt * HHI_FU_cou_cGVC\%$ determines the final effect. Accordingly, in small countries, an increase in final-user concentration can significantly suppress growth. However, as the size of the domestic market increases, this effect gradually diminishes, and in the largest countries it can even turn slightly positive.

Fig. 19 Determinants of value chain types' growth contributions.

Figure 19 summarises the explanatory variables identified during the regression analysis of the growth contribution of each value chain type.

6.5 Growth from final product value chains

In Subsection 6.5, we further break down the types of value chains. Within the four main groups (*pudo*, *trtr*, *sGVC*, and *cGVC*), we also distinguish value chains by the type of final product produced, or, more precisely, by the industry (*FP_Industry*) that produces it.⁹ In this sense, automotive value chains are those at the end of which an automotive final product is produced, while electronic value chains are those in which the final product is produced by the electronics industry. Intermediate or semi-finished products, of course, can originate from any industry. A chip manufacturing company operating in the electronics industry, whose products are incorporated (directly or indirectly) into cars and computers in some country worldwide, participates to some extent in both final product value chains. In pure domestic and traditional foreign trade value chains, the production of final products and the source of value added are in the same country, whereas in global value chains, they may differ. In simple global value chains, they definitely differ, but in complex value chains, it is also possible that, after several production phases carried out in different countries, the final product is ultimately produced in the source country of value added.

Figure 20 shows the value chains of the most significant final products in domestic, foreign trade, and global breakdowns from the perspective of the entire national growth. This figure is also based on the average growth contributions from the period 2001-2014. We examined how much each final product value chain played a decisive role in the growth of individual countries. A dominant final product value chain was defined as the one that contributed most to growth within that value chain type in a given country, as well as overall. For example, the very first row of the figure indicates that pure domestic construction value chains—thanks to the significant volume and multiplier effects of the sector (Koppány, 2017c)—proved to be a dominant growth factor in 12 countries (including Australia, Belgium, Bulgaria, etc.) with an average contribution of 0.7%. In total, we identified 10 such dominant internal value chains across the 44 countries in the WIOD (besides construction, sectors such as wholesale and retail

⁹ The final product industry concentration of growth was examined in the previous subsection and used as an explanatory variable in the regression analysis.

trade, transportation, accommodation and catering, real estate transactions, public services, education, and healthcare are also shown in the upper part of Figure 20).

The number of dominant foreign trade value chains is higher than the domestic ones (14). The food industry, wholesale trade, automotive industry, chemical industry, and electronics industry were the most influential in this regard in most countries. However, the number of dominant global end-product value chains is significantly smaller.

Fig. 20 Dominant final product value chains between 2001 and 2014.

The construction industry plays a prominent role in both simple and complex global value chains, especially in simple ones. Although the average growth contribution of simple construction global value chains was only 0.1%, significantly lower than the 0.7% average growth of pure domestic construction value chains, participation in these chains accounted for the largest growth contribution in this category across 32 countries.¹⁰ In simple global value chains, the healthcare and social care sector ranked second, and in complex ones, the automotive industry ranked second.¹¹ In the latter, it provided the highest growth contribution in 16 countries. The arithmetic mean of these was 0.1%. The third place is occupied by the complex global value chains of electronic end-products, which were dominant in China, Japan, Korea, and Taiwan, with an average contribution of 0.2%.

It is evident that the growth contributions generated by dominant global value chains fall short of those from foreign trade, and even more so from purely domestic value chains. However, significant differences still exist between individual countries. To illustrate this, we selected the automotive value chains, which in three countries—Czechia, Hungary, and Slovakia—considering all four types of value chains (i.e., overall), contributed the most to economic growth. Panel A on the left side of Figure 21 clearly shows that the value added by these chains in the three aforementioned countries is negligible compared to the size of major automotive hubs. At the same time, it is also visible how much these chains have grown. Of course, it is important to note that Panel A shows changes from 2000 to 2014 in nominal dollars, which were significantly influenced by price and exchange rate changes. The real growth in terms of purchasing power is much lower due to the strengthening of local currencies against the dollar. (This is also true for Germany, which is considered a central hub to which these countries are connected.)

¹⁰ Beyond the aforementioned multiplicative effects, there are other reasons which can be found in the characteristics of the sector's products. A building (residential, office building, etc.) or a structure (road, bridge, etc.) can only be finally utilised in the country where it is produced as a finished product. The construction industry's value chain exists solely domestically or globally; there is no foreign trade when the final product crosses the border. Neither a building nor a structure can be produced in one country and then transported as a finished product to another. The zero growth contribution of foreign trade construction value chains simply stems from the fact that such value chains do not exist. The loss of growth due to this absence is compensated by higher contributions in simple construction GVCs. If a construction company imports raw materials, components, and services to produce its final output for use in the same country, this represents growth for exporting countries, facilitated by simple global value chains. If the final product is more complex and produced within an international division of labour involving multiple countries (e.g., Country A produces plastic granulate, which Country B uses to make windows and doors, which are then installed in a building constructed in Country C), this is considered a complex global value chain. Moreover, many sectors (mining and quarrying, manufacturing of chemicals and chemical products, rubber and plastic products, non-metallic mineral products, basic metals, fabricated metal products, electrical equipment, machinery and equipment, repair and installation of machinery and equipment, electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply, trade, transport, warehousing, financial services, insurance, legal and accounting activities, management consultancy activities, architectural and engineering activities; technical testing and analysis, administrative and support service activities, etc.) produce goods and services that are directly or indirectly incorporated into construction final products. Therefore, the multiplier effects of construction activities are significant. Not to mention that the volume of construction final products, the value of household, business and government orders, i.e., the final demand, are usually enormous. Coupled with these substantial multiplier effects, this results in a truly significant growth factor.

¹¹ The value chains of healthcare and social care (Q) are very similar to those of the construction industry (F). In the case of the end-product value chains of the Q sector, there is no foreign trade either. Compared to the automotive industry (C29), where the global average contributions to growth are *pudo%* 0.02%, *trtr%* 0.04%, *sGVC%* 0.02%, and *cGVC%* 0.05%; in the construction industry (F), these figures are respectively 0.18%, 0.00%, 0.10%, and 0.05%; and in healthcare and social care (Q), they are 0.15%, 0.00%, 0.04%, and 0.02%. It is clear that in the latter two sectors, domestic value chains dominate, and there is no foreign trade.

The weight of the automotive value chains in the economy's value-added generation has nevertheless increased significantly: in the Czech Republic and Hungary by 1.36 times, and in Slovakia by 1.67 times. This is, of course, due to the growth of the automotive industry and other sectors that supply the automotive value chain. The average annual growth contribution of participation in automotive value chains was highest in Slovakia (0.65%), slightly lower in the Czech Republic (0.55%), while in Hungary it was less than half of Slovakia's (0.31%) (see Panel B of Figure 21). These can be attributed to foreign trade and global value chains in roughly equal proportions. Domestic automotive value chains contributed negatively to growth, and their weight and role decreased in all three countries. The most dramatic decline occurred in Hungary, where even the nominal value decreased significantly.

Panel A: GVA from automotive final products value chains

Panel B: Growth contributions by value chain type

Panel C: Contributions by automotive industry and spillovers

Fig. 21 Size (panel A) and growth contributions (panels B and C) of automotive final product value chains, 2000-2014.

Notes: (a) the area of the bubbles in panel A corresponds to the nominal GVA generated by the automotive final product value chains; (b) panels B and C shows the average growth contributions between 2001 and 2014.

Using the GVC-GCD database, it is also possible to examine the growth effects of participation in automotive value chains on sectors outside the automotive industry. These results are shown in Panel C of Figure 21, where it is clear that the outstanding performance of Slovakia can also be explained by the fact that the effects in other (mainly manufacturing) industries (manufacture of rubber and plastic (C22), basic metals (C24), fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment (C25), electrical equipment (C27)) is the largest here. More than half of Slovakia's growth contribution from participation in automotive value chains did not originate within the Slovakian automotive industry. The growth contribution within the automotive sector does not even reach the level of the Czech Republic; however, when combined with

effects in other sectors, Slovakia is leading. This is true despite the fact that the value-added ratio was the lowest in the Slovakian automotive sector (17-18% on average between 2000 and 2014), lagging significantly behind the Czech and Hungarian levels (24-25%). However, the volume of output increased year after year to such an extent that the Slovak automotive industry's output value, which was only a quarter of Hungary's in 2000, caught up, and its value added reached 70% of Hungary's by 2014. A similar pace of catch-up, primarily volume-based (but in some cases also driven by higher-value-added content), was observed in other Slovak manufacturing sectors linked to the domestic and global automotive value chains. The growth effects of final product value chains in the automotive industry on other sectors were lowest in Hungary among the three countries, a finding that is also related to the fact that the large, foreign-owned automotive companies here were the least embedded in the local economy (Braun & Sebestyén, 2025; Koppány, 2017a).

In the larger economies shown in panels A, B, and C, growth rates driven by the automotive value chains were significantly lower than in the previous countries. Although their weight has decreased, they have not lost their important role in the global automotive industry. Participation in global value chains contributed positively to growth in each of the countries listed, more or less offsetting the negative effects of the retreat of domestic value chains (though one country did not achieve this).

Among the countries listed on panels A, B, and C, only Mexico experienced a positive contribution to the growth of domestic automotive value chains. This is partly due to the country's size and the local market for predominantly American-owned car manufacturers. The growth effects of domestic and cross-border automotive value chains are also significant in other countries not shown in the diagrams (e.g., China, India, Indonesia, Romania, Brazil, Korea, Poland, Turkey, Slovenia, Bulgaria), sometimes even surpassing those of the previously mentioned nations. However, these were not the most influential end-product value chains for the country's overall growth. Therefore, they were not included in this analysis.

6.6 Final use value chains and welfare gains

Following the pattern of Figure 17, we have also created a 'world map' of the average real final use growth between 2001 and 2014 (Figure 22). Our planet as a whole (for now) is a closed economy, so, at the global level, value added (GVA) and final use (FU) are, by definition, the same. Therefore, their growth and the contributions of different value chain types to this are also identical. However, at the country level, this is not necessarily the case. There are countries (e.g., India, Russia, Romania, Australia, Norway, Canada, Mexico, etc., a total of 15) where the FU, and also some (more than 29), where the average real growth of GVA was higher during the examined period. In cases where FU grew faster than GVA, this was most often due to income flowing out through international trade and global value chains for final consumption increasing faster than income received by the country through these channels. In other words, in these countries, global value chains played a larger role in increasing well-being than in economic growth.

In Figure 22, we have again grouped countries exhibiting similar levels and structures of welfare growth. Due to the differences discussed earlier, the members of these groups, and thus the order of the countries, differ somewhat from what is shown on the horizontal axis of Figure 17. The countries (a total of 19) enclosed within the black box are those where more than half of the observed welfare growth is attributable to foreign trade or global value chains. The average annual rate of global welfare growth was surpassed by 18 countries. Only 7 countries overlap between these two groups. Comparing these figures with those in Figure 17, it appears

that the role of foreign trade and GVCs in welfare growth is less significant than in economic growth.

Fig. 22 Average real FU growth and FU growth contributions by value chain type in WIOD countries between 2001 and 2014.

6.7 Growth benefits in the long run

Finally, let us examine the increases at the national level achieved in global value chains over a longer period than the previous ones. Our ability to do so is limited to the growth contributions calculated based on the Long-run WIOD. The historical database does not include a significant number of countries, and the sectoral classification used (ISIC Rev.3) is not the same as the later nomenclature used in the standard WIOD (ISIC Rev.4). With the help of translation keys and appropriate aggregations, the conditions for comparability can be established to some extent, but here we do not undertake sector-level analyses (not least for reasons of length). However, we have prepared a long-term analysis for the countries that appear in both the Long-run and the standard WIOD.

The period from 1966 to 2014 was divided into three subperiods of nearly equal length. The first covers the years from 1966 to 1985, the second from 1986 to 2000 (the Long-run WIOD time frame was therefore split into two parts), and the third corresponds to the standard WIOD. The first period is thus 20 years long, the second 15, and the third 14. The average annual growth rates of the countries included in both databases during these periods, along with the growth contributions of the four value chain types, are shown in Table 4.

In the middle and right sections of the table, the differences between the first and second, as well as the second and third periods, can be seen. Between the first and second periods, global growth decreased by 1.06%. The largest decline was in the contribution of domestic value chains to growth, which was only partially offset by a slight increase in foreign trade and the contribution of complex global value chains.

Table 4 Average real GVA growth and GVA growth contributions by value chain type in Long-run WIOD countries between 1966-1985, 1986-2000, and 2001-2014.

Country	Average yearly growth contributions					Country	Differences in the average growth contributions					Average yearly growth contributions					Country	Differences in the average growth contributions									
	1966-1985						1986-2000					2001-2014						between the periods 2001-2014 and 1986-2000									
	pudo%	trtr%	sGVC%	cGVC%	total%		pudo%	trtr%	sGVC%	cGVC%	total%	pudo%	trtr%	sGVC%	cGVC%	total%		pudo%	trtr%	sGVC%	cGVC%	total%					
AUS	4.08%	0.11%	0.13%	0.12%	4.43%	2.30%	0.27%	0.37%	0.20%	3.14%	AUS	-1.78%	0.15%	0.24%	0.08%	-1.30%	2.68%	0.00%	0.32%	0.19%	3.19%	AUS	0.88%	-0.27%	-0.05%	-0.01%	0.65%
AUT	1.40%	0.43%	1.23%	0.30%	3.36%	1.45%	0.58%	0.57%	0.45%	3.04%	AUT	0.05%	0.15%	-0.06%	0.14%	-0.31%	0.41%	0.37%	0.26%	0.40%	1.45%	AUT	-1.04%	-0.20%	-0.30%	-0.05%	-1.59%
BEL	1.12%	0.45%	0.94%	0.48%	2.99%	0.62%	0.55%	0.62%	0.55%	2.34%	BEL	-0.50%	0.09%	-0.32%	0.08%	-0.66%	0.47%	0.30%	0.35%	0.33%	1.45%	BEL	-0.15%	-0.25%	-0.26%	-0.22%	-0.88%
BRA	6.50%	0.25%	0.35%	0.09%	7.18%	1.51%	0.10%	-0.02%	0.05%	1.65%	BRA	-4.98%	-0.15%	-0.36%	-0.03%	-5.53%	2.54%	0.15%	0.28%	0.14%	3.10%	BRA	1.83%	0.05%	0.30%	0.08%	1.45%
CAN	2.99%	0.48%	0.45%	0.09%	4.01%	1.19%	0.59%	0.69%	0.22%	2.69%	CAN	-1.80%	0.11%	0.24%	0.12%	-1.33%	1.73%	0.00%	0.18%	0.12%	2.02%	CAN	0.84%	-0.59%	-0.51%	-0.10%	-0.66%
CHN	2.51%	1.56%	2.19%	0.54%	6.80%	4.00%	2.96%	1.70%	0.66%	9.33%	CHN	1.48%	1.48%	-0.49%	0.12%	2.52%	7.45%	1.82%	0.85%	0.60%	10.72%	CHN	3.45%	-1.15%	-0.85%	-0.06%	1.39%
DEU	1.69%	0.50%	0.44%	0.22%	2.86%	1.34%	0.36%	0.28%	0.27%	2.25%	DEU	-0.35%	-0.15%	-0.16%	0.04%	-0.61%	0.06%	0.48%	0.31%	0.33%	1.19%	DEU	-1.28%	0.12%	0.03%	0.07%	-1.06%
DNK	1.56%	0.54%	0.46%	0.16%	2.72%	0.82%	0.58%	0.56%	0.34%	2.30%	DNK	-0.74%	0.04%	0.10%	0.18%	-0.42%	0.31%	0.14%	0.14%	0.09%	0.68%	DNK	-0.52%	-0.44%	-0.41%	-0.25%	-1.63%
ESP	2.99%	0.39%	0.48%	0.14%	4.00%	2.00%	0.54%	0.35%	0.25%	3.14%	ESP	-1.00%	0.15%	-0.18%	0.11%	-0.86%	0.87%	0.28%	0.11%	0.14%	1.40%	ESP	-1.22%	-0.26%	-0.24%	-0.11%	-1.74%
FIN	2.05%	0.63%	0.96%	0.33%	3.96%	0.77%	0.62%	0.66%	0.52%	2.58%	FIN	-1.28%	0.00%	-0.30%	0.20%	-1.39%	0.63%	0.10%	0.13%	0.20%	1.05%	FIN	-0.14%	-0.52%	-0.53%	-0.33%	-1.52%
FRA	2.37%	0.57%	0.60%	0.19%	3.72%	1.68%	0.48%	0.27%	0.23%	2.65%	FRA	-0.69%	-0.09%	-0.33%	0.04%	-1.07%	0.78%	0.13%	0.10%	0.14%	1.15%	FRA	-0.90%	-0.34%	-0.17%	-0.09%	-1.50%
GBR	1.65%	0.20%	0.20%	0.13%	2.18%	2.21%	0.45%	0.23%	0.24%	3.13%	GBR	0.56%	0.25%	0.04%	0.11%	0.95%	1.46%	0.15%	0.19%	0.18%	1.99%	GBR	-0.75%	-0.29%	-0.04%	-0.06%	-1.14%
GRC	1.26%	0.80%	1.38%	0.33%	3.78%	-0.30%	0.45%	0.58%	0.24%	0.96%	GRC	-1.56%	-0.36%	-0.80%	-0.10%	-2.82%	-0.47%	0.16%	0.16%	0.10%	-0.06%	GRC	-0.17%	-0.29%	-0.42%	-0.13%	-1.02%
HKG	0.22%	3.49%	3.06%	0.52%	7.28%	0.49%	1.30%	2.94%	0.94%	5.68%	HKG	0.27%	-2.19%	-0.12%	0.43%	-1.60%						HKG					
IND	2.09%	0.81%	1.01%	0.18%	4.09%	3.65%	0.83%	0.85%	0.27%	5.60%	IND	1.58%	0.02%	-0.15%	0.09%	1.52%	5.98%	0.51%	0.41%	0.23%	7.13%	IND	2.83%	-0.31%	-0.44%	-0.05%	1.93%
IRL	2.10%	1.32%	0.94%	0.32%	4.67%	1.19%	2.29%	1.91%	1.02%	6.41%	IRL	-0.91%	0.97%	0.93%	0.70%	1.74%	0.87%	0.64%	0.74%	0.40%	2.65%	IRL	-0.32%	-1.55%	-1.17%	-0.52%	-3.76%
ITA	3.09%	0.38%	0.24%	0.10%	3.81%	1.09%	0.38%	0.24%	0.21%	1.93%	ITA	-1.99%	0.00%	0.00%	0.11%	-1.88%	-0.30%	0.11%	0.05%	0.12%	-0.02%	ITA	-1.40%	-0.27%	-0.19%	-0.09%	-1.95%
JPN	5.16%	0.71%	0.40%	0.11%	6.38%	2.18%	0.10%	0.09%	0.10%	2.47%	JPN	-2.98%	-0.61%	-0.31%	-0.01%	-3.91%	0.10%	0.11%	0.08%	0.09%	0.39%	JPN	-2.08%	0.01%	0.00%	-0.01%	-2.08%
KOR	5.68%	1.73%	1.22%	0.26%	8.89%	4.44%	1.54%	1.31%	0.60%	7.89%	KOR	-1.23%	-0.19%	0.09%	0.34%	-1.01%	1.96%	0.83%	0.58%	0.51%	3.89%	KOR	-2.48%	-0.71%	-0.72%	-0.09%	-4.00%
MEX	3.98%	0.42%	0.89%	0.16%	5.45%	0.38%	0.80%	0.77%	0.21%	2.17%	MEX	-3.60%	0.38%	-0.11%	0.05%	-3.28%	1.72%	0.14%	0.14%	0.07%	2.06%	MEX	1.34%	-0.57%	-0.54%	-0.14%	-0.11%
NLD	2.15%	0.35%	0.61%	0.42%	3.52%	1.09%	0.89%	0.57%	0.53%	3.08%	NLD	-1.06%	0.54%	-0.04%	0.12%	-0.44%	-0.03%	0.20%	0.48%	0.55%	1.21%	NLD	-1.22%	-0.59%	-0.09%	0.02%	-1.88%
PRT	3.30%	0.36%	0.39%	0.13%	4.17%	2.19%	0.62%	0.35%	0.25%	3.41%	PRT	-1.11%	0.26%	-0.04%	0.13%	-0.76%	-0.59%	0.25%	0.38%	0.26%	0.29%	PRT	-2.77%	-0.38%	0.03%	0.01%	-3.12%
SWE	0.82%	0.63%	1.00%	0.33%	2.79%	0.52%	0.63%	0.51%	0.48%	2.14%	SWE	-0.30%	0.09%	-0.49%	0.15%	-0.64%	1.01%	0.30%	0.30%	0.32%	1.94%	SWE	0.49%	-0.33%	-0.21%	-0.16%	-0.21%
TWN	5.45%	2.54%	1.75%	0.51%	10.25%	4.83%	1.01%	1.48%	0.66%	7.98%	TWN	-0.62%	-1.53%	-0.23%	0.16%	-2.26%	1.10%	0.45%	1.18%	1.15%	3.89%	TWN	-3.73%	-0.56%	-0.30%	0.49%	-4.10%
USA	3.07%	0.07%	0.09%	0.05%	3.28%	2.97%	0.16%	0.13%	0.14%	3.40%	USA	-0.10%	0.09%	0.04%	0.09%	0.12%	1.43%	0.05%	0.07%	0.06%	1.62%	USA	-1.54%	-0.11%	-0.06%	-0.08%	-1.79%
ROW	6.44%	0.20%	0.15%	0.10%	6.90%	3.63%	0.37%	0.32%	0.24%	4.55%	ROW	-2.81%	0.17%	0.16%	0.13%	-2.35%	2.81%	0.25%	0.33%	0.42%	3.80%	ROW	-0.82%	-0.13%	0.01%	0.19%	-0.75%
TOT	3.61%	0.34%	0.33%	0.13%	4.41%	2.45%	0.38%	0.30%	0.22%	3.35%	TOT	-1.16%	0.04%	-0.03%	0.09%	-1.06%	1.87%	0.28%	0.24%	0.22%	2.61%	TOT	-0.58%	-0.10%	-0.06%	0.01%	-0.74%

The situation mirrors that in most countries: domestic growth declined, and foreign trade compensated to some extent. Only five countries experienced an increase in the average growth rate. Of these, three (China, the United Kingdom, and India) saw this happen alongside an acceleration in domestic growth, with international trade further amplifying this. Only two countries (Ireland and the USA) managed to fully offset the slowdown in domestic growth through external channels, resulting in an overall increase.

In the third period (by comparison with the second), however, we find no such country. The pace of global economic growth continues to slow (decreasing by 0.74%). Not only does the contribution of domestic trade decline, but also that of foreign trade and simple global value chains. Only the contribution of complex value chains increases marginally. There are four countries where growth rates have increased: Australia, Brazil, China, and India. The primary source of this in each case is the growing contribution of domestic value chains. In Australia, China, and India, this is paired with a declining contribution to growth from international value chains. Only in Brazil does the contribution of all types of value chains increase. No country was able to offset the slowdown in domestic growth channels through international trade and global value chains during the period from 2001 to 2014.

7 Discussion

The main conclusions from the analyses presented in the previous section are summarised in the following points. Some of these confirm earlier findings in the literature, while others may contradict them and prompt a rethinking of conventional globalisation narratives. Hopefully, all of them add to the current debate on growth and GVCs.

- GVCs have been present in the global economy for a long time; their presence, based on the Long-run WIOD, can already be detected from the mid-1960s.
- The role of international final product trade and global value chains in value-added generation has gradually doubled over nearly 50 years, from 1966 to 2014, but even in the mid-2010s, domestic value chains accounted for 80% of the value added in the global economy.
- At a global level, domestic value chains also represented the main source of growth, although their contribution gradually decreased over the long term. The trend in growth contributions from other value chains remained roughly constant.
- The growth rate of global value added generated in complex value chains was, throughout the entire analysed period, the highest among the four types of value chains. Moreover, in the initial decades, it was even higher than in the 1990s and 2000s.
- The growth of domestic value chains has always been the lowest, due to their diminishing role in value-added production and their decreasing contribution to growth.
- The growth rate of value-added production for the four types of value chains has decreased in the long run.
- Global growth and its value chain structure are primarily determined by the results of the largest economies. Behind the unified global trends, however, a quite diverse picture emerges at the country level, which can sometimes be markedly different from the global norm, especially in the short term. The complex relationships between growth and value chains can be fully understood only if countries are chosen as the units of analysis, enabling comparative studies.

- The aforementioned diversity was further enhanced by the fact that from the 1990s onwards, an increasing number of smaller and larger less developed countries were able to connect to global value chains. Based on the average data from 2001 to 2014, for most of the countries listed in WIOD, growth was more influenced by foreign trade and global value chains than by purely domestic factors. Among them, 10 countries grew faster than the global economy.
- Between centrum and periphery economies, there's an asymmetry in growth dependencies: centrum contributes more to periphery than vice versa.
- The econometric analysis of the growth contributions of different value chain types showed that a lower level of development generally resulted in greater growth, and a smaller domestic market prompted a greater reliance on external value chains, thereby increasing their contribution to growth. However, the initial level of development of the countries did not influence the growth contributions of complex global value chains. Both developed and less developed economies could achieve modest or even outstanding levels of growth through their complex global value chains.
- In certain aspects and to some extent, concentration influenced the rate of growth in almost all types of value chains. On the one hand, the advantages of specialisation became apparent, while on the other, the risks and growth disadvantages stemming from low-level diversification also emerged.
- The production of final products in global value chains has occurred in relatively few sectors. In most countries, the construction, automotive, healthcare, and electronics value chains played the most significant role in their growth between 2001 and 2014.
- International trade and global value chains contributed less to the growth of welfare (final consumption) than to the increase in income (value added).
- Despite short-term successes, maintaining the higher growth rates of previous decades over the long run through participation in global value chains was not guaranteed. Among the countries listed in the Long-run WIOD, we did not find any that, during the period from 2001 to 2014, could offset the decline in their domestic value chain contributions through international trade and global value chains.

8 Limitations and further research

Like every analysis, the one presented here also has numerous limitations. Some of these stem from the data, while others arise from the applied modelling framework. In fact, we have already touched upon all of them earlier in some part of the study. Here, we will briefly summarise these.

The limitations regarding the data stem from the temporal and regional coverage, as well as the sectoral breakdown, of the WIOD and the Long-run WIOD time series. As a result, our analyses could not extend beyond 2014. There are also global input-output databases available that include more countries and sectors, as well as later years than those found in WIOD. However, none of these currently contain tables calculated at the previous year's prices. To date, only the WIOD is suitable for examining real growth and global value chains. When applying the WIOD and the Long-run WIOD, additional limitations arise because the two databases are not perfectly comparable. The number of countries and sectors considered in the Long-run WIOD is significantly lower, and the sectoral classification systems used differ.

It is important to emphasise once again that during the study (as in most input-output or other sectoral analyses), economic performance is not measured using market-price (headline) GDP,

the most common indicator in official statistics, but rather with the basic-price GDP, or GVA (Gross Value Added). The sectoral performance levels and the impacts of inter-sectoral relationships are better and more easily captured using this measure, since the majority of product taxes and subsidies included in GDP are not allocated to sectors in the input-output tables.

According to the methodology presented in Sections 3-5, the technical limitations of the GVC-GCD database are discussed in detail in those same sections. Particular attention must be paid to the additivity rules. The growth contribution data can only be aggregated at the national level; for global analyses, the technical country marked with the TOT code (which represents the entire world) should be used. However, within individual countries, various aggregations and disaggregations based on different aspects and variables can be applied.

Of course, it is possible to further deepen these investigations by more detailed structural decompositions (SDA) widely used in input-output analysis (Oosterhaven, 2024). For example, we can distinguish the growth effects arising from changes in the level and structure of final demand, as well as from the intermediate-use and value-added coefficients (Koppány, 2017b). However, the most important research direction is the application of the method to more recent, more detailed global input-output databases that include previous year's price data; thereby updating the GVC-GCD and extending it over time, regions, industries, and sectors.

Finally, there is one more topic that might leave the reader feeling that information is missing. The literature review mentioned backward linkages and import-led economic growth. Why does our decomposition model not address this?¹² In an IO framework, the appearance of primary inputs and the generation of their income (i.e., the value added) is the starting point of a value chain. The endpoints are the use of final products. Equations in Section 3 roll up the entire value-creation process from the end of the chain (i.e., from the final products). Iterative calculations stop when the original value-added sources are reached. This is a full backward investigation of the output side of each related value-added source industry. The process is logical and reasonable from the perspective of GVA and its output-side growth accounting. In this way, value added can only be decomposed based on the output, not the input side.¹³ Your value added is included only in what you sell, not in what you buy. You can only detect and decompose your GVA and GVA-growth downstream, based on your direct and indirect buyers and your output-side selling activities.

Of course, one can also break down intermediate inputs by value chain type (*pudo*, *sGVC*, and *cGVC*; note that there is no *trtr* in this case). (Presenting this would require a separate study.) However, this structure of intermediate use, based on the aggregate IO data, could only be arbitrarily projected onto value added. There is no clear and natural part-whole relationship between the *pudo*-, *sGVC*-, and *cGVC*-type inputs and the value added.¹⁴ The intermediate input structure is, of course, still closely related to the added value, which can and should be analysed theoretically and statistically using production functions. In contrast, output-side decomposition of GVA and growth depicts a true part-whole relationship based solely on the IO model.

¹² At the same time, backward linkages and import-led growth are fully exposed in final use growth contributions.

¹³ This approach is different from traditional input-side growth and productivity accounting (M. P. Timmer & Ye, 2020).

¹⁴ Studies examining the relationship between growth and import-side participation in GVCs, therefore, do not break down the value added and its percentage change by value chain types.

9 Summary, conclusions, and policy implications

This paper presented a novel method for global value chain (GVC) analysis. Unlike earlier static frameworks that decompose levels of related nominal variables (such as gross exports or value added), our model adopts a dynamic approach, providing a year-by-year breakdown of economic growth. Its headline indicator, percentage change in real GDP is, of course, not the only, and moreover, far from the most perfect measure of economic development. Despite its numerous shortcomings, it remains one of the most frequently cited macroeconomic indicators to this day.

In this study, we broke down the volume indices of basic-price GDP (gross value added, GVA) by value chain and the contributions of the actors (countries and sectors) within each. The paper's novelty lies not only in analysing real growth through the lens of value chains but also in bringing the GVC phenomenon closer to the headline growth indicator. Decompositions include contributions from value-added sources, final producers and users, and various types of value chains: pure domestic, traditional foreign trade, and both simple and complex global value chains. The analysis of real growth in final use adopts a similar approach. Growth contributions offer a new perspective on GVC research, with particular attention to the literature on the relationship between economic growth, welfare, and value chains, as presented in Section 2.

The decomposition methods applied in this study are based on input-output theory. Mathematical background presented in Section 3 and an illustrative numerical example in Section 4 demonstrate the calculation process, the structure and application of the resulting matrices, and how to interpret the figures. By applying this framework to the World Input-Output Database (WIOD) and its historical extension, the Long-run WIOD, an original GVC Growth Contribution Database (GVC-GCD) has been created and is published alongside the paper (Section 5).

Initial analyses in Section 6 offer insights into its various applications for mapping value chain growth. Although they cannot aim for a comprehensive, full-depth investigation within a single paper, these partial studies can provide new perspectives on existing ideas in the literature on GVCs and growth, or yield novel insights into the phenomenon—sometimes confirming previous findings, at other times generating debate and incentives to rethink conventional narratives (Section 7). The results suggest that GVCs have a longer history than the possibilities of their quantitative analysis. They existed even before the term itself was coined, and their influence on growth over time follows a relatively stable long-term trend. Nonetheless, significant differences exist across short periods, at global and national levels, among large and small economies, and between developed and developing countries. Specialisation and diversification also play a crucial role. With few exceptions, the pace of growth and the contribution of different types of value chains—even those of global ones—have declined over time. Although participation in international trade and global value chains has brought benefits to many countries, none of the Long-run WIOD economies could permanently offset the decline in the growth contributions of their domestic value chains.

In an objective analysis, we generally have both positive and negative conclusions. Even the latter, however, do not in any way intend to deny the benefits associated with globalisation, global value chains, and the interconnectedness of the world's countries, which we have already experienced. Without these, we would undoubtedly be much poorer. At the same time, we must recognise that these benefits are neither automatic nor eternal. With some realism, we can probably state that global value chains are not a panacea that can be used without preconditions,

risks, or side effects, and that their conditional positive impacts on growth do not last forever. This can serve as a useful lesson for current affairs.

To go beyond the historical approach and preliminary investigations, the growth contribution database (GVC-GCD) provides valuable inputs for further empirical analyses and growth modelling, whether in academic or policy contexts. Overcoming the current limitations (described in Section 8), once the previous year's price tables become widely available in world input-output databases and cover later periods as well, value chain growth decompositions can then—using the methodology presented here, or any developed variants—be recalculated, allowing the GVC-GCD to be extended in terms of space, time, and level of detail. These developments also provide a better understanding of the relationship between growth and value chains, which, in turn, allows the conclusions drawn from the initial analyses using the first version to be verified or, if necessary, revised.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by the National Research, Development and Innovation (NRDI) Office project number 150782.

References

- Afonso, O. (2001). *The Impact of International Trade on Economic Growth* (FEP Working Papers) [Working paper]. Universidade do Porto, Faculdade de Economia do Porto. <https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:por:fepwps:106>
- Aguiar, A., Chepeliev, M., Corong, E. L., McDougall, R., & Mensbrugghe, D. van der. (2019). The GTAP Data Base: Version 10. *Journal of Global Economic Analysis*, 4(1), 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.21642/JGEA.040101AF>
- Ahmad, F., Draz, M. U., & Yang, S.-C. (2018). Causality nexus of exports, FDI and economic growth of the ASEAN5 economies: Evidence from panel data analysis. *The Journal of International Trade & Economic Development*, 27(6), 685–700. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638199.2018.1426035>
- Alves-Passoni, P., & Neria, A. B. (2023). Determinants of Growth in Mexico and Brazil Between 2003 and 2018: A Demand-led Decomposition of Growth Using Input-output Tables. *Review of Political Economy*, 35(3), 670–686. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09538259.2022.2150437>
- Andersen, S. S., Nellemann, P. B., & Thomsen, C. R. (2015). *Global Value Chains* (No. 102). Danmarks Nationalbank.
- Antràs, P. (2019). *Conceptual Aspects of Global Value Chains* (No. W26539; p. w26539). National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w26539>
- Antràs, P., & Gortari, A. (2020). On the Geography of Global Value Chains. *Econometrica*, 88(4), 1553–1598. <https://doi.org/10.3982/ECTA15362>
- Arkolakis, C., Costinot, A., & Rodríguez-Clare, A. (2009). *New Trade Models, Same Old Gains?* (No. W15628; p. w15628). National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w15628>
- Awokuse, T. O. (2007). Causality between exports, imports, and economic growth: Evidence from transition economies. *Economics Letters*, 94(3), 389–395. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econlet.2006.08.025>
- Backer, K. D., & Miroudot, S. (2013). Mapping Global Value Chains. *OECD Trade Policy Papers*, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5k3v1trgnbr4-en>
- Balassa, B. (1978). Exports and economic growth: Further evidence. *Journal of Development Economics*, 5(2), 181–189. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3878\(78\)90006-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3878(78)90006-8)
- Baldwin, R., & Freeman, R. (2022). Risks and Global Supply Chains: What We Know and What We Need to Know. *Annual Review of Economics*, 14(Volume 14, 2022), 153–180. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-economics-051420-113737>
- Baldwin, R., Freeman, R., & Theodorakopoulos, A. (2022). *Horses for Courses: Measuring Foreign Supply Chain Exposure* (Working Paper No. 30525). National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w30525>
- Baldwin, R., Freeman, R., & Theodorakopoulos, A. (2023). *Hidden Exposure: Measuring US Supply Chain Reliance* (Working Paper No. 31820). National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w31820>
- Barnes, J. A. (1966). Durkheim's Division of Labour in Society. *Man*, 1(2), 158–175. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2796343>

- Barro, R. J. (1992). Convergence. *Journal of Political Economy*, 100(2), 223–251. <https://doi.org/10.1086/261816>
- Basco, S., & Mestieri, M. (2019). The world income distribution: The effects of international unbundling of production. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 24(2), 189–221. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10887-019-09164-4>
- Benkovskis, K., Masso, J., Tkacevs, O., Vahter, P., & Yashiro, N. (2020). Export and productivity in global value chains: Comparative evidence from Latvia and Estonia. *Review of World Economics*, 156(3), 557–577. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10290-019-00371-0>
- Berg, A., Ostry, J. D., Tsangarides, C. G., & Yakhshilikov, Y. (2018). Redistribution, inequality, and growth: New evidence. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 23(3), 259–305. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10887-017-9150-2>
- Bernon, B., Magerman, G., & Palazzolo, A. (2025). *Belgian Regions in Local and Global Value Chains*. ECARES. https://static1.squarespace.com/static/55e85d72e4b0146280523def/t/68b85c985615d960f8d25a54/1756912792034/WIOT_MRIO_Belgium.pdf
- Berrill, K. (1960). International Trade and the Rate of Economic Growth. *The Economic History Review*, 12(3), 351–359. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2590883>
- Bhagwati, J. (1958). Immiserizing Growth: A Geometrical Note. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 25(3), 201–205. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2295990>
- Borin, A., & Mancini, M. (2023). Measuring what matters in value-added trade. *Economic Systems Research*, 35(4), 586–613. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09535314.2022.2153221>
- Braun E., & Sebestyén T. (2025). Szerkezeti változások és függőségek – Magyarország helyzete a globális értékláncokban. *Közgazdasági Szemle*, 72(9–10), 805–841. <https://doi.org/10.18414/KSZ.2025.9-10.805>
- Cazcarro, I., Usubiaga-Liaño, A., Román, M. V., Piñero, P., Dietzenbacher, E., Rueda-Cantuche, J. M., & Arto, I. (2025). FIGARO-E3: A high-resolution extended multi-regional input-output database consistent with official statistics. *Scientific Data*, 12(1), 575. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-025-04431-z>
- Cervellati, M., Meyerheim, G., & Sunde, U. (2023). The empirics of economic growth over time and across nations: A unified growth perspective. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 28(2), 173–224. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10887-022-09216-2>
- Ciešlik, E., Biegańska, J., & Środa-Murawska, S. (2021). Central and Eastern European States from an International Perspective: Economic Potential and Paths of Participation in Global Value Chains. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 57(13), 3587–3603. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1540496X.2019.1602519>
- Constantinescu, C., Mattoo, A., & Ruta, M. (2019). Does vertical specialisation increase productivity? *The World Economy*, 42(8), 2385–2402. <https://doi.org/10.1111/twec.12801>
- Crafts, N. F. R. (1995). The Golden Age of Economic Growth in Western Europe, 1950–1973. *The Economic History Review*, 48(3), 429–447. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2598175>
- De Gregorio, J., Giovannini, A., & Krueger, T. H. (1994). The Behavior of Nontradable-Goods Prices In Europe: Evidence and Interpretation*. *Review of International Economics*, 2(3), 284–305. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9396.1994.tb00045.x>
- De Groot, H. L. F., Linders, G.-J., Rietveld, P., & Subramanian, U. (2004). The Institutional Determinants of Bilateral Trade Patterns. *Kyklos*, 57(1), 103–123. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0023-5962.2004.00245.x>
- Degain, C., Meng, B., & Wang, Z. (2017). Recent trends in global trade and global value chains. In World Bank, OECD, & IBRD, *Global value chain development report 2017: Measuring and analyzing the impact of GVCs on economic development*. World Bank.
- Dietzenbacher, E., Los, B., Stehrer, R., Timmer, M., & de Vries, G. (2013). The Construction of World Input–Output Tables in the Wiod Project. *Economic Systems Research*, 25(1), 71–98. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09535314.2012.761180>
- Dodaro, S. (1991). Comparative advantage, trade and growth: Export-Led growth revisited. *World Development*, 19(9), 1153–1165. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-750X\(91\)90064-O](https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-750X(91)90064-O)
- Dollar, D., & Kraay, A. (2003). Institutions, trade, and growth. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 50(1), 133–162. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3932\(02\)00206-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3932(02)00206-4)
- Domingues, T., Amaral, J. F. do, & Lopes, J. C. (2021). Global value chains, value-added generation and structural change in EU core and periphery economies: An Input-Output approach. *Working Papers REM, Working Papers REM*, Article 2021/0157. <https://ideas.repec.org/p/ise/remwps/wp01572021.html>
- Eaton, J., & Kortum, S. (2002). Technology, Geography, and Trade. *Econometrica*, 70(5), 1741–1779. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0262.00352>
- Eppinger, P., Felbermayr, G. J., Krebs, O., & Kukharsky, B. (2021). *Decoupling Global Value Chains* (SSRN Scholarly Paper No. 3848341). Social Science Research Network. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3848341>

- Fagerberg, J., Lundvall, B.-Å., & Srholec, M. (2018). Global Value Chains, National Innovation Systems and Economic Development. *The European Journal of Development Research*, 30(3), 533–556. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41287-018-0147-2>
- Fally, T. (2012). *Production Staging: Measurement and Facts*.
- Feder, G. (1983). On exports and economic growth. *Journal of Development Economics*, 12(1–2), 59–73. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3878\(83\)90031-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3878(83)90031-7)
- Findlay, R. (1980). The Terms of Trade and Equilibrium Growth in the World Economy. *The American Economic Review*, 70(3), 291–299.
- Foster-McGregor, N., & Verspagen, B. (2016). The Role of Structural Change in the Economic Development of Asian Economies. *Asian Development Review*, 33(2), 74–93. https://doi.org/10.1162/ADEV_a_00073
- Frankel, J., & Romer, D. (1999). Does Trade Causes Growth? *American Economic Review*, 89, 379–399. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.89.3.379>
- Frederick, S. (2019). Global value chain mapping. In *Handbook on Global Value Chains* (pp. 29–53). Edward Elgar Publishing. <https://www.elgaronline.com/edcollchap/edcoll/9781788113762/9781788113762.00007.xml>
- Gabisch, G. (1975). A vintage capital model of international trade: The case of trade with second-hand machines. *Journal of International Economics*, 5(4), 365–383. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1996\(75\)90038-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1996(75)90038-0)
- Galor, O. (1996). Convergence? Inferences from Theoretical Models. *The Economic Journal*, 106(437), 1056–1069. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2235378>
- Gáspár T. (2020). Az ágazati kapcsolatok mérlegének új perspektívái a nemzetközi gazdaság kutatói számára. *Statistikai Szemle*, 98(5), 373–399. <https://doi.org/10.20311/stat2020.5.hu0373>
- Gáspár T., & Koppány K. (2020). A globális értékláncok mérése nemzetközi ÁKM-ek alapján. *Statistikai Szemle*, 98(9), 1035–1065. <https://doi.org/10.20311/stat2020.9.hu1035>
- Gereffi, G. (1994). *The Organization of Buyer-Driven Global Commodity Chains: How U.S. Retailers Shape Overseas Production Networks* (pp. 95–122).
- Gereffi, G. (2014). Global value chains in a post-Washington Consensus world. *Review of International Political Economy*, 21(1), 9–37. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09692290.2012.756414>
- Gereffi, G., Humphrey, J., & Sturgeon, T. (2005). The governance of global value chains. *Review of International Political Economy*, 12(1), 78–104. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09692290500049805>
- Gereffi, G., & Fernandez Jara, K. (2010). The offshore services value chain: Developing countries and the crisis. In O. Cattaneo, G. Gereffi, & C. Staritz (Eds), *Global Value Chains in a Postcrisis World: A Development Perspective* (pp. 335–372). World Bank.
- Gervais, A. (2015). Trade and growth: A gravity approach. *Southern Economic Journal*, 82(2), 453–470. <https://doi.org/10.4284/0038-4038-2013.272>
- Grossman, G. M., & Helpman, E. (1991). Trade, knowledge spillovers, and growth. *European Economic Review*, 35(2–3), 517–526. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-2921\(91\)90153-A](https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-2921(91)90153-A)
- Gündoğdu, C., & Saracoğlu, D. Ş. (2016). *Participation of Turkey in Global Value Chains: An Analysis Based on World Input Output Database* (Working Paper No. 1610; ERC Working Papers). ERC - Economic Research Center, Middle East Technical University. <https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:met:wpaper:1610>
- Hagemeyer, J. (2018). Trade and Growth in the New Member States: The Role of Global Value Chains. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 54(11), 2630–2649. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1540496X.2017.1369878>
- Hauge, J. (2020). Industrial policy in the era of global value chains: Towards a developmentalist framework drawing on the industrialisation experiences of South Korea and Taiwan. *The World Economy*, 43(8), 2070–2092. <https://doi.org/10.1111/twec.12922>
- Herfindahl, O. C. (1950). *Concentration in the steel industry*. PhD Dissertation, Columbia University.
- Herzer, D. (2010). Outward FDI and economic growth. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 37(5), 476–494. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01443581011075424>
- Hirschman, A. O. (1945). *National power and the structure of foreign trade*. University of California Press.
- Hummels, D., Ishii, J., & Yi, K.-M. (2001). The nature and growth of vertical specialization in world trade. *Journal of International Economics, Trade and Wages*, 54(1), 75–96. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1996\(00\)00093-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1996(00)00093-3)
- Ivanova, N., & Ivanov, E. (2017). *The role of Bulgaria in global value chains*. Bulgarian National Bank Publications Division.
- Jangam, B. P., & Rath, B. N. (2021a). Do global value chains enhance or slog economic growth? *Applied Economics*, 53(36), 4148–4165. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2021.1897076>
- Jangam, B. P., & Rath, B. N. (2021b). Do global value chains enhance or slog economic growth? *Applied Economics*, 53(36), 4148–4165. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2021.1897076>

- Johnson, R. C., & Noguera, G. (2012). Accounting for intermediates: Production sharing and trade in value added. *Journal of International Economics*, 86(2), 224–236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinteco.2011.10.003>
- Johnson, R. C., & Noguera, G. (2017). A Portrait of Trade in Value-Added over Four Decades. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 99(5), 896–911. https://doi.org/10.1162/REST_a_00665
- Jones, L., Wang, Z., Degain, C., & Li, X. (2016). *The Similarities and Differences among Three Major Inter-Country Input-Output Databases and their Implications for Trade in Value-Added Estimates*. Presented at the 19th Annual Conference on Global Economic Analysis, Washington DC, USA; US International Trade Commission. Presented at the 19th Annual Conference on Global Economic Analysis, Washington DC, USA; US International Trade Commission. http://www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu/resources/res_display.asp?RecordID=4919
- Kapela, M. (2024). Poland in International Supply Chains in 1995-2020: Global Value Chains and Shift-Share Analysis. *European Research Studies*, XXVII(4), 1102–1121.
- Kaplinsky, R. (2000). Globalisation and Unequalisation: What Can Be Learned from Value Chain Analysis? *The Journal of Development Studies*, 37(2), 117–146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/713600071>
- Kee, H. L., Fernandes, A., & Winkler, D. (2020). *Determinants of Global Value Chain Participation: Cross-Country Evidence*. World Bank, Washington, DC. <https://doi.org/10.1596/1813-9450-9197>
- Keller, W. (2002). Trade and the Transmission of Technology. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 7(1), 5–24. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1013461025733>
- Kelly, G., & La Cava, G. (2014). The Structure of Australia's Domestic Supply Chain. *Research Discussion Papers*, (December). <https://www.rba.gov.au/publications/rdp/2014/2014-07/str-aus-dom.html>
- Kim, J., & Seo, B. (2025). Effects of Global Value Chain Participation on Economic Growth and Carbon Emissions: A Panel VAR Analysis. *International Economic Journal*, 39(1), 147–167. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10168737.2024.2448323>
- Kiss, T., Braun, E., & Sebestyén, T. (2025). Production network structure, specialization and unemployment: Measuring the structural resilience of national economies. *Structural Change and Economic Dynamics*, 72, 11–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.strueco.2024.11.009>
- Kiyota, K., Oikawa, K., & Yoshioka, K. (2017). The Global Value Chain and the Competitiveness of Asian Countries*. *Asian Economic Papers*, 16(3), 257–281. https://doi.org/10.1162/asep_a_00573
- Kılavuz, E., Erkekoglu, H., & Topcu, B. A. (2013). Globalizing Production Structure and Intra-Industry Trade: The Case of Turkey. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 3(4), 799–812.
- Koopman, R., Powers, W., Wang, Z., & Wei, S.-J. (2010). *Give Credit Where Credit Is Due: Tracing Value Added in Global Production Chains* (Working Paper No. 16426). National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w16426>
- Koopman, R., Wang, Z., & Wei, S.-J. (2014). Tracing Value-Added and Double Counting in Gross Exports. *American Economic Review*, 104(2), 459–494. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.104.2.459>
- Koppány, K. (2017a). A növekedés lehetőségei és kockázatai. Magyarország feldolgozóipari exportteljesítményének és ágazati szerkezetének vizsgálata, 2010–2014. *Közgazdasági Szemle*, 64(1), 17–53. <https://doi.org/10.18414/KSZ.2017.1.17>
- Koppány, K. (2017b). Estimating growth contributions by structural decomposition of input-output tables. *Acta Oeconomica*, 67(4), 605–642. <https://doi.org/10.1556/032.2017.67.4.6>
- Koppány, K. (2017c). *Makrogazdasági és regionális hatáselemzés multiplikátor modellel. Hazai alkalmazásokkal és szám példákkal, Excel környezetben*. Széchenyi István Egyetem, Komáromi Nyomda és Kiadó Kft.
- Koppány K., & Gáspár T. (2022). A szálak összeérnek...: A globális értékláncok jelentősége és mérésének dilemmái. In Szegedi K. (Ed.), *Szemelvények a BGE kutatásaiból* (pp. 151–156). Budapesti Gazdasági Egyetem. https://doi.org/10.29180/978-615-6342-49-2_17
- Kowalski, P., Gonzalez, J. L., Ragoussis, A., & Ugarte, C. (2015). Participation of Developing Countries in Global Value Chains: Implications for Trade and Trade-Related Policies. *OECD Trade Policy Papers*, 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5js331fw0xxn-en>
- Krugman, P. (1980). Scale Economies, Product Differentiation, and the Pattern of Trade. *The American Economic Review*, 70(5), 950–959.
- Krugman, P. (2017, June 14). A Finger Exercise On Hyperglobalization. *The New York Times*. <https://archive.nytimes.com/krugman.blogs.nytimes.com/2017/06/14/a-finger-exercise-on-hyperglobalization/>
- Lenzen, M., Kanemoto, K., Moran, D., & Geschke, A. (2012). Mapping the Structure of the World Economy. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 46(15), 8374–8381. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es300171x>
- Lenzen, M., Moran, D., Kanemoto, K., & Geschke, A. (2013). Building Eora: A Global Multi-Region Input-Output Database at High Country and Sector Resolution. *Economic Systems Research*, 25(1), 20–49. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09535314.2013.769938>

- Leontief, W. W. (1936). Quantitative Input and Output Relations in the Economic Systems of the United States. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 18(3), 105. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1927837>
- Leslie, D., & Reimer, S. (1999). Spatializing commodity chains. *Progress in Human Geography*, 23(3), 401–420. <https://doi.org/10.1177/030913259902300304>
- Lipsey, R. E. (2010). Measuring the Location of Production in a World of Intangible Productive Assets, Fdi, and Intrafirm Trade. *Review of Income and Wealth*, 56(s1), S99–S110. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-4991.2010.00385.x>
- Lipsey, R. E., Molinari, L., & Kravis, I. B. (1990). *Measures of Prices and Price Competitiveness in International Trade in Manufactured Goods* (Working Paper No. 3442). National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w3442>
- Los, B., Gouma, R., Timmer, M., & IJtsma, P. (2014). *Note on the Construction of WIOTs in Previous Year's Prices (December 2014-release)*. <https://dataverse.nl/api/access/datafile/199087>
- Los, B., & Timmer, M. (2018). *Measuring Bilateral Exports of Value Added: A Unified Framework* (No. W24896; p. w24896). National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w24896>
- Los, B., Timmer, M. P., & Vries, G. J. de. (2015). How Global Are Global Value Chains? A New Approach to Measure International Fragmentation. *Journal of Regional Science*, 55(1), 66–92. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jors.12121>
- Lucas, R. E. (1988). On the mechanics of economic development. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 22(1), 3–42. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932\(88\)90168-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932(88)90168-7)
- Lund, S., Manyika, J., Woetzel, J., Bughin, J., Krishnan, M., Seong, J., & Muir, M. (2019). *Globalization in transition: The future of trade and value chains* (No. 144). McKinsey Global Institute.
- Luzzati, D. S., Fagiolo, G., & Zema, S. M. (2026). Link or Languish? A Long-Run Empirical Analysis of Production Network Positioning, Embeddedness and Growth. *The World Economy*, n/a(n/a). <https://doi.org/10.1111/twec.70102>
- Magistretti, G., & Vassileva, I. (2024). *Bulgaria in Global Value Chains: Leveraging Integration with the EU* (No. 2024/23; Selected Issues Paper, p. 26). IMF. <https://doi.org/10.5089/9798400280580.018>
- Marčeta, M., & Bojnec, Š. (2023). Trade openness, global competitiveness, and catching up between the European Union countries. *Review of International Business and Strategy*, 33(4), 691–714. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RIBS-12-2021-0155>
- Melitz, M. J. (2003). The Impact of Trade on Intra-Industry Reallocations and Aggregate Industry Productivity. *Econometrica*, 71(6), 1695–1725. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0262.00467>
- Meng, B., Fang, Y., & Yamano, N. (2012). Measuring global value chains and regional economic integration: An international input-output approach. *IDE Discussion Papers, IDE Discussion Papers*, Article 362. <https://ideas.repec.org/p/jet/dpaper/dpaper362.html>
- Michie, J. (2017). *Advanced Introduction to Globalisation*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Milberg, W., & Winkler, D. E. (2010). *Trade Crisis and Recovery: Restructuring of Global Value Chains* (SSRN Scholarly Paper ID 1601769). Social Science Research Network. <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=1601769>
- Miroudot, S., & Nordström, H. (2020). Made in the World? Global Value Chains in the Midst of Rising Protectionism. *Review of Industrial Organization*, 57(2), 195–222. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11151-020-09781-z>
- Miroudot, S., & Ye, M. (2020). Multinational production in value-added terms. *Economic Systems Research*, 32(3), 395–412. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09535314.2019.1701997>
- Miroudot, S., & Ye, M. (2021). Decomposing value added in gross exports. *Economic Systems Research*, 33(1), 67–87. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09535314.2020.1730308>
- Morrison, A., & Pattinson, M. (2020). *Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3)* [Policy Brief]. https://www.interregeurope.eu/sites/default/files/inline/Smart_Specialisation_Strategy__S3__-_Policy_Brief.pdf
- Mudambi, R. (2008). Location, control and innovation in knowledge-intensive industries. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 8(5), 699–725. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jeg/lbn024>
- Ngai, L. R., & Samaniego, R. M. (2009). Mapping prices into productivity in multisector growth models. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 14(3), 183–204. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10887-009-9044-z>
- OECD. (2025a). *Inter-Country Input-Output tables*. OECD. <https://www.oecd.org/en/data/datasets/inter-country-input-output-tables.html>
- OECD. (2025b). *Trade in value-added*. OECD. <https://www.oecd.org/en/tiva.html>
- Oosterhaven, J. (2024). A decomposition of economic growth decompositions. *The Annals of Regional Science*, 73(4), 1395–1408. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00168-024-01309-7>
- P, J., Ashraf, S., & Umar, Z. (2023). Does global value chain participation induce economic growth? Evidence from panel threshold regression. *Applied Economics*, 55(24), 2788–2800. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2022.2106032>

- Pahl, S., & Timmer, M. P. (2020). Do Global Value Chains Enhance Economic Upgrading? A Long View. *The Journal of Development Studies*, 56(9), 1683–1705. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220388.2019.1702159>
- Peruško, I. V., Kovač, K., & Jošić, M. (2018). Croatia in Global Value Chains. *Surveys, Surveys*, Article 32. <https://ideas.repec.org/p/hnb/survey/32.html>
- Prasad, E. S. (2011). Rebalancing Growth in Asia. *International Finance*, 14(1), 27–66. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2362.2011.01276.x>
- Raei, F., & Ignatenko, A. (2019). Global Value Chains: What are the Benefits and Why Do Countries Participate? *IMF Working Papers*, 2019(018). <https://doi.org/10.5089/9781484392928.001.A001>
- Redmond-Tiedrez, I., & Rueda-Cantuche, J. M. (2019). *European Union inter-country supply, use and input-output tables—Full international and global accounts for research in input-output analysis (FIGARO)*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-statistical-working-papers/-/ks-tc-19-002>
- Revesz, T. (2025). On the identity of two solution algorithms of the ‘improved normalized squared differences’ matrix adjustment model. *Central European Journal of Operations Research*, 33(1), 315–332. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10100-024-00924-1>
- Révész T., & Koppány K. (2018). FOGALMAK, MÓDSZEREK: A nemzetgazdasági modellekben szereplő mátrixok kétirányú kiigazítási módszereiről. *SZIGMA Matematikai-közgazdasági folyóirat*, 49(3–4), 139–172.
- RIGVC UIBE,. (2022). *UIBE GVC Database*. <http://gvcdb.uibe.edu.cn>
- Rivera-Batiz, L. A., & Romer, P. M. (1991). International trade with endogenous technological change. *European Economic Review*, 35(4), 971–1001. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-2921\(91\)90048-N](https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-2921(91)90048-N)
- Rodríguez-Clare, A. (2010). Offshoring in a Ricardian World. *American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics*, 2(2), 227–258. <https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.2.2.227>
- Rodrik, D., Subramanian, A., & Trebbi, F. (2004). Institutions Rule: The Primacy of Institutions Over Geography and Integration in Economic Development. *Journal of Economic Growth*, 9(2), 131–165. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:JOEG.0000031425.72248.85>
- Romer, P. M. (1986). Increasing Returns and Long-Run Growth. *Journal of Political Economy*, 94(5), 1002–1037. <https://doi.org/10.1086/261420>
- Sala-i-Martin, X. X. (1996a). Regional cohesion: Evidence and theories of regional growth and convergence. *European Economic Review*, 40(6), 1325–1352. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-2921\(95\)00029-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-2921(95)00029-1)
- Sala-i-Martin, X. X. (1996b). The classical approach to convergence analysis. *Economic Journal*, 106(437), 1019–1036. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2235375>
- Șerbănel, C. I. (2015). Romania and its Position on the Global Value Chain. An Introductory Analysis. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 22nd International Economic Conference of Sibiu 2015, IECS 2015 ‘Economic Prospects in the Context of Growing Global and Regional Interdependencies’, 27, 136–143. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671\(15\)00982-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2212-5671(15)00982-X)
- Siddiqui, A., & Rehman, A. ur. (2017). The human capital and economic growth nexus: In East and South Asia. *Applied Economics*, 49(28), 2697–2710. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2016.1245841>
- Singh, T. (2010). Does International Trade Cause Economic Growth? A Survey. *The World Economy*, 33(11), 1517–1564. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9701.2010.01243.x>
- Steen-Olsen, K., Owen, A., Barrett, J., Guan, D., Hertwich, E. G., Lenzen, M., & Wiedmann, T. (2016). Accounting for value added embodied in trade and consumption: An intercomparison of global multiregional input–output databases. *Economic Systems Research*, 28(1), 78–94. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09535314.2016.1141751>
- Stehrer, R., & Stöllinger, R. (2013). *Positioning Austria in the Global Economy: Value Added Trade, International Production Sharing and Global Linkages* (Research Report 2013/14-02). FIW-Research Reports. <https://www.econstor.eu/handle/10419/121230>
- Stiglitz, J. E. (1967). A Two-Sector Two Class Model of Economic Growth. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 34(2), 227–238. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2296811>
- Strange, R., & Zucchella, A. (2017). Industry 4.0, global value chains and international business. *Multinational Business Review*, 25(3), 174–184. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MBR-05-2017-0028>
- Tajoli, L., & Felice, G. (2018). Global Value Chains Participation and Knowledge Spillovers in Developed and Developing Countries: An Empirical Investigation. *The European Journal of Development Research*, 30(3), 505–532. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41287-017-0127-y>
- Tang, C. F., Lai, Y. W., & Ozturk, I. (2015). How stable is the export-led growth hypothesis? Evidence from Asia’s Four Little Dragons. *Economic Modelling*, 44, 229–235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econmod.2014.09.022>
- Temin, P. (1997). The Golden Age of European growth: A review essay. *European Review of Economic History*, 1(1), 127–149. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1361491697000063>

- Timmer, M. P., Dietzenbacher, E., Los, B., Stehrer, R., & de Vries, G. J. (2015). An Illustrated User Guide to the World Input–Output Database: The Case of Global Automotive Production. *Review of International Economics*, 23(3), 575–605. <https://doi.org/10.1111/roie.12178>
- Timmer, M. P., Los, B., Stehrer, R., & de Vries, G. J. (2016). An Anatomy of the Global Trade Slowdown based on the WIOD 2016 Release. *An Anatomy of the Global Trade Slowdown Based on the WIOD 2016 Release, GGDC Research Memoranda*, 162. <http://www.ggdc.net/publications/memorandum/gd162.pdf>
- Timmer, M. P., & Ye, X. (2020). Accounting for growth and productivity in global value chains. In *Measuring Economic Growth and Productivity* (pp. 413–426). Academic Press. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-817596-5.00018-4>
- Timmer, M., & Vries, de, Gaaitzen. (2015). *Dutch Manufacturing Competing in Global Value Chains: Final report for Ministry of Economic Affairs and VNO/NCW*.
- Tukker, A., & Dietzenbacher, E. (2013). GLOBAL MULTIREGIONAL INPUT–OUTPUT FRAMEWORKS: AN INTRODUCTION AND OUTLOOK. *Economic Systems Research*, 25(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09535314.2012.761179>
- Tuzova, Y., & Qayum, F. (2016). Global oil glut and sanctions: The impact on Putin’s Russia. *Energy Policy*, 90, 140–151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2015.12.008>
- Uzawa, H. (1961). On a Two-Sector Model of Economic Growth. *The Review of Economic Studies*, 29(1), 40–47. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2296180>
- Vakhal, P. (2023). The evolution of downstream global value chains in Eastern Europe. *Society and Economy*, 270–292. <https://doi.org/10.1556/204.2023.00006>
- Vanek, J. (1971). Economic Growth and International Trade in Pure Theory. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 85(3), 377–390. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1885928>
- Voskoboynikov, I. B. (2017). Sources of long run economic growth in Russia before and after the global financial crisis. *Russian Journal of Economics*, 3(4), 348–365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ruje.2017.12.003>
- Wang, Z., Wei, S.-J., Yu, X., & Zhu, K. (2017a). *Characterizing Global Value Chains: Production Length and Upstreamness* (Working Paper No. 23261). National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w23261>
- Wang, Z., Wei, S.-J., Yu, X., & Zhu, K. (2017b). *Measures of Participation in Global Value Chains and Global Business Cycles* (Working Paper No. 23222). National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w23222>
- Wang, Z., Wei, S.-J., Yu, X., & Zhu, K. (2022). Global value chains over business cycles. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 126, 102643. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jimonfin.2022.102643>
- Woltjer, P., Gouma, R., & Timmer, M. P. (2021). *Long-run World Input-Output Database: Version 1.1 Sources and Methods GGDC RESEARCH MEMORANDUM 190*. https://www.rug.nl/ggdc/html_publications/memorandum/gd190.pdf
- WTO. (2021). *Global Value Chain Development Report 2021: Beyond Production* (0 edn). Asian Development Bank. <https://doi.org/10.22617/TCS210400-2>
- WTO. (2023). *Global Value Chain Development Report 2023: Resilient and Sustainable Global Value Chains in Turbulent Times*. WTO iLibrary. <https://doi.org/10.30875/9789287075673>
- WTO. (2025). *Global Value Chain Development Report 2025: Rewiring GVCs in a changing global economy*. WTO iLibrary. <https://doi.org/10.30875/9789287085641>
- Yanikkaya, H. (2003). Trade openness and economic growth: A cross-country empirical investigation. *Journal of Development Economics*, 72(1), 57–89. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3878\(03\)00068-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3878(03)00068-3)
- Zhuqing, M. (2022). Global Value Chains and economic growth: A nonlinear analysis. *The Singapore Economic Review*, 67(03), 985–1004. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1142/S0217590821450028>

Appendices

Appendix A: Vectors and matrices based on the example world input-output table for the year $t-1$ at current prices

$f^D =$	$f^E =$	$f =$	$F^D =$	$F^E =$	$F =$
$\begin{bmatrix} 120 \\ 660 \\ 2,020 \\ 300 \\ 6,070 \\ 15,400 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 30 \\ 1,700 \\ 150 \\ 150 \\ 480 \\ 150 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 150 \\ 2,360 \\ 2,170 \\ 450 \\ 6,550 \\ 15,550 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 90 & 30 & 0 & 0 \\ 270 & 390 & 0 & 0 \\ 1,050 & 970 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 250 & 50 \\ 0 & 0 & 3,150 & 2,920 \\ 0 & 0 & 8,700 & 6,700 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 20 & 10 \\ 0 & 0 & 1,400 & 300 \\ 0 & 0 & 90 & 60 \\ 120 & 30 & 0 & 0 \\ 260 & 220 & 0 & 0 \\ 100 & 50 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 90 & 30 & 20 & 10 \\ 270 & 390 & 1,400 & 300 \\ 1,050 & 970 & 90 & 60 \\ 120 & 30 & 250 & 50 \\ 260 & 220 & 3,150 & 2,920 \\ 100 & 50 & 8,700 & 6,700 \end{bmatrix}$
$\langle f^D \rangle =$	$\langle f^E \rangle =$	$\langle f \rangle =$	$\langle F^D \rangle =$	$\langle F^E \rangle =$	$\langle F \rangle =$
$\begin{bmatrix} 120 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 660 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2,020 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 300 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 6,070 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 15,400 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 30 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1,700 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 150 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 150 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 480 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 150 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 150 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2,360 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2,170 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 450 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 6,550 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 15,550 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 150 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2,360 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2,170 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 450 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 6,550 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 15,550 \end{bmatrix}$	
$\langle c \rangle =$	$I =$	$A =$	$A^D =$	$A^E =$	
$\begin{bmatrix} 0.400 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.227 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.585 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.483 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.364 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.598 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.150 & 0.031 & 0.008 & 0.050 & 0.003 & 0.002 \\ 0.117 & 0.167 & 0.069 & 0.033 & 0.057 & 0.009 \\ 0.100 & 0.088 & 0.223 & 0.042 & 0.008 & 0.006 \\ 0.100 & 0.008 & 0.008 & 0.100 & 0.025 & 0.002 \\ 0.083 & 0.442 & 0.046 & 0.167 & 0.357 & 0.085 \\ 0.050 & 0.038 & 0.062 & 0.125 & 0.185 & 0.298 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.150 & 0.031 & 0.008 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.117 & 0.167 & 0.069 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.100 & 0.088 & 0.223 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.100 & 0.025 & 0.002 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.167 & 0.357 & 0.085 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.125 & 0.185 & 0.298 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.050 & 0.003 & 0.002 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.033 & 0.057 & 0.009 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.042 & 0.008 & 0.006 \\ 0.100 & 0.008 & 0.008 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.083 & 0.442 & 0.046 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.050 & 0.038 & 0.062 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$	
$L =$	$L^D =$	$F^{D\%} =$	$F^{E\%} =$	$F^{\%} =$	
$\begin{bmatrix} 1.197 & 0.057 & 0.019 & 0.073 & 0.016 & 0.007 \\ 0.219 & 1.294 & 0.129 & 0.095 & 0.132 & 0.034 \\ 0.193 & 0.169 & 1.309 & 0.088 & 0.042 & 0.020 \\ 0.148 & 0.047 & 0.021 & 1.133 & 0.052 & 0.011 \\ 0.390 & 0.966 & 0.215 & 0.418 & 1.726 & 0.225 \\ 0.243 & 0.352 & 0.183 & 0.330 & 0.477 & 1.490 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 1.185 & 0.046 & 0.016 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.180 & 1.218 & 0.110 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.173 & 0.143 & 1.302 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1.121 & 0.046 & 0.009 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.328 & 1.624 & 0.197 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.286 & 0.437 & 1.478 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0.667 & 0.333 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.824 & 0.176 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.600 & 0.400 \\ 0.800 & 0.200 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.542 & 0.458 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.667 & 0.333 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0.600 & 0.200 & 0.133 & 0.067 \\ 0.114 & 0.165 & 0.593 & 0.127 \\ 0.484 & 0.447 & 0.041 & 0.028 \\ 0.267 & 0.067 & 0.556 & 0.111 \\ 0.040 & 0.034 & 0.481 & 0.446 \\ 0.006 & 0.003 & 0.559 & 0.431 \end{bmatrix}$		

Appendix B: Vectors and matrices based on the example world input-output table for the year t at previous year's prices

$f^D =$	$f^E =$	$f =$	$F^D =$	$F^E =$	$F =$
$\begin{bmatrix} 140 \\ 690 \\ 2,060 \\ 330 \\ 6,300 \\ 15,570 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 50 \\ 1,840 \\ 170 \\ 160 \\ 540 \\ 190 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 190 \\ 2,530 \\ 2,230 \\ 490 \\ 6,840 \\ 15,760 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 110 & 30 & 0 & 0 \\ 280 & 410 & 0 & 0 \\ 1,080 & 980 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 280 & 50 \\ 0 & 0 & 3,300 & 3,000 \\ 0 & 0 & 8,820 & 6,750 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 40 & 10 \\ 0 & 0 & 1,500 & 340 \\ 0 & 0 & 100 & 70 \\ 130 & 30 & 0 & 0 \\ 290 & 250 & 0 & 0 \\ 120 & 70 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 110 & 30 & 40 & 10 \\ 280 & 410 & 1,500 & 340 \\ 1,080 & 980 & 100 & 70 \\ 130 & 30 & 280 & 50 \\ 290 & 250 & 3,300 & 3,000 \\ 120 & 70 & 8,820 & 6,750 \end{bmatrix}$
$\langle f^D \rangle =$	$\langle f^E \rangle =$	$\langle f \rangle =$	$\langle F^D \rangle =$	$\langle F^E \rangle =$	$\langle F \rangle =$
$\begin{bmatrix} 140 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 690 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2,060 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 330 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 6,300 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 15,570 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 50 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1,840 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 170 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 160 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 540 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 190 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 190 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2,530 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2,230 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 490 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 6,840 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 15,760 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 190 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2,530 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2,230 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 490 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 6,840 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 15,760 \end{bmatrix}$	
$\langle c \rangle =$	$I =$	$A =$	$A^D =$	$A^E =$	
$\begin{bmatrix} 0.419 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.225 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.584 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.473 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.369 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.599 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.151 & 0.031 & 0.008 & 0.050 & 0.003 & 0.002 \\ 0.118 & 0.168 & 0.070 & 0.034 & 0.059 & 0.009 \\ 0.090 & 0.087 & 0.223 & 0.042 & 0.008 & 0.007 \\ 0.090 & 0.008 & 0.008 & 0.110 & 0.025 & 0.002 \\ 0.084 & 0.443 & 0.046 & 0.167 & 0.350 & 0.085 \\ 0.049 & 0.037 & 0.062 & 0.123 & 0.185 & 0.297 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.151 & 0.031 & 0.008 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.118 & 0.168 & 0.070 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.090 & 0.087 & 0.223 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.110 & 0.025 & 0.002 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.167 & 0.350 & 0.085 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.123 & 0.185 & 0.297 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.050 & 0.003 & 0.002 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.034 & 0.059 & 0.009 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.042 & 0.008 & 0.007 \\ 0.090 & 0.008 & 0.008 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.084 & 0.443 & 0.046 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.049 & 0.037 & 0.062 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$	
$L =$	$L^D =$	$F^{D\%} =$	$F^{E\%} =$	$F^{\%} =$	
$\begin{bmatrix} 1.197 & 0.057 & 0.019 & 0.074 & 0.016 & 0.007 \\ 0.220 & 1.298 & 0.131 & 0.099 & 0.134 & 0.034 \\ 0.176 & 0.168 & 1.309 & 0.089 & 0.042 & 0.020 \\ 0.135 & 0.047 & 0.021 & 1.145 & 0.052 & 0.011 \\ 0.382 & 0.961 & 0.214 & 0.421 & 1.710 & 0.223 \\ 0.235 & 0.348 & 0.183 & 0.329 & 0.471 & 1.487 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 1.186 & 0.046 & 0.016 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.181 & 1.220 & 0.112 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.157 & 0.142 & 1.301 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1.134 & 0.046 & 0.009 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.329 & 1.606 & 0.195 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.284 & 0.431 & 1.475 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0.800 & 0.200 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.815 & 0.185 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.588 & 0.412 \\ 0.813 & 0.188 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.537 & 0.463 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.632 & 0.368 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.579 & 0.158 & 0.211 & 0.053 \\ 0.111 & 0.162 & 0.593 & 0.134 \\ 0.484 & 0.439 & 0.045 & 0.031 \\ 0.265 & 0.061 & 0.571 & 0.102 \\ 0.042 & 0.037 & 0.482 & 0.439 \\ 0.008 & 0.004 & 0.560 & 0.428 \end{bmatrix}$		

Appendix C: Codes and names of countries, productive industries and final user sectors in WIOD

Country code	Country	Industry code	Industry
AUS	Australia	A01	Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities
AUT	Austria	A02	Forestry and logging
BEL	Belgium	A03	Fishing and aquaculture
BGR	Bulgaria	B	Mining and quarrying
BRA	Brazil	C10-C12	Manufacture of food products, beverages and tobacco products
CAN	Canada	C13-C15	Manufacture of textiles, wearing apparel and leather products
CHE	Switzerland	C16	Manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture; manufacture of articles of straw and plaiting materials
CHN	China, People's Republic of	C17	Manufacture of paper and paper products
CYP	Cyprus	C18	Printing and reproduction of recorded media
CZE	Czech Republic	C19	Manufacture of coke and refined petroleum products
DEU	Germany	C20	Manufacture of chemicals and chemical products
DNK	Denmark	C21	Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations
ESP	Spain	C22	Manufacture of rubber and plastic products
EST	Estonia	C23	Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products
FIN	Finland	C24	Manufacture of basic metals
FRA	France	C25	Manufacture of fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment
GBR	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	C26	Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products
GRC	Greece	C27	Manufacture of electrical equipment
HRV	Croatia	C28	Manufacture of machinery and equipment n.e.c.
HUN	Hungary	C29	Manufacture of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers
IDN	Indonesia	C30	Manufacture of other transport equipment
IND	India	C31_C32	Manufacture of furniture; other manufacturing
IRL	Ireland	C33	Repair and installation of machinery and equipment
ITA	Italy	D35	Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply
JPN	Japan	E36	Water collection, treatment and supply
KOR	Republic of Korea	E37-E39	Sewerage; waste collection, treatment and disposal activities; materials recovery; remediation activities and other waste management services
LTU	Lithuania	F	Construction
LUX	Luxembourg	G45	Wholesale and retail trade and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles
LVA	Latvia	G46	Wholesale trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles
MEX	Mexico	G47	Retail trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles
MLT	Malta	H49	Land transport and transport via pipelines
NLD	Netherlands	H50	Water transport
NOR	Norway	H51	Air transport
POL	Poland	H52	Warehousing and support activities for transportation
PRT	Portugal	H53	Postal and courier activities
ROU	Romania	I	Accommodation and food service activities
RUS	Russian Federation	J58	Publishing activities
SVK	Slovakia	J59_J60	Motion picture, video and television programme production, sound recording and music publishing activities; programming and broadcasting activities
SVN	Slovenia	J61	Telecommunications
SWE	Sweden	J62_J63	Computer programming, consultancy and related activities; information service activities
TUR	Turkey	K64	Financial service activities, except insurance and pension funding
TWN	Taiwan	K65	Insurance, reinsurance and pension funding, except compulsory social security
USA	United States	K66	Activities auxiliary to financial services and insurance activities
ROW	Rest of the World	L68	Real estate activities
TOT	TOTAL	M69_M70	Legal and accounting activities; activities of head offices; management consultancy activities
		M71	Architectural and engineering activities; technical testing and analysis
		M72	Scientific research and development
		M73	Advertising and market research
		M74_M75	Other professional, scientific and technical activities; veterinary activities
		N	Administrative and support service activities
		O84	Public administration and defence; compulsory social security
		P85	Education
		Q	Human health and social work activities
		R_S	Other service activities
		T	Activities of households as employers; undifferentiated goods- and services-producing activities of households for own use
		U	Activities of extraterritorial organizations and bodies
		CONS_h	Final consumption expenditure by households
		CONS_np	Final consumption expenditure by non-profit organisations serving households (NPISH)
		CONS_g	Final consumption expenditure by government
		GFCF	Gross fixed capital formation
		INVEN	Changes in inventories and valuables
		II_fob	Total intermediate consumption
		TXSP	taxes less subsidies on products
		EXP_adj	Cif/ fob adjustments on exports
		PURR	Direct purchases abroad by residents
		PURNR	Purchases on the domestic territory by non-residents
		VA	Value added at basic prices
		IntITM	International Transport Margins
		GO	Output at basic prices

Appendix D: Codes and names of countries, productive industries and final user sectors in Long-run WIOD

Country code	Country	Industry code	Industry
AUS	Australia	AtB	Agriculture, Hunting, Forestry and Fishing
AUT	Austria	C	Mining and Quarrying
BEL	Belgium	D15t16	Food, Beverages and Tobacco
BRA	Brazil	D17t19	Textiles, Textile, Leather and Footwear
CAN	Canada	D21t22	Pulp, Paper, Paper, Printing and Publishing
CHN	China	D23	Coke, Refined Petroleum and Nuclear Fuel
DEU	Germany	D24	Chemicals and Chemical Products
DNK	Denmark	D25	Rubber and Plastics
ESP	Spain	D26	Other Non-Metallic Mineral
FIN	Finland	D27t28	Basic Metals and Fabricated Metal
FRA	France	D29	Machinery, Nec
GBR	United Kingdom	D30t33	Electrical and Optical Equipment
GRC	Greece	D34t35	Transport Equipment
HKG	Hong Kong	Dnec	Manufacturing, Nec; Recycling
IND	India	E	Electricity, Gas and Water Supply
IRL	Ireland	F	Construction
ITA	Italy	G	Wholesale and Retail Trade
JPN	Japan	H	Hotels and Restaurants
KOR	Korea, Republic of	I60t63	Transport and Storage
MEX	Mexico	I64	Post and Telecommunications
NLD	Netherlands	J	Financial Intermediation
PRT	Portugal	K	Real Estate, Renting and Business Activities
SWE	Sweden	LtQ	Community Social and Personal Services
TWN	Taiwan	xCONS_h	Household consumption
USA	United States of America	xCONS_g	Government consumption
xROW	Rest-of-World	xGFCF	Gross Fixed Capital Formation
xTOT	TOTAL	xINV	Changes in Inventories
		xX	Exports
		xM	Imports
		xII	Total Intermediate Inputs
		xVA	Total Value Added
		xTXSP	Taxes Less Subsidies on Products
		xSD	Statistical Discrepancy
		xPURNR	Purchases on the Domestic Territory by Non-Residents
		xPURR	Direct Purchases Abroad by Residents
		xGO	Total Gross Output